

《新型纳米高新科技改变现有灭杀新冠病毒的疫苗、抗体、药物之类模式：诺贝尔奖成果 C60 更新换代产品改变灭杀新冠病毒的路径——充分的厌氧菌发酵改变下水道系统污染》

New Nano-Technology to Change Existing Model of Vaccine, Antibodies, and Drugs to Kill New Coronavirus: Nobel Prize Achievement C60 Innovative Product Changes the Path to kill New Coronavirus

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【内容提要】新冠病毒造成了肆虐全人类的严重后果，现在临床医学治疗的主流观点，是没有特效药，需要疫苗解决新型冠状病毒的感染问题，让人体免疫系统控制新冠病毒。问题是新冠病毒的变异愈演愈烈，疫苗研发速度永远跟不上新冠病毒变异的速度。出路只能是 C60 这种小于病毒的单质分子，进入病毒，就像病毒进入人体那样的，重组病毒的 RNA，使得被迫变成无害化的另一种物质。即便如此，也需要对于人畜禽的粪便污水垃圾进行厌氧菌发酵的密封杀毒灭菌处理，确保现在已经发现的下水道体系长年累月污染水资源问题被完全彻底的解决好，把厕所确认为完整性的处理粪便污水垃圾系统，而非仅仅是大小便的个体空间。尤其是下水道体系和给排水系统必须坚定不移的杜绝“有毒排放”，确定全部下水道体系排放的是无害化“中水”。为此，需要规定现有的地下管廊系统不允许粪便污水垃圾流动化进行绕场一周的多次连续性污染环境，必须就地建立化粪池与沼气池一体化设备，就近完成粪便污水垃圾的无害化处理。一句话，把病毒细菌污染源就地完成无害化处理。

Abstract

The new coronavirus has resulted in the serious consequences of Wuhan pneumonia ravaging the entire human race. Now the mainstream view of clinical medicine for the treatment of Wuhan pneumonia is that there is no effective drug, and that vaccine is needed to address the problem of infection of the new coronavirus and allow human immune system to take control of the coronavirus. The problem is that the mutation is getting worse, and vaccine development can never keep up with the rate of viral mutation. The only way out is for C60, a monomeric

molecule smaller than the virus, to enter the virus like how the virus entered the human body, and recombining the viral RNA, so that is forced to become a harmless alternative substance. Even so, there is a need for anaerobic fermentation of human and livestock feces and sewage waste with sealed sterilization to ensure that the problem of chronic water pollution in the sewerage system, which has been identified for many years, is utterly and completely solved, and to recognize toilets as a complete system for the treatment of feces and sewage waste, instead of just individual spaces for defecation. In particular, sewerage systems and drainage systems must be steadfast in eliminating "toxic discharges" to ensure that all sewerage systems discharge harmless "reclaimed water". To this end, it is necessary to provide that the existing underground pipeline system does not allow the flow of fecal sewage waste that could pollute the environment for multiple times a week, and that septic and biogas digesters must be built in situ, so that the disposal of fecal sewage waste can be carried out in the vicinity of the site. In summary, a complete and harmless treatment of viral bacterial contamination sources in situ.

【关键词】 C60 富勒烯聚磷酸二钠 新冠病毒 疫苗 抗体 下水道 水资源污染 沼气池 厌氧菌发酵 中水

**【Keywords】 C60 Fullerene Disodium polyphosphate 2019-nCoV
Vaccine Antibody Sewage Water Pollution biogas Digester
Anaerobic fermentation Water**

2020年5月20日世界卫生大会刚刚结束以后，全球感染新冠肺炎病毒的人数超过了五百万，病逝人数超过了32万人，新冠肺炎传染病大流行第二波疫情，也在中国等地跃跃欲试，倒

逼着世界各国争分夺秒的探索发现治疗新冠肺炎的方案，痛下决心研发药到病除的抗击新型冠状病毒传染病那种药品，需要我们人类了解病毒，知己知彼百战不殆。

On May 20, 2020, just after the World Health Assembly, the number of people infected with the new coronavirus worldwide exceeded 5 million, and the number of people who died exceeded 320,000. The second wave of the pandemic is about to emerge in China, forcing countries around the world to race against time to explore and discover a cure for the new virus, determining to develop drugs to eliminate the new coronavirus. To achieve that, we need human beings to understand the virus, as knowing is half the battle.

病毒是地球上古老的有机物与生命体过渡阶段生物体，它们种类繁多、数量巨大，对地球的生态有着重要的作用。人类与病毒一直相生相伴，病毒在给人类带来灾难的同时，也在造福人类。搞清楚病毒与人类的恩恩怨怨，传递保护好地球生态圈、保护好野生动物就是保护人类的科学道理，树立团结一心战胜困难的信念。这一点，要求我们不能以恐惧和仇恨的心态去“敌视病毒”，不应该就像俗语所说的要消灭一切害人虫，全无敌。许多害人虫都是中药材，可以治病救人。

Viruses are ancient organisms of the Earth in the transition stage between organisms and life forms. They are numerous in species and in numbers, and have an important role in the ecology of the Earth. Human beings have always been in constant companionship with viruses, and while viruses bring disaster to humanity, they are also benefiting it. To understand the entanglement between the virus and humankind, to convey the scientific reasoning that protecting the earth's ecosphere and wildlife is to protect mankind, and to establish the belief that unity overcomes difficulties. This requires that we not be "hostile to the virus" or bear a mentality of fear and hatred, and that requires we not, as the saying goes, eliminate all vermin and eradicate all oppositions. Many of the pests have medicinal properties that can cure and save people.

我们关注到世界卫生组织官方网站公布信息：截至 2020 年 5 月 11 日已经官方备案了 110 个正在研发的新冠肺炎疫苗，其中已经进入临床试验的共有 8 个，采用的技术平台分别是非复制性病毒载体、RNA、灭活疫苗和 DNA。尚未进入临床试验的 102 个备案疫苗中，采用比较多的技术平台包括 DNA、非复制性病毒载体、蛋白质亚基、复制病毒载体、RNA 等。其中 DNA 技术平台疫苗 9 种、非复制性病毒载体 13 种，蛋白质亚基 38 种，复制病毒载体 12 种，RNA 技术平台 14 种，其他采用的技术平台还包括灭活疫苗、减毒活病毒、类病毒颗粒等。而美国洛斯阿拉莫斯国家实验室 2020 年 4 月 30 日在“生物学论文档案网” (BioRxiv) 上刊登了一份 33 页的报告，指出新冠病毒已发生了突变，这种变异病毒株自 2020 年 2 月初开始从中国到欧洲传播，之后传到美国和加拿大等地区，直到 3 月底成为全球感染个案的主要病毒株。而这种病毒株似乎更具传染性。该实验室与美国杜克大学 (Duke University) 和英国谢菲尔德大学 (The University of Sheffield) 合作，在分析数千个新冠病毒序列后，确定病毒目前有 14 种变异。围绕着不超过 15 个类型的病毒株，居然有不少于二百种疫苗在研发，足以证明许多疫苗是重复性的浪费，也是对于病毒认识不到位的表现。对此，我们的路线图是探索发现不同于疫苗的特效方式，对于所有的危害人类生命健康的病毒，进行一致性的瓦解。这就是 1996 年诺贝尔化学奖成果 C60 富勒烯的升级版产品，即富勒烯聚磷酸二钠，维护人体细胞组织和优化人体免疫系统，把人体本身的健康水平向前推进一个新的高度。

We are concerned about the information published on the official website of the World Health Organization (WHO): as of May 11, 2020, 110 new coronavirus vaccines have been officially filed, of which 8 have entered clinical trials, using non-replicating viral vectors, RNA, inactivated vaccines and DNA; among the 102 filed vaccines that have not entered clinical trials, more technology platforms were used, including DNA, non-replicating viral vectors, protein subunits, replicating viral vectors, RNA and etc. Among them, the DNA technology platform has 9 vaccines, 13 non-replicating viral vectors, 38 protein subunits, 12 replicating viral vectors and 14 RNA technology platforms, and other technology platforms used

include inactivated vaccines, live attenuated viruses and viral-like particles. The Los Alamos National Laboratory published a 33-page report on 30 February 2020 on BioRxiv, stating that the new coronavirus had mutated and that the mutant strain began to spread from China to Europe in early February 2020, then to the United States and Canada, before becoming the leading strain of infection worldwide by the end of March. And this strain seems more contagious. The lab, in collaboration with Duke University in the US and The University of Sheffield in the UK, determined that the virus currently has 14 mutations after analyzing thousands of the new coronavirus sequences. The fact that no fewer than 200 vaccines are being developed around no more than 15 strains of the virus is evidence that many vaccines are a waste of duplication and a sign of poor knowledge of the virus. Our roadmap for this is to explore ways to discover special effects that are different from vaccines and to disintegrate all viruses that are harmful to human life and health in a consistent manner. This is an upgraded product based on the result of 1996 Nobel Prize for Chemistry, fullerene disodium phosphonate, which maintains the body's cellular organization and optimizes the body's immune system, taking the body's own health to a new level.

一、新冠病毒与人体细胞的适应性要弱于 C60 与人体细胞的关联度

Relevance of the adaptability of Covid-19 to human cells lesser than C60 to human cells

病毒是最早期的生命结构，严格意义上说它只是半生命体，像这次发生于武汉的新型肺炎冠状病毒，就是需要以人体的细胞为载体的，反过来危害人类的肺部细胞，让人体免疫系统还没有发生“细胞因子风暴”的时候，肺部细胞组织已经发生了致命性的病变，肺黏膜已经不正常了。而在临床医学实践当中发现，微生物感染中，近 75%的传染病是由病毒引起的。只是临床医学的实践检验了一个基本的事实，那就是富勒烯 C60 要比病毒在宇宙空间、在地球上更早一些出现，

在人体细胞形成的过程中更加处于可以进入“人体细胞基础”的位置和序列，能够先于病毒危害人体细胞的时间段，就首先瓦解了病毒的“衣壳”，就可以进入病毒的核酸酶层次，把病毒在人体细胞里面的破坏性第一时间损坏了。这样的科学实验，在小白鼠、小蜜蜂和猪牛羊鸡猴子身上的实验，结果如出一辙。

The virus is the earliest living structure, though strictly speaking it is only semi-life, like the new coronavirus that occurred in Wuhan, is in need of human cells as a carrier, then in turn harming human lung cells, causing lethal pathological changes to the lung tissues before the human immune system initiated "cytokine storm". And in clinical medical practice, it is found that nearly 75% of microbial infections are caused by viruses. It is just the practice of clinical medicine examined a fundamental truth, which is that fullerenes C60 appeared on Earth earlier than viruses in space, and is in a position to enter the position and sequence of human cellular base during the process of human cell formation, so that it can disintegrate the "shell" of the virus before the virus damages the human body cells. Such scientific experiments on mice, bees, and pigs, cows, and chickens, monkeys, turned out just as well.

当然，我们最关心的是病毒变异，也是目前危害全人类的疫情最大不确定性的因素，由于是单链 RNA，很容易发生变异，从病毒进化的生物学方向看，变异会朝着高传染的方向恶化，在变异当中强化毒性及其给人类造成了比较高的死亡率。这方面的例证，有位于美国新墨西哥州的洛斯阿拉莫斯国家实验室 (LANL) 的研究人员称，病毒的突变株于 2020 年 2 月初开始在欧洲传播，自那以后，它就进入了美国，到 3 月份就已经成为美国东海岸最常见、最具侵略性的菌株。科学家们说它现在是世界上主要的菌株，该研究指出这颗超级菌株从意大利杀入纽约，开启了一场比珍珠港事件和 9.11 事件还更猛烈的攻击。美国这一新研究结果，与一个月前英国剑桥大学的研究成果有相似之处：新型冠状病毒的扩散过程中，病毒持续变异，根据研究发现，最致

命的突变病毒种类，在 4 个国家的病患身上发现，包括中国浙江省、西班牙、意大利以及美国纽约。也有研究指出，不仅各个地区的病毒不同，每个族裔的感染率和死亡率也不相同。

Of course, we are most concerned about the viral mutation, which is also the most uncertain factor in the current pneumonia epidemic in Wuhan that poses a threat to the entire human race. Since is a single-stranded RNA that is susceptible to mutation, the evolutionary biology of the virus suggests that mutations worsen towards high infectivity, intensifying the toxicity of the mutations and causing a relatively high mortality rate in humans. As an example of this, researchers at Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) in New Mexico, USA, say that the mutant strain of the virus began spreading in Europe in early February 2020, and since then it has made its way into the US, becoming the most common and aggressive strain on the US East Coast by March. Scientists say it's now the world's leading strain, and the study notes that the super strain slaughtered its way into New York from Italy, launching an attack that was even more violent than Pearl Harbor and 911. The new U.S. study has similar findings to those from the University of Cambridge in the United Kingdom a month ago: the new coronavirus, , continues to mutate during the spread of Wuhan pneumonia, and according to the study the most lethal mutant virus species was found in patients from four countries, including Zhejiang Province, China, Spain, Italy and New York, USA. It has also been noted that not only does the virus vary from one region to another, but also that the infection and mortality rates vary from one ethnicity to another.

从 2019 年到 2020 年持续的病毒感染造成了的全球扩散，病毒一直都在持续变异，根据中国大陆浙江大学医学院的流行病学调查研究发现，最致命的突变病毒种类，在中国浙江省、西班牙、意大利和美国纽约病患身上发现，最毒病毒株的病毒量，是最温和病毒株的 270 倍，而最温和病毒株，大多在非纽约的美国病患身上发现。台湾感染症医学会理事长黄立民说：“病毒

株比较独立比较强，所以造成他比较严重，还是因为他们的感控做的，刚开始做的不是那么好，所以病毒传的很广泛。

The virus, which has been continuously mutating from 2019 to 2020, caused the global spread of Wuhan pneumonia. According to the epidemiological study of Zhejiang University Medical School in China, the most virulent mutant virus species, found in Zhejiang Province, China, Spain, Italy, and New York patients in the United States, was 270 times more virulent than the mildest strain; while the mildest strain is mostly found in non-New York patients in the United States. Huang Limin, President of the Infectious Disease Society of Taiwan, said: "The virus strains are relatively independent and fierce, so is the severity; or perhaps that the infectious control was poorly done in the beginning, allowing the virus spread widely.

最重要的是，病毒太多的变异当中，究竟是哪一只变异病毒现在比较厉害的威胁人们，这个目前也还没有办法从实验室去百分之百的确认。”美国新墨西哥州的洛斯阿拉莫斯国家实验室，美国和英国的研究人员得出结论，导致的病毒，目前有数百种变体，一种特殊的“D614G 突变”占主导地位，使得病毒突变的生长速度更快，传染性更强。到目前为止，科学家仍不清楚，这对病毒的防控和疫苗开发，影响有多大。台湾感染症医学会理事长黄立民说：“这个病毒株再怎么变，它的传染模式是不会变的，它还是飞沫、接触传染为主。病毒株的改变，最大的关键还是在于病毒株，对于人类产生的免疫反应，有没有逃脱的效果。”2020年4月初，剑桥大学的研究指出，病毒变异成三种毒株的A、B、C版本。不仅各个地区的病毒不同，每个族裔的感染率和死亡率也不同。英国的非洲裔及其他少数族裔，死于新冠疾病的风险，比白人高2到4倍。美国的研究则显示，西语裔及非裔人口，受疫情打击较大。

Most importantly, there are so many mutations of the virus that there is no way to confirm 100 percent from the lab which one of them is the most powerful threat to people right now." Researchers at Los Alamos National Laboratory in

New Mexico, USA, and the UK have concluded that the virus, which causes Wuhan pneumonia, currently has hundreds of variants, dominated by a specific "D614G mutation", making the virus mutations grow faster and more infectious. So far, it is unclear to scientists how much of an impact this will have on virus prevention and control and vaccine development. Huang Limin, President of the Infectious Disease Society of Taiwan, said: "No matter how this strain changes, its mode of transmission will not change, it is still respiratory droplet and contact transmission. The biggest key to the change in strain is still the strain, and whether it can effectively escape from the immune response in humans." In early April 2020, research from the University of Cambridge showed that the virus mutated into three strains, known as A, B, and C. Not only does the virus vary from region to region, but the infection and mortality rates vary for each ethnic group. African and other minorities in the UK have a 2 to 4 times higher risk of dying from the virus than caucasians. Studies in the United States have shown that Hispanic and African-American populations, on the other hand, have been hit harder by the epidemic.

我们的临床医学实验证明，跨越人们族群差异的富勒烯 C60，尤其是我们独一无二无毒化富勒烯聚磷酸二钠喷雾剂，能够对于一切病毒株及其变异，还有 SARS 病毒，乃至所有的冠状病毒，都是行之有效的瓦解。这是划时代的发现，也是对于 1996 年诺贝尔医学与化学奖成果富勒烯的进一步开发，耗费了数以百计人们组成的科学家团队二十多年的精力。

Our clinical trials have shown that fullerenes C60, which crosses ethnic boundaries, and in particular our unique non-toxicized fullerenes disodium phosphonate spray, are effective against all Covid-19 strains and their variants, as well as the SARS virus and all coronaviruses. It is a landmark discovery and a major progress of fullerenes that is based on the 1996 Nobel Prize in medicine and

chemistry, which took more than two decades of work by a team of scientists made up of hundreds of people.

在理论上对于这种现象的解释，很简单，那就是富勒烯 C_{60} 与生命起源的关联度，要比病毒与生命的关联度，更加基础和底层，使得 C_{60} 分子进入人体细胞和病毒的速度，远远高于病毒进入人体细胞的活动能力。这种适应性坐标系上的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠 C_{60} 优越性，使得 C_{60} 就像是一个小小的微型机器人，在人体细胞和组织器官里面自由流动，不断的优化组合人体细胞的良性循环和新陈代谢，包括对于人体免疫系统的识别率进行提升，这也是 C_{60} 抗衰老的秘籍之一。在这种流动性当中， C_{60} 能够识别不同于人体细胞的病毒，对于病毒改变人体细胞的“特洛伊木马”能够及时性探索发现，并且直截了当的深入虎穴，进入病毒内部瓦解了病毒的核酸酶，让病毒无害化了。与此同时，把这种无害化的病毒，在人体新陈代谢过程中，排泄出去。我们的厌氧菌发酵罐，作为厕所革命的完整性系统，就地把人畜禽的粪便污水垃圾进行无害化处理，确保厌氧菌发酵罐排出去的是无害化的中水，而非包含病毒细菌危害人体的污染物。

The theoretical explanation for this phenomenon is simply that the degree of association of fullerenes C_{60} with the origin of life is more basic and substrate than the degree of association of viruses with life, allowing C_{60} molecules to enter human cells and viruses at a much higher rate than the ability of viruses to enter human cells. This adaptive coordinate system of fullerene disodium phosphonate C_{60} is superior, making C_{60} like a small micro-robot, flowing freely inside human cells and tissues, constantly optimizing the virtuous circulation and metabolism of human cells, including improving the recognition rate of the human immune system, which is one of the secrets of C_{60} anti-aging. The C_{60} is able to identify viruses that are different from human cells, and to detect the "Trojan horse" that changes human cells in a timely manner. At the same time, excrete this harmless virus, in the course of the body's metabolism. Our anaerobic fermenters, as the integrity system of the toilet revolution, treat human and livestock fecal sewage

waste in situ, ensuring that the anaerobic fermenters discharge harmless medium water, not contaminants containing viral bacteria that harm humans.

相比之下，疫苗真的是扼杀病毒的解药吗？我认为疫苗问世，面临三大疑问。只不过由于病毒重创全球，人们期待疫苗能及早问世。新型冠状病毒在传染全世界的情况下，被传统观念的特色专家认定疫苗能成为这场疫情的解药，使得各国的疫苗研发也加紧脚步，包括核酸疫苗、病毒载体疫苗和灭活疫苗在内，目前全球有 7 支以上的病毒候选疫苗进入临床试验阶段。然而，疫苗的开发成功概率有多少？若问世，有效性和安全性又将如何？医学理论与实践告诉我们，疫苗并非万能，SARS 病毒、艾滋病等，都是十多年、三十多年没有成功的疫苗研发出来。“在过去一、二十年中，疫苗领域发展很快，但针对 RNA 病毒，没有什么成功的疫苗发展出来。”前美国陆军研究所病毒系实验室主任林晓旭博士说。

By contrast, are vaccines really the antidote to strangling the virus? I think the development of vaccines are faced with three major questions. It was only because the virus hit the world so mercilessly that the world are desperate for the advent of vaccines. As the new coronavirus infects the world, the vaccine has been identified by traditional experts as the antidote to the epidemic, which has led to an intensification of vaccine development in various countries. However, what is the probability of successful vaccine development? What about effectiveness and safety, if it comes out? Medical theory and practice tell us that vaccines are not everything, and that SARS virus, AIDS, etc. are all vaccines that have not been developed successfully for more than a decade or three. "The field of vaccines has evolved rapidly over the past year or two, but there have been few successful vaccines developed against RNA viruses." Dr. Xiaoxu Lin, former laboratory director of the U.S. Army Medical Research Institute of Infectious Disease, said.

再看看流感病毒、冠状病毒（例如 SARS、MERS）、登革热病毒、艾滋病毒和伊波拉病毒都属于 RNA 病毒。除了流感病毒之外，其它 RNA 病毒都没有成功的疫苗问世。流感病毒疫苗

，算是目前全球最成熟的 RNA 病毒疫苗，但效果仍然有限。因流感病毒年年变异，每年的流感病毒疫苗种株都要重新挑选，且施打流感疫苗后，并非绝对不会感染。据美国疾控中心 (CDC) 报告，历年流感疫苗有效率在 40% ~ 60% 之间。从来都没有 100% 的有效疫苗，就像没有百分百治愈率的药品一样。

Then look at influenza viruses, coronaviruses (e.g. SARS, MERS), dengue viruses, HIV and Ebola viruses, which are all RNA viruses. With the exception of the influenza virus, no successful vaccine has been introduced for any of the other RNA viruses. The influenza virus vaccine is the most mature RNA virus vaccine in the world, but its effectiveness is still limited. Because the influenza virus varies from year to year, each year the strain of the influenza virus vaccine is reselected and is not absolutely immune to infection after the flu vaccine is administered. According to the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the flu vaccine is between 40% and 60% effective over the years. There is never a 100% effective vaccine, just like there is no medicine with a 100% cure rate.

2020 年 5 月 15 日下午加州索伦托生物治疗公司 (Sorrento Therapeutics) 宣布，已经发现可以 100% 抑制冠状病毒的抗体，可以在 4 天内完全清除人体中的冠状病毒。疫苗最快将在数月内上市，并进入治疗阶段。发布信息者说“我们强调，这是一种治愈方法，并且可以达到 100% 有效！”恰恰是这个百分百的说法，令人不敢相信了，毕竟临床医学实验证明，从来就没有百分百的医疗效果，尽管这则信息里面所说的抗体，是我们每个人都想要的，希望它很好的灭杀病毒。美中不足的是，加州索伦托公司还没有足够的临床医学实验，就说 100% 杀毒和治愈率，明显的违背了科学常识与常规。请记住，索伦托公司的这种产品是以体外试验作为依据，进行判断的哗众取宠，相应的“抗体”在血清疗法类型里面都是做不到广谱性，一旦所谓的有效成分作为抗体进入人体，就会遭受人体细胞的外部包膜特异性的困扰。此外，由于它是人工的，因此建立了不能保证有效抵抗冠状病毒突变株的依赖性。从长远来看，富勒烯聚磷酸二钠仍然是瓦解病毒的王冠上那颗钻石，是无可替代的。他们索伦托公司的“抗体”类型药品，如果真实的好，也需要

半年以上的临床医学实验检验，也可以使用我们的富勒烯膦酸钠二钠作为纳米颗粒表面活性剂递送系统，把这种“抗体”输送的人体器官，实现全身的瓦解病毒目标。何况，我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠雾化方式向人体肺部给药，即采取蒸气输送的方式方法，将改变索伦托公司产品的整体动力机制，从而实现广泛的通用处方。

On the afternoon of May 15, 2020, Sorrento Therapeutics of California announced that it has discovered antibodies that inhibit 100% of coronaviruses and can completely remove coronaviruses from the body within 4 days. The vaccine will be on the market and in the treatment phase within months at the earliest. The person who posted the information said "We stress that this is a cure and can be 100% effective!" It is precisely this claim of 100% cure rate makes it unbelievable. After all, clinical medical experiments prove that there is never a 100% medical effect, although the antibodies mentioned in this claim are what we all want and hope that it is good enough to kill the virus. The missing piece is that Solento California has not had enough clinical medical trials to say 100% kill and cure rates, a clear violation of scientific common sense and convention. Once the so-called active ingredient enters the body as an antibody, it will suffer from the specificity of the external envelope of human cells. In addition, because it is artificial, a dependency is established that does not guarantee effective resistance to the coronavirus mutant strain. In the long run, disodium fullerene phosphonate remains the diamond in the crown of disintegrating viruses and is irreplaceable. Sorrento's "antibody", if really good, also require more than six months of clinical medical testing; or they can collaborate with our fullerene-dronate disodium as a nanoparticle surfactant delivery system can be used to deliver this "antibody" to the human organism to achieve the goal of whole body disintegration of the virus. What's more, the vaporization of our fullerene disodium phosphonate to the human

lung, i.e., a vapor delivery method, will change the overall dynamics of Sorrento's products, allowing for a wide range of universal prescriptions.

雾化吸入肺部，与给新冠肺炎病毒感染的病患者输液，究竟哪一个是效果最好的呢？这种“给药”方式的比较研究并不多，仅仅是从直达病灶的方式要比拐弯抹角更好一些的基础逻辑来看，最佳选择就是鼻腔吸收，让雾化的药品直接进入人体肺部（1）直接处理肺部感染，快刀斩乱麻。（2）成本大幅度降低，变成普惠全人类的救死扶伤医疗福利保障。我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠即便是以口服液的方式存在，也知道口服液直接到人体其他感染的器官，应该说是必要的，现已证实全身各系统都会感染新冠肺炎病毒，人体免疫系统全方位针对新冠肺炎病毒形成的自体免疫抗体，当然是最好了。只不过哪里是最重要的病灶？深入这个病灶，才是纲举目张的“抓手”，不可以眉毛胡子一把抓，平铺直叙的千头万绪一把乱麻，所以这种没有临床医学万人以上实践检验的百分百说法，不靠谱。我们希望他们没有言过其实的哗众取宠，希望使用这种“抗体”成功抗疫拯救人类，即便是他们现在骗了我们也算好。我要说的是，关于“疫苗~抗体”过去的一次又一次失败，启发我们认识到，疫苗用于往往无法全面消灭所有的病毒过程中，包括新的变异病毒让“疫苗”的抗体也无法识别，固此还会让人体病灶再犯疾病。何况，我们从医疗经济学的角度核算与调查了很长时间，发现口服液的成本和效果——性价比都不是最佳的，输液、舌下含服、经过胃液反应的口服、定位封闭、鼻腔吸入肺部等等，应该说口服液要比电子烟雾化器贵了很多倍，我们需要的万全之策是最好把口服液与雾化剂等等，都做测试及临床医学实验。

Which is the most effective, vapor inhalation into the lungs, or infusion to patients with novel coronavirus infection? There are not much study on the comparison of "drug delivery" method, only that logically speaking direct delivery to the infected area, which is nasal inhalation, is better than beating around the bush, since inhalation of the aerosolized drugs directly into the human lung (1) is a direct treatment of lung infections, quick and clean; and (2) the costs have been substantially reduced, turning them into life-saving medical benefits accessible to all people. Our fullerenes disodium phosphonate comes in the form of oral solution,

and that oral solution can spread directly to other infected organs of the body, which is necessary, since it has been confirmed that the whole body system can be infected with novel coronavirus. Of course it is best for our immune system to develop all-round antibodies against the coronavirus. Just where are the most important lesions? A direct treatment of the lesion is what Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM) referred to as the "grasping hand", a random and blind treatment of every symptoms is not suggested. That is why this kind of 100% cure claim without the backing of clinical trials of more than ten thousand participants is not reliable. We hope that they have not overstated their claptrap and that they will use this "antibody" to successfully fight the epidemic and save humanity, and it is fine for now even if they lied. What I am saying is that past failures of "vaccines~antibodies" approach have inspired us to realize that vaccines are used in processes that often fail to completely eliminate all viruses, including new mutated viruses that are unrecognizable to the antibodies of the "vaccine", and thus allow the body to be vulnerable to reinfection. Moreover, we have spent a long time on verification and investigation based on the concept of medical economics, and found that the cost and effectiveness of oral fluids—the cost-performance ratio is not the best. Considering infusion, sublingual administration, oral administration after gastric fluid reaction, positioning closure, nasal inhalation into the lungs, etc, it should be said that oral fluids are several times more expensive than e-cigarette and vaping devices. What we need as a foolproof solution is to conduct tests and clinical trials on oral fluids and vapers.

舆论上过分宣传的疫苗“特效”是一种误导，期待新冠肺炎的病毒疫苗开发后，能像流感一样，通过年年施打疫苗去控制，纯粹的就是违背科学常识。我认为，就算有疫苗，强悍的新冠肺炎传染病毒可能还是会造成很多人感染、重症，甚至死亡。因为新冠肺炎病毒在传播过程中不断的

变异，传染力太强了，死亡率也高，目前全球死亡率高达 6.7%，在英国、法国、意大利、比利时等国，死亡率更超过 14%。而且，新冠肺炎病毒疫苗的实际应用，面临三大疑问。

The over-publicized "special effect" of the vaccine is a misleading expectation that the anti-coronavirus vaccine will be developed, and the virus can be controlled through vaccination year after year, just like influenza. The thought is purely against scientific common sense. In my opinion, even with a vaccine, the powerful novel coronavirus infectious agent may still cause many people to become infected, seriously ill, and even die. Because the novel coronavirus is constantly mutating during transmission, it is too infectious and has a high mortality rate, which is currently 6.7% worldwide and more than 14% in the United Kingdom, France, Italy, Belgium and other countries. Moreover, the practical application of the novel coronavirus vaccine faces three major questions.

其一、病毒变异可能削弱疫苗有效性，“我对（新冠肺炎病毒）疫苗基本不看好。”瑞士生物技术公司 SunRegen Healthcare AG 的首席科学家、欧洲病毒学专家董宇红坦言，RNA 病毒疫苗开发很难。开发一支疫苗，至少需要 18 个月的时间。然而，18 个月后病毒的变异难以预防。因为 RNA 病毒比 DNA 病毒变异更快，而新冠肺炎病毒的 S 蛋白又是高度变异区。董宇红解释，疫苗设计的原理，是在新冠肺炎病毒结合人体的 S 蛋白上，寻找一个关键的抗原表位（*epitope*），通过疫苗模拟这个表位，期望人体免疫系统能对疫苗产生抗体。未来抗体能中和入侵人体的新冠肺炎病毒，让它们不再感染细胞。但新冠肺炎病毒除了可从人体细胞表面的 ACE2 受体入侵外，生物学预印（*BioRxiv*）网站发表文章指出，该病毒也可与免疫系统 T 淋巴细胞表面的 CD147 受体结合。当 ACE2、CD147 等受体都可能参与感染环节，使新冠肺炎病毒 S 蛋白可能结合的关键表位的研究更加困难。

First, viral mutations can weaken vaccine effectiveness. "I'm fundamentally unimpressed with the (novel coronaviruses) vaccine." Dong Yuhong, chief scientist at Swiss biotech company SunRegen Healthcare AG and a European virologist,

admits that RNA virus vaccine development is difficult. It takes at least 18 months to develop a vaccine. However, mutation of the virus after 18 months is difficult to prevent. This is because RNA viruses mutate faster than DNA viruses and the S-protein of novel coronavirus is a highly variable region. The principle of vaccine design, explains Dong, is to look for a key antigenic epitope (epitope) on the novel coronavirus-binding human s-protein, which is mimicked by the vaccine in the expectation that the human immune system will produce antibodies against the vaccine. Future antibodies neutralize novel coronaviruses that invade the body so that they no longer infect cells. But in addition to invading from the ACE2 receptor on the surface of human cells, the novel coronaviruses can also bind to the CD147 receptor on the surface of T-lymphocytes of the immune system, according to an article published on the website BioRxiv (Biological Preprinting). When ACE2, CD147, and other receptors are likely to be involved in the infection chain, it makes it more difficult to study the key epitopes that the neo-coronavirus S-protein may bind.

就算找到一个假定的表位，董宇红提出一个质疑：“免疫系统是一个很复杂的巨系统，人们对它的认识到现在还在摸索之中，能用一个表位解决这个超级病毒的问题吗？”新冠肺炎传染的病毒变异快，使疫苗的开发变得很困难。

Even if a hypothetical epitope is found, Dong Yuhong poses a question: "The immune system is a very complex giant system, and people are still exploring. Can this super virus be solved with an epitope?" The rapid viral variation of novel coronaviruses transmission makes vaccine development difficult.

其二、新冠肺炎的病毒可破坏免疫系统，必然的使得疫苗效力未必可以持久。2019年11月到2020年半年多时间的“抗疫”实践让临床医学证明，新冠肺炎传染病的这种病毒，是一个

相当难对付的病毒，对细胞的杀伤力也很强。许多专家对新冠肺炎病毒的感受都是这样的，上海复旦大学附属医院的知名专家张文宏教授一次又一次的强调指出这一点。

Second, the new coronavirus can damage the immune system, inevitably makes the vaccine effectiveness unsustainable. Many experts feel the same way about the new coronavirus, and Professor Zhang Wenhong, a well-known expert at Shanghai Fudan University Hospital, has stressed this point time and time again.

最突出的难题，就是新冠肺炎传染的病毒具备攻击人体免疫系统的特点。现在公认的研究成果揭示，人体感染新冠肺炎病毒以后，会出现外周血淋巴细胞的进行性下降。医疗专家董宇红解释，一般在感染其它病毒后，人体出现小幅度的淋巴细胞下降属正常现象，这是因为淋巴细胞清除病毒造成的自身损失，“但若淋巴细胞数目严重或持续性的降低就不妙。”这一点，也造成疫苗开发的难度。因为注射疫苗的目的，就是指望免疫系统能被它激活，产生针对病毒的抗体，因此人体本身要有相对健康的免疫系统。

The most salient challenge is that the novel coronavirus-transmitting virus has the characteristic of attacking human immune system. It is now well established that humans infected with novel coronavirus experience a progressive decline in peripheral blood lymphocytes. Medical expert Dong Yuhong explained that it is normal for the body to experience a small drop in lymphocytes after being infected with other viruses, which is due to the lymphocytes removing their own losses caused by the virus, "but it is not good if the lymphocyte count is severely or persistently reduced." This, too, has made vaccine development difficult. Because the purpose of vaccination is to expect the immune system to be activated by it to produce antibodies against the virus, therefore the body itself should have a relatively healthy immune system.

在免疫系统已受损的情况下，疫苗注射进入人体之后，产生的抗体量和持续性都不见得长久。这就意味着发生再度感染的风险比较高，这是要求现有的疫苗研发，必须考虑人体免疫系统在新冠肺炎病毒感染过程中，受到伤害的速度，与疫苗激活人体免疫系统的速度，以及预警机制适应病毒变异的能力，多方面的综合反应，现在是一个谜。因此，不能断言“疫苗是战胜病毒唯一的或者决定性路径”，这样的误入歧途就会造成整个临床医学的重大损失。

In cases where the immune system is compromised, the amount and persistence of antibodies produced after the vaccine is injected into the body is not as long lasting. This implies a relatively high risk of reinfection, which is a requirement for existing vaccine development, which must consider the rate at which the human immune system is harmed during novel coronaviruses infection, versus the rate at which the vaccine activates the human immune system, and the ability of early warning mechanisms to adapt to viral mutations, a multifaceted and integrated response that is now a mystery. Therefore, it cannot be asserted that "the vaccine is the only or decisive path to defeat the virus", and such a misdirection would result in a major loss to clinical medicine as a whole.

其三、疫苗安全性未知，可能产生严重的副作用，原因是怎么样评估疫苗本身对于人体的无害化风险？临床医学并没有万全之策，整个现代医学都是一脸茫然。也就是说，关于疫苗的科学还是比较落后了，艾滋病就把疫苗和免疫系统研究直截了当的拎起来，让现代医学下不来台，非常的尴尬。再加上这一次新冠肺炎病毒感染疫情的大流行，把预防医学、疫苗和免疫系统研究赤裸裸的暴露在无能为力状态。临床医学的事实证明，疫苗有可能产生严重的副作用，就是“抗体依赖性免疫加强反应”（*Antibody-dependent enhancement, ADE*），抗体无法中和病毒，而是与病毒结合，激活病毒复制或感染能力。这就是“帮倒忙”的疫苗问题，这种风险评估和风险管理，还需要更多的探索发现，来弥补漏洞百出的“抗疫”工作。另外，考虑到新冠病毒或许出现抗体依赖感染增强作用（*ADE*）效应和其他一些因素，生产出有效的疫苗需要花费更多时间，至少一年半以上。再者，确定疫苗是否有效，也可能要数年时间。因此，新冠肺炎的病毒疫苗从

研发到真正投入临床应用，还有很长的路要走，对于当下的“全球化抗疫”严峻形势，无异于远水解不了近渴。

Third, the safety of vaccines is unknown and may have serious side effects, because how is the risk of harmlessness of the vaccine itself to humans assessed? Clinical medicine is not foolproof; the whole of modern medicine is a daze. In other words, the science of vaccines is still behind, and AIDS is an embarrassment to modern medicine by rendering vaccine and immune system research ineffective. Coupled by this pandemic of novel coronaviruses infections, the powerlessness of preventive medicine, vaccines, and immune system research are exposed. Clinical evidence shows that vaccines have the potential to have a serious side effect of "antibody-dependent immune enhancement (ADE)," in which antibodies do not neutralize the virus, but instead bind to it and activate its ability to replicate or infect. This is the problem of "unhelpful" vaccines, a risk assessment and risk management that requires more exploration and discovery to close the gap of "anti-vaccine" efforts. In addition, considering that neocoronaviruses may show antibody-dependent infection enhancing effect (ADE) effects and a number of other factors, it would take more time, at least a year and a half, to produce an effective vaccine. Again, it can take years to determine whether a vaccine is effective. Therefore, the new coronavirus vaccine from research and development to the real clinical application, there is still a long way to go, for the current "globalization of antiepidemic" grim situation, is no different from fetching water too far to quench the thirst.

疫苗的这种状态，不能成为现在“抗疫”的生力军，今后也不可以把疫苗当成“大救星”，毕竟疫苗的风险触目惊心，不可不高度重视副作用。2012年美国等国的科学家曾尝试开发 SARS 病毒疫苗，在动物实验中，动物对 SARS 病毒有强大的抗体反应，当再次接触野生病毒株时，这

些动物却产生抗体依赖性免疫加强反应，最终导致死亡。1960年代呼吸道合胞病毒（RSV）疫苗的临床实验中，这种过度免疫反应曾造成2名儿童死亡。董宇红直言：“有效性和安全性都受质疑，针对这个病毒的特效疫苗保护人群的可能性，几乎不存在。”疫苗研发存在安全性问题，可能产生严重副作用。除了等待疫苗，还有何解药？这就是我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠水溶性雾化治疗药品，直接进入肺部而且没有副作用，不对于现在的人体免疫系统产生刺激，才是直截了当的最佳选择。

In such a state, vaccines cannot be prioritized in the fight against epidemics now, nor can they be regarded as the "saviour" in the future; after all, the risks of vaccines are alarming and side effects must be given high priority. In 2012, scientists in the United States and other countries tried to develop a vaccine against the SARS virus, and in animal experiments, animals showed a strong antibody response to the virus, and when they were exposed to the wild strain of the virus again, the animals developed an antibody-dependent immune response, which eventually led to death. Dong Yohong said bluntly, "Both effectiveness and safety are in question, and the possibility of a potent vaccine against this virus to protect the population is almost non-existent." There are safety issues with vaccine development that can have serious side effects. What is the antidote, other than waiting for the vaccine? This is why our fullerene disodium phosphonate water-soluble vapor therapy drug, which goes directly to the lungs with no side effects and no stimulation of the current human immune system, is straightforward and the best choice.

对于疫苗的积极作用，可以期待，但不要指望。我们现在全世界的二百多个病毒疫苗，能否成功问世？能否发挥效用？我们需要亦步亦势的探讨答案。我认为，即便病毒变异，第一批疫苗产生的免疫性，如果能交叉保护（两种病毒感染一种寄主时，先入侵的病毒能够保护寄主不再受

第二种病毒的侵染)，一样可能会有效。问题是我们必须坦言，目前这些都是未知的，因此应该是先用各种可能的策略去发展疫苗，并赶快进入临床试验，评估安全性及有效性。

For the positive effects of the vaccine, one can look forward to it, but don't count on it. Can we have a successful vaccine for the 200-plus viruses we now have around the world? Will it work as intended? We need to explore the answers in the same way. I think that even if the virus mutates, the immunity produced by the first vaccine is just as likely to be effective if cross-protected (when two viruses infect one host, the virus that invades first protects the host from the second virus). The problem is that we have to be honest, these are currently unknown, so it should be a matter of developing the vaccine first with every possible strategy and getting into clinical trials quickly to evaluate safety and effectiveness.

在疫苗问世仍未见曙光之下，保持社交距离可起到一定的防护效果。除此之外，增强自身免疫力、保持健康心态都很重要，这也是我们研发出来的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠针锋相对的进入病毒，不是让人们等待着病毒在身体里面发作，而是积极主动的向病毒主动出击，把“进攻最好的防御”演绎为：向病毒发起进攻才是最重要的防止新冠肺炎形成的策略。我们每个人在求助疫苗、药物的同时，也应该发现积极向上的精神力量对防疫的重要性，乐观主义的人生态度，幸福快乐的家庭生活与和谐的工作团队，本来就是战胜病毒感染疫情的强大社会力量。当人的精神颓废时，免疫系统无法维持强壮；但如果人们有信仰、拥有正信正念时，精神上的力量会增强自身的免疫力。无论疫苗能否成功问世，都不妨碍人类从自身寻找解药，例如积极劳动和锻炼身体。

Keeping social distance can have a protective effect in the absence of a vaccine. In addition, it is important to strengthen the immune system and maintain a healthy mind, which is why we developed fullerenes disodium phosphonate into the virus tit-for-tat. Each of us, while seeking help for vaccines and medications, should also discover the importance of positive spirituality in the prevention of the epidemic, optimism, a happy family life and a harmonious work team, which is a

powerful social force to overcome the epidemic of viral infection. When people are spiritually decrepit, the immune system cannot remain strong; but when people have faith and possess the right beliefs, spiritual strength strengthens their immunity. Whether or not a vaccine is successful, it does not prevent humans from finding an antidote from themselves, such as active labor and physical exercise.

与此同时，气候变化越来越暖和，我们需要说明温暖的天气，根本无法杀死新冠肺炎的病毒。当临近夏天时，人们对如何利用热量来对抗这种流行病展开了很多讨论。加拿大多伦多大学 (U Of T) 的一项最新研究发现，温暖的天气实际上无助于杀死新冠病毒流行病。据 Narcity 报导，多伦多大学近日发布的研究发现，尽管很多人建议将病毒暴露于高温下可以杀死它们，但炎热的天气实际上并不能抵御新冠肺炎病毒。该研究的主要作者多伦多大学教授彼得·尤尼 (Peter Jüni) 表示：“我们的研究表明，天气转暖不应成为决定重开学校的因素。”他指出，初步研究表明温度可能在杀死病毒方面起一定作用，但在“更严格的条件下”反复进行实验，研究小组发现了相反的结果。

At the same time, climate change is getting warmer and we need to make the case that warm weather simply cannot kill the virus of novel coronavirus. As summer approaches, there is a lot of discussion about how to use the heat to fight this epidemic. A new study from the University of Toronto (U Of T) in Canada has found that warm weather doesn't actually help to kill the Covirus epidemic. According to Narcity, a recently released study from the University of Toronto found that while many people suggest that exposing viruses to high temperatures can kill them, hot weather doesn't actually protect against the novel coronavirus. Peter Jüni, a professor at the University of Toronto and lead author of the study, said, "Our research suggests that warmer weather should not be a factor in the decision to reopen schools." He noted that preliminary studies suggested that temperature might play a role in killing the virus, but that the team found the

opposite result when the experiment was repeated under "more stringent conditions".

为了证明这个结论，该研究调查了全球 144 个区域，这些地区截止 3 月 27 日感染病毒的病例超过 37.5 万例。调查发现，温暖的天气与寒冷的气候相比，没有任何优势。研究的合著者、多伦多大学教授盖辛克 (Dionne Gesink) 说：“病毒不会在夏天消失。”所以，相信科学技术是人类战胜病毒的最大实力，我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠一定能够在人体肺部灭杀新冠病毒，让人的肺部感染新冠肺炎病毒变得普遍性轻微化，让现代科技的槲皮素药品和中医药抗病毒配方，都可以大显身手。

To support this conclusion, the study looked at 144 regions around the world, where more than 375,000 cases of the virus had been reported as of March 27. The survey found that the warm weather had no advantage over the cold climate. Dionne Gesink, a University of Toronto professor and co-author of the study, said, "The virus won't go away in the summer." Therefore, it is believed that science and technology is the greatest strength of mankind to defeat the virus, our fullerene phosphonate disodium will certainly be able to kill the neocoronavirus in the human lung, make the human lung infection neocoronavirus become widespread mild, so that modern technology quercetin drugs and Chinese medicine antiviral formulations, both can make a big impact.

这方面我们一直都是竭尽全力的向着自知之明与知人之明奋斗，诚惶诚恐的面对人体免疫系统和病毒传染的机制，不遗余力的探索发现。因为我们知道过去的医学成果在进步过程中，都有不可忽视的副作用，都是利害攸关的双刃剑，从来就没有十全十美的治病救人药品。记得 2018 年诺贝尔医学奖授予美国免疫学家詹姆斯·艾利森和京都大学的本庶佑教授，成果就是分子刹车免疫抗肿瘤，或者说扼杀癌细胞。分子刹车抗肿瘤的理论了不起，但临床效果有限，如胰岛素 1921 年被发现，1923 年获得诺贝尔奖，无疑是伟大的发现，当初以为能根绝糖尿病，而现实是糖尿病有增无减。免疫抗肿瘤的内容很广，许多人都希望它替代放射性化疗等等，可事实上只

能是免疫疗法发展尽管很快，也只能是基本与传统的手术、化疗、放疗比肩。这种免疫疗法早已经从很多角度在探讨，如非特异性免疫赋活剂。这类如一些补益中药、食用真菌和细菌成分；抑制肿瘤生长的单克隆抗体，如人表皮生长因子受体-2 (Her2) 和血管内皮细胞生长因子的抗体 (VEGF)；激活免疫细胞的细胞因子，如干扰素和白细胞介素；导入免疫细胞，如注射 NK 细胞，同种造血干细胞移植；接种肿瘤疫苗，还未成功；免疫调节剂，即获奖相关的 PD-1、PD-L1、CTLA-4 抗体 (伊匹单抗)。应该说 2018 年诺贝尔医学奖成果分子刹车，属于免疫调节剂。两位获奖者分别发现了 T 淋巴细胞表面有防止免疫过度应答刹车式的关口 (检查站) PD-1 和 CTLA-4，也许还有其他蛋白有待发现，如果肿瘤细胞分泌 PD-L1，与 T 淋巴细胞的 TD-1 结合，T 细胞活性受到抑制便不能发挥杀伤肿瘤细胞的作用，所以把 PD-1 和 CTLA-4 称谓细胞刹车或分子刹车。如果用抗体把 PD-1 和 CTLA-4 等车刹废掉，T 淋巴细胞被激活，便能发挥抗肿瘤作用。但是副作用非常明显，CTLA-4 抗体和 TD-1 抗体治疗恶性黑色素瘤，实际有效性大约只有 20~30%，目前扩大试用于其他肿瘤，有一定疗效，其很大的副作用也很有特色。例如副作用特色是全身性，这是其他药品没有的现象。正常情况下，炎症组织和炎症细胞分泌 PD-L1，与 T 淋巴细胞的 TD-1 结合，或相当于保安的树状细胞产生 CD80/CD86，与 T 淋巴细胞的 CTLA-4 结合，T 细胞便失活，以避免炎症扩大，而保护自身组织。用 CTLA-4 抗体和 TD-1 抗体把刹车除掉了，T 细胞被充分活化，处于暴走状态，攻击肿瘤细胞，也会攻击自己所有正常组织细胞，造成自身免疫疾病，引起广泛损伤。对此，2018 年诺贝尔医学奖获得者本庶佑教授观察到，除掉小鼠的 TD-1 基因，便造成类似严重红斑狼疮的病变；美国学者实验观察到，敲掉小鼠的 CTLA-4 基因，出生几周后，小鼠因 T 细胞过度活化造成免疫风暴而死亡。可见 CTLA-4 和 TD-1 等分子刹车是生理功能，机体不能没有。CTLA-4 抗体和 TD-1 抗体虽有抑制肿瘤作用，但如日本《癌的免疫疗法》一书总结的那样，分子刹车抗肿瘤药，可引起间质性肺炎、重症肌无力、心肌炎、消化道穿孔、甲状腺病、1 型糖尿病、脑下垂体炎、眼病、肾上腺机能不全、血小板减少性紫癜、肝炎、肾炎、皮炎、神经炎等。

In this regard, we are always striving for self-knowledge and human knowledge, facing the human immune system and the mechanisms of viral transmission with

great fear, and spared no effort to explore and discover. Because we know that in the past, the medical achievements in the process of progress, all have side effects that cannot be ignored, all are double-edged swords at stake, and there has never been a perfect cure for the sick. Recall that the 2018 Nobel Prize in Medicine was awarded to American immunologist James Allison and Kyoto University's Professor Tsuyoshi Motoharu, and the result was molecular braking immunity against tumors, or choking off cancer cells. The theory of molecular brakes against tumors is remarkable, but the clinical effects are limited, such as insulin was discovered in 1921 and won the Nobel Prize in 1923, undoubtedly a great discovery, initially thought to eradicate diabetes, but the reality is that diabetes continues to increase. Immuno-anti-tumor is so broad that many people want it to replace radiotherapy and so on, but the fact is that immunotherapy, although it is developing rapidly, can only be comparable to traditional surgery, chemotherapy, and radiation therapy. This immunotherapy has long been explored from many angles, such as non-specific immune excipients. These include some tonic herbs, edible fungi and bacterial components; monoclonal antibodies that inhibit tumor growth, such as human epidermal growth factor receptor-2 (Her2) and vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF); cytokines that activate immune cells, such as interferon and interleukin; imported immune cells, such as injected NK cells, homozygous hematopoietic stem cell transplants; tumor vaccination, which has not been successful; and immunomodulators, such as the award-winning associated PD-1, PD-L1, CTLA-4 antibodies (epidermidimab). It should be said that the 2018 Nobel Prize in Medicine results in molecular brakes, belonging to immunomodulators. The two winners found that PD-1 and CTLA-4, which are the brake gates (checkpoints) on the surface of T-lymphocytes to prevent immune over-response,

respectively, and perhaps other proteins are yet to be discovered, and that if tumor cells secrete PD-L1 and bind to PD-1 of T-lymphocytes, the inhibited T-cell activity cannot play a role in killing tumor cells. T-lymphocytes can be activated if the antibodies against PD-1 and CTLA-4 are abrogated and the anti-tumor effect is achieved. The actual effectiveness of CTLA-4 and PD-1 antibodies in treating malignant melanoma is only about 20-30%, and it is currently being tried in other tumors on an expanded basis. Side effects, for example, are characterized as systemic, a phenomenon not found in other drugs. Under normal conditions, inflammatory tissues and inflammatory cells secrete PD-L1, which binds to PD-1 of T lymphocytes, or the equivalent of security dendritic cells that produce CD80/CD86, which binds to CTLA-4 of T lymphocytes, and the T cells are inactivated to avoid the expansion of inflammation and to protect their own tissues. After the brakes are removed with CTLA-4 and PD-1 antibodies, T cells are fully activated and in a state of mobbing, attacking tumor cells and all normal tissue cells, causing autoimmune diseases and extensive damage. In response, 2018 Nobel Laureate in Medicine Professor Tasuku Honjo observed that removing the PD-1 gene from mice resulted in lesions similar to severe lupus erythematosus; American scholars experimentally observed that knocking out the CTLA-4 gene from mice a few weeks after birth resulted in the death of mice due to an immune storm caused by excessive activation of T cells. CTLA-4 and PD-1 antibodies have tumor suppressing effects, but as summarized in the Japanese book "Immunotherapy for Cancer", molecular braking anti-tumor drugs can cause interstitial pneumonia, severe muscle weakness, myocarditis, gastrointestinal perforation, thyroid disease, type 1 diabetes, pituitary inflammation, eye disease,

adrenal insufficiency, thrombocytopenic purpura, hepatitis, nephritis, dermatitis, neuritis and so on.

相比之下，现在 2020 抗击新型冠状病毒传染的全球化奋斗过程中，那些不遗余力推崇“抗体疗法”的公司医疗研发人员，即便是院士、教授、医疗专家等等，也基本上都在夸大其词，从来没有襟怀坦白的向公众说明白推荐“抗体”产品的时候，副作用究竟是什么样子？片面性的吹嘘“抗体”多么神奇的“干掉新冠病毒”，却是拿不出来数以千计的临床医学人体实验数据，显得不珍惜人类生命，缺乏人道主义和医学应该有的严谨态度。

In contrast, in the course of the 2020 globalized fight against novel coronavirus infections, those medical company researchers that spare no effort to promote "antibody therapy", even academicians, professors, medical experts, and so on, are basically exaggerating and never frankly explaining to the public what the side effects will be when recommending "antibody" products. The one-sided bragging about how miraculous the "antibodies" are to "kill the new coronavirus", but the thousands of clinical and medical human experimental data are not available, seemingly not to value human life and lacking the rigor that humanism and medicine should have.

在这里，我们对于自己的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠分子瓦解新冠肺炎病毒的传染能力之际，也担心它的副作用就是瓦解人体里面的“有益病毒”。例如对于人类生育系统的病毒机制发生破坏，导致不孕不育。这是重大的可能性风险，怎么样防止？我们正在探讨，在权衡利弊的过程中，尽心尽力的趋利避害。

While we are concerned about the ability of our fullerene disodium phosphonate molecule to disintegrate the novel coronaviruses, we are also concerned that its side effect may be the disintegration of the "beneficial virus" in the body. For example, the viral mechanisms of the human reproductive system are disrupted, resulting in infertility. This is a significant probability risk, how to

prevent it? We are exploring, in the process of weighing the pros and cons, to do our best to avoid harm.

二、富勒烯 C60 来源于宇宙空间的生命源头

Fullerene C60 is the source of life in space

全世界人民经过了即将半年的“抗疫”努力，病毒疫情依然如故的汹涌而来，迫切需要科学技术研发优秀产品扼杀新型冠状病毒。北京时间 2020 年 5 月 19 日第 73 届世界卫生大会 (WHA) 结束了的时候，欧洲大部分国家的新型冠状病毒肺炎疫情开始回落，但世界卫生组织 (WHO) 官员重申，欧洲应该着手为第二波疫情的到来做准备。中国疫情近日也出现反弹，中国医学专家钟南山呼吁警惕第二波。而西方的专家也是这样指出：根据西班牙流感的经验，第二波恐怕更为致命。WHO 欧洲区主任克鲁格 (Hans Kluge) 日前重申，疫情尚未结束，欧洲国家应该准备面对第二波疫情。克鲁格警告，第二波疫情可能会与麻疹或流感同时来袭。参照以往的大流行历史，即使是在第一波中未受影响的国家，也可能会遭受第二波袭击。在没有有效疫苗的前提下，各国仍需谨慎应对。近日，在英国、法国、意大利等疫情重灾区，新增确诊病例都在下降，各国相继推出逐步解封的措施。同时，欧洲疫情中心开始东移，与中国毗邻的俄罗斯出现疫情大爆发，连日新增确诊破万。俄罗斯周边的乌克兰、白俄罗斯、哈萨克等地的确诊病例也在持续上升。中国虽然已紧急关闭中俄边境，但紧邻俄罗斯的黑龙江已出现大规模群聚感染。武汉、吉林等地也再次出现疫情爆发迹象。钟南山接受美国 CNN 采访时表示，当前疫苗开发并不乐观，中国也没有建立起群体免疫，因此仍然面临第二波疫情的挑战，情况并不比国外乐观。英格兰首席医疗官惠提 (Chris Whitty) 等专家警告，根据 1918 年至 1920 年夺走逾五千万条生命的西班牙流感的经验，第二波疫情的致命程度恐怕将高于第一波。根据学界研究结果，目前新型冠状病毒肺炎已经突变出逾百个变种，已适应各个种族。台湾中研院的研究发现，病毒突变量与致死率呈现正相关，并随着时间有增强的趋势。

After half a year of "anti-epidemic" efforts, the virus epidemic is still raging as usual, and there is an urgent need for scientific and technological research and development of excellent products to kill the new coronavirus. As the 73rd World

Health Assembly (WHA) ends on May 19, 2020, Beijing time, the outbreak of novel coronavirus pneumonia in most European countries is beginning to decline, but World Health Organization (WHO) officials reiterated that Europe should begin preparing for a second wave of the disease. China's epidemic has also seen a rebound in recent days, with Chinese medical expert Zhong Nanshan calling for vigilance against a second wave. Western experts have also pointed out that, based on the experience of the Spanish flu, the second wave is feared to be more deadly. WHO Europe Director Hans Kluge recently reiterated that the epidemic is not over and that European countries should prepare for a second wave. Krueger warned that a second wave of the epidemic could come at the same time as measles or the flu. With reference to the history of previous pandemics, even countries that were not affected in the first wave are likely to be hit by the second wave. In the absence of an effective vaccine, countries still need to respond with caution. Recently, in the United Kingdom, France, Italy and other hard-hit areas of the epidemic, new confirmed cases are declining, and countries have introduced measures to gradually unblock. At the same time, the epidemic center in Europe began to move eastward, and a major outbreak occurred in Russia, which is adjacent to China, with more than 10,000 new confirmed cases in a row. The number of confirmed cases in Ukraine, Belarus, Kazakhstan and other places around Russia is also on the rise. While China has urgently closed the China-Russia border, there has been a massive swarming of infections in Heilongjiang, which is immediately adjacent to Russia. Wuhan, Jilin and other places are also showing signs of another outbreak. Zhong Nanshan, an Chinese medical expert, said in an interview with CNN that the current vaccine development is not optimistic, and China has not established mass immunization, so it still faces the challenge of a

second wave of the epidemic, and the situation is no more optimistic than abroad. Experts such as England's chief medical officer Chris Whitty have warned that the second wave of the pandemic is feared to be more deadly than the first, based on experience of the Spanish flu that claimed more than 50 million lives between 1918 and 1920. According to academic research, the new coronavirus has now mutated over a hundred variants that have been adapted to various races. A study by the Chinese Academy of Sciences in Taiwan found that the amount of viral mutation was positively correlated with lethality and showed a tendency to increase over time.

事实上，病毒是地球真正的“原始”居民。不是病毒生活在我们人类的世界里，而是我们人类生活在病毒的海洋里。成千上万的病毒们是地球上所有生态系统的重要部分，我们人类呼吸的氧气很大一部分是在病毒的帮助下生产的，我们人类所在的这颗星球的温度也和病毒的活动息息相关。甚至，科学家发现，人类有 8% 的 DNA 来源于病毒。

In fact, virus is the true "original" inhabitant of the planet. It is not that virus lives in the world of humans, but that we humans live in a sea of viruses. Thousands of viruses are an important part of all the ecosystems on the planet, a large part of the oxygen we humans breathe is produced with the help of viruses, and the temperature of this planet where we humans live is also closely related to the activity of viruses. Even, scientists have found that 8% of human DNA comes from viruses.

在生命演化史上，最近的瞬间，人类脱颖而出，病毒功不可没。古老的鼻病毒可以训练我们的免疫系统不会出现过度反应。如果没有病毒，我们甚至可能没法“出生”——胎盘的进化就来自于病毒的贡献。科学家认为，大约 1 亿年前，哺乳动物的祖先感染了一种病毒，这种病毒把抵御免疫系统攻击的能力转移给了哺乳动物。胎儿的血型、基因与母亲不同，却可以免受免疫系统攻击，就是因为胎盘拥有了欺骗免疫系统的能力。

In the history of the evolution of life, in recent moments, humans have stood out and viruses have done much to help. Ancient rhinoviruses can train our immune system to not overreact. Without viruses, we might not even be "born" - the evolution of the placenta comes from the contribution of viruses. Scientists believe that about 100 million years ago, mammalian ancestors were infected with a virus that transferred the ability to defend against attacks on the immune system to mammals. The reason a fetus with a different blood type and genes from its mother is immune to attack is because the placenta possesses the ability to trick the immune system.

即便是 2020 年的今天，每个人的一生中，要被 500~600 甚至 1000 种不同的病毒攻击，多数攻击都被人体的免疫系统击败。进入体内的病毒，实施打击只需四步：第一步，吸附和注入宿主细胞。第二步，利用宿主细胞，进行蛋白质和核酸的复制，并制造病毒外壳。第三步，将组装好的病毒核酸和外壳从破裂的细胞中释放出去，感染新细胞。这种入侵和复制的速度极快，六小时内可以产生 10 万拷贝。第四步，每种病毒的攻击目标和方式不一样，一些病毒攻击表皮细胞，留下可怖的疤痕，但真正让人丧命的，是在人体内部器官进行复制的病毒。例如，新型冠状病毒，就是这样的利用人体肺部细胞组织，进行复制和毒害。

Even today, in 2020, each person will be attacked by 500 to 600 or even 1,000 different viruses in his or her lifetime, most of which are defeated by the body's immune system. The virus that enters the body, implements the strike in just four steps: the first, adsorption and injection into the host cell. The second step, using the host cell, carries out replication of proteins and nucleic acids and makes a viral shell. In the third step, the assembled viral nucleic acid and shell are released from the ruptured cells to infect the new cells. This invasion and replication is extremely fast, producing 100,000 copies in 6 hours. Step four, each virus targets and attacks in different ways, some viruses attack epidermal cells and leave horrific

scars, but what really kills people are the viruses that replicate in internal organs of the body. For example, the novel coronavirus is such that it uses cellular tissue in the human lung for replication and infection.

这时候，只有 C_{60} 碳分子作为单质的存在，要比病毒还小，可以钻进里面进行遗传基因链重组，才可以把病毒，以及这一类的全部新型冠状病毒，千篇一律的分化瓦解。因为，富勒烯聚磷酸二钠是由球形的 C_{60} 分子组成的分子晶体， C_{60} 是一种由 60 个碳原子构成的分子（物质一般不由原子构成），形似足球，又名足球烯。富勒烯 C_{60} 作为单纯由碳原子结合形成的稳定分子，它具有 60 个顶点和 32 个面，其中 12 个为正五边形，20 个为正六边形，其相对分子质量约为 720，在科学实验当中经常性的用于作催化剂和超导体，具有非比寻常的穿透力和重组功能。恰恰是这样的细小入微能力，让富勒烯 C_{60} 在人体细胞和病毒当中所向披靡。这方面一定要高度重视富勒烯 C_{60} 与钻石，都是完全由碳原子所组成的同素异形体（由相同的元素构成的分子），即由 60 个碳原子构成的分子，都属于高质量的存在，拥有足够的能量。这种巨大的能量，在生命体的新陈代谢活动当中，释放出来以后，就把病毒这种不完整的存在形态，当成了“怪物”，按照人体细胞的接纳病毒时候，与人体器官组织的正常功能匹配程度进行比较和识别，采取保护或者攻击、瓦解，使得人体免疫系统还没有敏感到了病变的时候，就已经把病毒危害人体组织功能的细胞改变可能性扼杀于无形之中，让病毒本身的核酸酶发生致命伤。于是，关于富勒烯 C_{60} 在清除自由基方面的功效，目前全世界已经有近 3 万篇论文被发表，近 3 千个专利获得了认可。但是，并没有一篇论文就像本文这样的揭示富勒烯 C_{60} 能够瓦解病毒，也没有相关的富勒烯 C_{60} 治疗新冠肺炎专利。这方面，我们的科学实验不打算申请专利权的私有制，而是无条件贡献给全人类，作为中国科学家团队拯救世界的爱心，不分你我他她共同分享，仅仅是制造商的产业化成本是需要良性循环的。

When this happens only the existence of C_{60} molecules as monomers, which are smaller than the virus, can penetrate into the virus for genetic recombination, so that the virus and all the new coronaviruses of this class can be dismantled in one swift blow. Because, fullerenes disodium phosphonate is a molecular crystal

composed of spherical molecules of C_{60} , a molecule composed of 60 carbon atoms (substances are generally not composed of atoms), shaped like a football, also known as footballene. Fullerene C_{60} is a stable molecule formed purely by the bonding of carbon atoms. It has 60 vertices and 32 faces, 12 of which are positive pentagonal and 20 positive hexagonal, and its relative molecular mass is about 720. It is frequently used as a catalyst and superconductor in scientific experiments, with unusual penetration and recombination. It is precisely this small, microscopic ability that makes fullerenes C_{60} unbeatable among human cells and viruses. In this regard, it is important to pay great attention to the fact that fullerenes C_{60} and diamonds, which are isomorphs (molecules made up of the same elements) composed entirely of carbon atoms, i.e. molecules made up of 60 carbon atoms, both exist in high quality and have sufficient energy. This huge energy, in the metabolic activity of the living body, after release, the virus, this incomplete form of existence, as a "monster", according to the acceptance of the virus by human cells, and the normal function of human organs and tissues to compare and identify, protect or attack, disintegrate, so that the human immune system is not yet sensitive to the lesion, the virus has already strangled the possibility of cellular changes that endanger the function of human tissues, so that the virus itself nucleates a fatal injury. As a result, nearly 30,000 papers have been published worldwide and nearly 3,000 patents have been granted on the efficacy of fullerenes C_{60} in the removal of free radicals. However, there is no paper like this one that reveals how fullerenes C_{60} can disrupt the virus, nor is there a relevant patent for fullerenes C_{60} for novel coronaviruses. In this regard, our scientific experiments are not intended to patent the private system, but to contribute unconditionally to all mankind, as a team of Chinese scientists to save

the world of love, not divided into you, me and he or she to share, just the manufacturer's industrialization costs need a virtuous circle.

对于富勒烯 C_{60} ,早在 1971 年的时候,日本的一位化学家就曾描述过宇宙中 C_{60} 的存在,不过一直到 2010 年,来自加拿大的天文学家们才首次在宇宙找那个发现了 C_{60} 存在的证据,一直到今年,科学家们发现了星云中的 C_{60} ,这也让科学家们对于宇宙有了新的认识。

For fullerenes C_{60} , as early as 1971, a Japanese chemist had described the existence of C_{60} in the universe, but it was not until 2010 that astronomers from Canada first found evidence of the existence of C_{60} in the universe, and until this year, scientists discovered C_{60} in the nebula, which has also given scientists a new understanding of the universe.

其实在地球之上,富勒烯 C_{60} 的存在还是很普遍的,在岩石和矿物质中很常见,并且一般烟尘在经历过高温燃烧之后,也会产生 C_{60} 分子。不过,以前在宇宙中却从未曾发现过 C_{60} 的存在,这也让科学家们一度认为它只存在于地球之上,这也让地球变得愈发的特别。通过哈勃望远镜,科学家们发现太空中 C_{60} 的存在很普遍,就连我们所在的银河系中, C_{60} 可以说是无处不在,只不过之前我们一直没有发现而已。

In fact, the presence of fullerenes C_{60} is still common above the Earth and in rocks and minerals, and the C_{60} molecule is also produced in general soot after it has undergone high temperature combustion. However, the fact that C_{60} has never been found in the universe before has made the Earth increasingly special, leading scientists to believe for a time that it only exists above the Earth. Through the Hubble telescope, scientists have discovered that the presence of C_{60} in space is widespread, even in our own galaxy, where C_{60} is arguably ubiquitous, except that we have not found it before.

为何科学家们认为 C_{60} 关乎着生命的起源呢?这是因为如果没有碳的存在,可能整个人类的生活都将不复存在,尤其是蛋白质和 DNA 之中,碳更是起着决定性的作用,并且所有的生命

基础都是由碳所构成的，可以说，碳可以形成多种化合物，如果没有碳，世界都会消失。为何碳如此的神奇呢？这是因为碳的外层有着 4 个电子，它们让碳变得丰富多彩。

Why do scientists think the C60 is associated with the origin of life? This is because without the existence of carbon, the entire human life may not exist, especially in proteins and DNA, carbon plays a decisive role, and all life is based on carbon. It can be said that carbon can form a variety of compounds. Without carbon, the world would not have existed. Why is carbon so amazing? This is because the outer layer of carbon has four electrons, which make it amazing.

这就是星际介质惊现 C60“巴克球”或者说富勒烯，2019 年初哈勃望远镜首次在太阳系以外、星系之间的空旷地带，发现了带电的 C60（巴克球，buckyball）分子，这是一种由 60 个碳原子组成的空心球状分子，和足球的结构相同，是相对复杂的一种碳分子。由于碳是所有生命的基础，研究者们想到，是否太空中物质运动会自发产生生命？

That's when C60 "buckyball," or fullerenes, first discovered in interstellar medium. In early 2019 the Hubble telescope discovered for the first time the charged C60 (buckyball) molecule, a hollow spherical molecule of 60 carbon atoms with the same structure as a football, a relatively complex type of carbon molecule, in the open space between solar systems and galaxies. Since carbon is the basis of all life, researchers wonder if matter in space will spontaneously generate life?

这份 2019 年 6 月份发表在《天文物理期刊通讯》上的研究论文，公布了这一发现：星系之间空旷的地带，也叫星际介质带（ISM），其中存在的气体和尘埃混合物相当稀疏，却发现了这样复杂的碳元素结构 C60，这令研究者颇为惊讶。

This research paper, published in the June 2019 issue of Astrophysical Journal Letters, announces the discovery that a rather sparse mixture of gas and dust, also known as the Interstellar Medium (ISM), in which the intergalactic void is present,

has found such a complex carbon element structure, C_{60} , which surprised researchers.

天文学家认为，恒星和行星从气体和尘埃混合物中诞生，因此星际介质带就像天体的发源地，里面所含的物质成分对了解宇宙、生命的起源和发展具有重要意义。

Astronomers believe that stars and planets emerge from a mixture of gas and dust, so the interstellar media belt is like the birthplace of celestial bodies and the material components contained therein are important for understanding the universe and the origin and development of life.

“稀疏的星际介质带可以看作是化学过程的起点，最终生成行星和生命。”这份研究论文的作者之一美国天主教大学物理系的 Martin Cordiner 说，“因此完全了解里面的成分将提供生成恒星和行星所需成分的信息。”

"The sparse interstellar medium can be seen as the starting point for chemical processes that eventually generate planets and life." Martin Cordiner of the Department of Physics at Catholic University of America, one of the authors of this research paper, said, "So a complete understanding of what's inside will provide information about the ingredients needed to generate stars and planets."

这种 C_{60} 碳原子也叫“巴克球”，地球上含量很少，偶尔会在岩石、矿物或煤烟中存在。追根溯源，就会发现，原子所带的电子被恒星发出的紫外线“剥夺”，使其带正电荷。“以前认为星际介质带环境太恶劣，不会有任何像样的大分子存在，”Cordiner 说，“在发现 C_{60} 之前，发现的最大分子是由 12 个原子组成的分子。这次发现的 C_{60} 分子说明，即便在这样稀疏、充满紫外线辐射的星系环境中，也会存在如此复杂的天文化学成分。”

This C_{60} carbon atom, also known as the "Bucky Ball", is found in very small amounts on Earth and is occasionally found in rocks, minerals or soot. Tracing the roots back to the source reveals that the electrons carried by the atom are "stripped" by the ultraviolet light emitted by the star, making it positively charged.

"It was previously thought that the interstellar medium environment was too harsh for any decent large molecules to exist," said Cordiner, "before the discovery of C₆₀, the largest molecule found was a molecule made up of 12 atoms. This discovery of the C₆₀ molecule shows that even in such a sparse, ultraviolet radiation-filled galactic environment, such complex astronomical chemistry can exist."

我们知道的所有生命形态都是以碳元素为基础的，如今在恶劣的星际介质空间却发现了如此复杂的碳结构，不禁让研究者推测，也许太空环境中会自发产生生命。“从某种角度来说，生命可以看作是复杂化学反应的终极产物，”Cordiner说，“C₆₀的发现明确地展示，存在高度复杂的化学反应是太空环境的本质特性，也许是在告诉我们，太空环境很可能会自发的产生其它高度复杂、以碳为基础的生命形态。”

All life forms we know are based on carbon, but today such complex carbon structures are found in the harsh interstellar medium of space that researchers speculate that life may spontaneously arise in the space environment. "In some ways, life can be seen as the ultimate product of complex chemical reactions," says Cordiner, "The C₆₀ discovery clearly demonstrates that the existence of highly complex chemical reactions is an intrinsic characteristic of the space environment, perhaps it is telling us that the space environment is likely to spontaneously produce other highly complex, carbon-based life forms."

正是如此，在实验室制造出来 C₆₀ 的三位科学家，共同于 1996 年获得了诺贝尔医学与化学奖，这就是富勒烯 C₆₀ 的里程碑性质贡献度，把人类对于生命起源的认识提高了一个档次。富勒烯之所以获得诺贝尔奖就是因为颠覆了自由基革命。之前清除自由基类的成分，比如维生素 C、SOD、MT (金属硫蛋白) 等，都是通过化学反应，让自由基转化成其他物质或者成分，而且效果差强人意。直至富勒烯 C₆₀ 的发现，一切都发生了神奇的变化，富勒烯 C₆₀ 好像进入肌肤的一块海绵，将自由基吸附进来，然后代谢或者排除出去。富勒烯 C₆₀ 这种机制，对于病毒

，也是一样的。原因是富勒烯 C_{60} 是分子态的纳米级存在，要比其他的蛋白质之类存在形态，更加“小微”而在人体细胞层面无孔不入。例如，经过权威试验添加富勒烯的护肤品一次涂抹，可以保持 11 小时的持续自由基阻击，长期使用，对肤色不均，色斑，有痘肌，老化肌肤等皮肤问题有明显的逆转和修复功能，并能有效根源呵护保持改善后的皮肤新生健康状态。

It is in this way that the three scientists who produced the C_{60} in the laboratory together won the Nobel Prize in Medicine and Chemistry in 1996, a landmark contribution of the fullerenes C_{60} , raising human understanding of the origin of life to a new level. Fullerenes won the Nobel Prize for revolutionizing the subversion of free radicals. The subversion of free radicals with materials such as vitamin C, SOD, MT (metallothionein) and etc. convert free radicals through chemical process into other substances or components, and are not as effective as they should be. It wasn't until the discovery of fullerene C_{60} that everything magically changed, and fullerene C_{60} seemed to enter the skin as a sponge, attracting free radicals in and then metabolizing or eliminating them. This mechanism, fullerenes C_{60} , does the same to viruses. The reason for this is that fullerenes C_{60} are molecularly present at the nanoscale and are more "microscopic" than other proteins and are pervasive at the human cellular level. For example, a single application of fullerene skin care product can maintain 11 hours of continuous free radical blocking, which can significantly reverse and repair skin problems such as uneven skin tone, pigmentation, acne and aging skin, and can effectively care for the root cause to maintain the improved skin's new state of health.

现在人们聚焦的问题是富勒烯 C_{60} 是否可以把新冠肺炎传染病的这种新型冠状病毒扼杀了，给人类的生存安全“吃定心丸”呢？这是检验富勒烯神奇的功能一个最大挑战，原因是相对于世界范围的经济生产总量来看，77 亿的全球总人口显得绝对过剩，因此大自然将以它自有的残酷方

式，直接或者间接地淘汰十亿、二十亿甚至更多的人口。这就是 2019 年从传染病爆发以来，全世界二百多个国家和地区都感觉到恐惧和力不从心的根本问题，人们都在心底里呼喊：人类是否可以通过研发疫苗和新药来战胜 COVID-19 病毒呢？

The question now in the spotlight is whether fullerenes C60 can kill the new coronavirus of the novel coronavirus epidemic and give humans a "peace of mind" about their survival safety. This is one of the biggest challenges in testing the miraculous function of fullerenes, since the total global population of 7.7 billion appears to be absolutely excessive in relation to the world's total economic production, so nature will directly or indirectly eliminate one billion, two billion or more people in its own cruel way. This is the fundamental question that has been feeling fearful and overwhelmed in more than 200 countries and regions around the world since the outbreak of the pneumonia epidemic in Wuhan in 2019, with people crying out in their hearts: can humanity defeat the COVID-19 virus by developing vaccines and new drugs?

目前从生物学的角度来看，COVID-19 病毒堪称一个完美的杰作，就像一首宏大的交响诗一样，精妙复杂而又巧夺天工。人类在历史上，从来没有出现过这样强大的全能型的纳米级对手。它所具备的许多特性让它像是一个极微小（125 纳米）的智能机器人，可以自由自在地在人体的细胞内穿梭巡游，人类的肺脏、肝脏、肾脏、大脑、免疫系统、排泄系统、生殖系统，统统都是它的攻击目标。而在发起攻击的同时，它还可以轻松躲过药物对它的追杀，直到和宿主一起同归于尽。

From a biological point of view, the COVID-19 virus is now a perfect masterpiece, like a grand symphonic poem, subtle, complex and ingenious. Never before in the history of mankind has there been such a powerful comprehensive nano-level opponent. It has many characteristics that make it more like a tiny (125nm) intelligent robot that can freely roam around in human cells, targeting

the human lungs, liver, kidneys, brain, immune system, excretory system, reproductive system, all of which are targeted. And while launching an attack, it can easily evade the drug's pursuit of it until it dies with its host.

第一，病毒有超强的耐心，它可以在人体内无症状潜伏 14 天甚至更长时间，目的就是要在神不知鬼不觉之中，最大程度地传染给它能接触到的人。

Firstly, the virus is so patient that it can lurk in the human body asymptotically for 14 days or more, with the aim of infecting as many people as it can reach without been identified.

第二，病毒有惊人的谋略，它的病死率不高不低，与超长潜伏期结合得恰到好处，既不能让宿主很快病死，又能在被发现之前尽可能传染更多的人。

Second, the virus is surprisingly strategic. Its mortality rate is not high or low, coupled perfectly with an ultra-long incubation period, it won't allow the host to get sick and die quickly, so that it can infect as many people as possible before discovered.

第三，病毒有神鬼莫测的传播途径，它可以通过空气、触摸、饮食、粪便传播，甚至根据上海瑞金医院的解剖报告来看，病毒完全有可能通过大面积暴露和有损伤的皮肤传播。

Third, the virus has an unpredictable route of transmission; it can be transmitted through air, touch, food, feces, and according to the autopsy report from Shanghai Ruijin Hospital, it is entirely possible for the virus to spread through large areas of exposed and damaged skin.

第四，病毒有闪展腾挪的攻击路径，科学家原来以为新冠病毒主要是通过血管紧张素转化酶 (ACE-2) 来建立对人体的攻击路径，但是其后病毒出现变异，又发展出三条新的攻击路径 FURIN、GRP78 和 CD 147。

Fourth, the virus has a highly flexible attack pathway. Scientists originally thought that the novel coronavirus established an attack pathway against the

human body mainly through angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE-2), but then the virus mutated and developed three new attack pathways FURIN, GRP78 and CD 147.

第五，一些研究人员认为，病毒实际上具备了乙肝病毒和艾滋病病毒的特性与功能，又能以流感的方式大范围内传播，即使是宿主通过治疗恢复了健康，病毒可能还会终身寄生在宿主体内，等到各种条件具备的时候，它将再度生机萌发、兴风作浪。这就像是原本就十分凶恶无比的老虎，现在又突然长出了翅膀，而且还成了隐身，由此，各种现代化武器武装到了牙齿的人类，才会在第一时间被打得溃不成军，狼狈不堪。

Fifth, some researchers believe that the virus actually has the characteristics and functions of the hepatitis B virus and the HIV virus, and can spread widely by way of influenza, even if the host regains health through treatment, the virus may still live in the host body for life, and when the conditions are met, it will once again grow and flourish. It's like a tiger that was already fierce and vicious, but now suddenly sprouted wings and became invisible, so that all kinds of modern weapons armed to the teeth only to be beaten to the ground immediately.

现在，新型冠状病毒独往独来，所向披靡，让我们刮目相看：病毒的上述神奇之处，还不过是冰山的一角，并非局限于此。例如，新型冠状病毒是一个单链的 RAN 冠状病毒，极不稳定，非常容易出现变异，仅仅是在 2020 年 2 月 12 日之前，病毒的进化树上最少就已经有了 5 个单倍型。

Now, the new coronavirus has come out on its own and has taken us by storm: the virus is just the tip of the iceberg. For example, the new coronavirus is a single-stranded RAN coronavirus that is extremely unstable and highly susceptible to mutation, with at least five haplotypes already on the evolutionary tree of the virus just before February 12, 2020.

今后，在世界范围内的大流行过程中，病毒必然会产生越来越多的变异，繁衍出越来越多的亚型，甚至可能与别的病毒形成重组，突变演化出一些全新的超级病毒出来。另外，近来在网上出现一个资料，有人发现 3 月 8 号之前，美国华盛顿州的一个病毒毒株已经有了 26 步突变，在法国境内的毒株有了 18 步突变，而在中国境内，最早的毒株突变只有香港的一例，为 10 步。

From now on, in the course of a worldwide pandemic, viruses will inevitably mutate more and more, reproducing more and more subtypes, and possibly even recombine with other viruses, mutating and evolving into new super viruses. In addition, a recent online profile has revealed that before March 8, a strain of the virus in Washington state had a 26-step mutation, a strain in France had an 18-step mutation, while in China, the earliest mutation was only one in Hong Kong, at 10 steps.

人类在与病毒对抗的斗争中，一种被动的但可以最广泛使用的手段，就是生产出对付病毒的特定疫苗。然而，疫苗的研制周期最少需要几个月甚至一年的时间，这个速度远远小于病毒的变异速度，这也就是说，如果在没有中医药等有效药物介入的情况下，人类实际上就是在骑着自行车追赶病毒的高速列车，只会越追越远，越死越多。

One of the passive but most widely available means by which humans can fight against viruses is to produce specific vaccines against them. However, the vaccine development cycle takes at least a few months or even a year, which is far less than the rate at which the virus mutates, which means that without the intervention of effective drugs such as Traditional Chinese Medicine, humans are actually chasing the virus' high-speed train on a bicycle, which will only get further and further away and die more and more.

退一步说，即使半年或者一年后，能够对付病毒的疫苗和药物研制出来了，但是，这些疫苗和药物能够对付病毒各个家族中不断形成的新的亚型吗？如果那时病毒又产生了更大程度的突变

，那人类又该怎么样来应对呢？据冰岛媒体“雷克雅未克秘闻 (The Reykjavík Grapevine)”3月25日消息，冰岛国内一名新冠肺炎患者被检测出同时被两种新冠病毒的感染的情况，其中第二种为原始新冠病毒的变体，这是冰岛第一次发现受双重新冠病毒感染的患者。并且，冰岛科学家已在国内发现40个病毒变种。这一点，仿佛与其他的机构说新型冠状病毒只有十多个变异，是彼此矛盾的，其实不然，新型冠状病毒的变幻莫测让科学家们进行分类时，标准不尽相同，类型也就不一致了。这种意见分歧状态并不重要，重要的是新型冠状病毒确实变化太多了，让人类的现代医学和古老的医疗方式方法，都显得心有余而力不足。恰恰是这样的颠覆性局面，才需要我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠完全彻底的没有从医学角度看问题，纯粹的就是站在物理化学的坐标系上，依据静电结构的力学原理，举重若轻的深入浅出，解决新型冠状病毒的问题。

Even if, six months or a year later, vaccines and drugs are developed to deal with the virus, will they be able to deal with the new subtypes that are emerging in the various families of the virus? If by then the virus has mutated to an even greater degree, how will humans cope? The Reykjavík Grapevine, the Icelandic media outlet, reported on March 25 that a patient with novel coronavirus in Iceland has been found to be infected with two novel coronaviruses, and the second of which is a variant of the original novel coronaviruses. Moreover, Icelandic scientists have identified 40 variants of the virus in the country. This, as if contradicting other agencies that say there are only a dozen or so variants of the novel coronavirus, is not the case; in fact, the fickleness of the novel coronavirus leaves scientists with different criteria and different types to classify. This state of disagreement is not important, what is important is that the new coronavirus has indeed changed so much that it makes both modern medicine and the old medical approaches seem more than adequate for human beings. It is precisely such a disruptive situation that requires our fullerenes disodium phosphonate that completely deviate from a medical point of view, stand purely on the coordinate

system of physicochemical, and based on the mechanics of the electrostatic structure, which offers a straightforward solution to the new coronavirus problem.

这方面，我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠主成分作为 C60 的更新换代产品，或者说 C60 的衍生物，整个瓦解新型冠状病毒的方案有很清楚的理论基础，也有可操作性的提供了一个全新的方向和方案。这是为人类战胜新型冠状病毒的“人类生命安全保卫战”开启了新纪元及新希望。我们 2020 年 5 月中旬和中国大陆以及世界多个大学医学院及疫苗中心的团队开了视频会议，他们非常兴奋的要和我们合作，2020 年 5 月 20 日就讨论签订合作方案。非洲和阿拉伯世界也有实验及临床合作方案出来，在拉丁美洲我们也送 200 套 Vaping system 和智慧大数据（由医生掌控病患的使用雾化器的次数及吸入量的控制）到疾控中心 CDC，注入 cartridges，专机空运到世界各地进行临床医学实验，以 Compassionate drug 的方式给病患使用，而且这是独立自主就可以起作用的特效药，不需要其他的药品一起进入人体，进入病毒。当然，也不排斥其他的药品随后一起复合使用，需要进行匹配实验。何况，富勒烯 C60 在中国并不是新鲜东西，长沙古汉墓马王堆里面的笼状碳，即是富勒烯的一种存在平台，事实上里面就有富勒烯分子。我们在 2020 年 5 月份一定要把富勒烯聚磷酸二钠瓦解病毒的成功路径，在世界各地用来拯救病患者，相信我们的努力肯定是硕果累累。我们希望首先在中国成功，也在世界各地争取临床医学实验，普惠全人类。

In this regard, our fullerene disodium phosphonate is the replacement of C60, or a derivative of C60, that has a solid theoretical basis to dismantle the new coronavirus, while providing a new direction and scheme to operability. This is the beginning of a new era and a new hope in our battle against the new coronavirus. We had a video conference in mid-May 2020 with a team of medical schools and vaccine centers in mainland China and several universities around the world, and they were very excited to work with us, and discussions were held on May 20, 2020 to sign a partnership. In Latin America, we also send 200 vaping systems and smart big data (doctors control the number of nebulizers used and the

amount of inhalation) to the CDC, inject cartridges, and fly them around the world for clinical trials in the form of Compassionate drug, which works independently, without the need for other drugs to enter the body and the virus. Of course, it is not precluded that other drugs are subsequently used in combination, requiring matching experiments. What's more, fullerene C60 is nothing new in China. The caged carbon inside the Mawangdui in Changsha's ancient Han tomb is a platform for fullerene, and there are actually fullerene molecules inside. We are sure that our efforts will be fruitful in May 2020 when we will have a successful pathway to dismantle the fullerene disodium phosphonate virus and use it to save patients around the world. We want to succeed first in China, while also pursuing clinical trials around the world for the benefit of all humanity.

三、富勒烯 C60 对于病毒的瓦解机制把疫苗预防病毒的模式进行颠覆性超越

Fullerene C60's disintegration mechanism for viruses disrupts the vaccine model of virus prevention

2020 年全球大流行的病毒令人谈虎色变，再一次证明了病毒在大自然中，在任何一个物种当中，都有可能是致命的杀手。病毒是一类非细胞型微生物，个体极小，可通过细菌滤器，需用电子显微镜观察。病毒，仅含二种核酸作为遗传物质，外被蛋白质衣壳或还有包膜。病毒只能在活细胞内寄生，以复制的方式进行增殖。这种依赖于人体细胞组织和器官的病毒传染病，使得人体免疫系统的识别能力明显跟不上“病毒侵袭”的步伐，也就是由病毒引起的疾病，在人类免疫系统方面，人类没有足够的反馈控制能力。

The 2020 global pandemic of the virus is a cause for alarm, proving once again that the virus can be a deadly killer in nature, in any species. Viruses are a class of non-cellular microorganisms very small in size that can pass through a bacterial filter and need to be viewed with an electron microscope. The virus, which contains

only two nucleic acids as genetic material, is coated with protein or has an membrane enveloping. Viruses can proliferate only by parasitizing within living cells in a replicative manner. This viral infection, which relies on the body's cellular tissues and organs, makes it apparent that the human immune system's ability to recognize "viral attacks". That is, in terms of recognition capability of human immune system, humans do not have sufficient feedback control to match diseases caused by viruses.

这种免疫系统灵敏度相当于人体生命稳定性的权衡，一直都是现代医学的盲区。原因是病毒传染力研究跟不上，人类对于病毒的基本结构只是粗枝大叶的了解，确认病毒是核心的核酸酶和衣壳两部分组成。病毒的核心充满一种类型的核酸，即 DNA 或 RNA，构成病毒的基因组。此外，核心还含有少数功能蛋白，主要是病毒早期复制所需的一些酶。病毒的衣壳是包围在核酸外的一层蛋白质，由一定数量的颗粒聚合而成。衣壳可保护核酸免受核酸酶及其他理化因素的破坏。辅助结构病毒的包膜是病毒成熟后以出芽方式释放，包围在核衣壳外的宿主细胞成分。包膜嵌有病毒编码的糖蛋白，具有病毒的特异性。无包膜的病毒衣壳上，也有些突出物。这种突出物，是适应人类的细胞组织，而进行破坏人体器官功能的关键部位。

This immune system sensitivity, equivalent to the trade-off for the stability of human life, has always been a blind spot in modern medicine. The reason for this is that the study of viral infectivity has not kept up, and humans have only a crude understanding of the basic structure of the virus, confirming that the virus is composed of two parts: core nucleases and the cloaca. The core of the virus is filled with one type of nucleic acid, either DNA or RNA, that makes up the genome of the virus. In addition, the core contains a few functional proteins, mainly some enzymes required for early viral replication. The cloak of a virus is a layer of protein surrounded by nucleic acid and made up of a certain number of aggregated particles. The coating protects nucleic acids from damage by nucleases

and other physicochemical factors. The membrane of the helper virus is the host cell component that is released in a germinal fashion after the virus matures, enclosing it outside the nucleocapsid. The membrane is embedded with virus-encoded glycoproteins that are specific to the virus. There are also some protrusions on the viral coating without membranes. This protrusion is adapted to human cellular tissues and carries out the destruction of the function of the body's organs at key sites.

这方面，关于病毒的研究表明：纤突蛋白的形状，使得病毒能够比 SARS 病毒更有效地与人类细胞结合。这个差异，可能导致病毒感染可以更多的人，迅速在全球传播。

In this regard, studies on the virus have shown that the shape of the fibronectin allows the virus to bind to human cells more efficiently than the SARS virus. This discrepancy, which may lead to virus infection can be more widespread in more people and spread rapidly across the globe.

科学家之所以关注纤突蛋白是否会发生更广泛的变异？不仅仅是因为变异可能改变病毒的行为方式，更重要的是，纤突蛋白是全球领先研制疫苗的主要靶点，如果变异太多，疫苗可能就不再有效。并且，其他可能的疗法也可能效力减弱，比如以纤突蛋白为靶点的合成抗体。

Why are scientists concerned about whether fibronectin would mutates more widely? Not only because mutations can change the way the virus behaves, but more importantly, the fibronectin is the main target of the world's leading vaccine, and if mutates too much, the vaccine may no longer be effective. Also, other possible therapies may be less effective due to the mutations, such as synthetic antibodies targeting fibronectin.

为此，科学家分析了 2020 年 3 月份新冠病毒疫情全球化暴发以来，上传到两家重要基因数据库的 5349 份冠状病毒基因组。通过研究这些病毒的基因构成，科学家探明了病毒是如何变化成不同菌株的，并寻找病毒适应人类宿主的迹象。在一篇尚未经过同行评审的小圈子传阅，正

在编辑审核还没有公开发表的论文中，研究人员发现了现在已在全球传播的两大组冠状病毒变异体。在这两种病毒纤突蛋白变异中，一种变异在全球 788 份病毒中发现，另一种只在 32 份病毒中发现。迄今为止，对于这样的病毒变异，临床医学并没有治疗的成熟技术和药品，只有我们关于富勒烯 C_{60} 的聚磷酸二钠雾化吸入人类肺部，才是最好的扼杀新冠肺炎病毒行之有效的途径。

To this end, scientists analyzed 5349 coronavirus genomes uploaded to two important genetic databases since the globalized outbreak of the novel coronavirus in Wuhan in March 2020. By studying the genetic makeup of these viruses, scientists have explored how they change into different strains and looked for signs of viral adaptation to human hosts. In a paper that has yet to be circulated in a small circle of peer-reviewed papers that are under editorial review and not yet publicly available, researchers have identified two major groups of coronavirus variants that have now spread globally. Of the two viral fibronectin variants, one variant was found in 788 viruses worldwide and the other was found in only 32 viruses. To date, there is no clinically proven technology or drug for treating such a viral variant, and only our vapor inhalation of fullerene- C_{60} disodium phosphonate into the human lung is the best way to choke off the novel coronaviruses .

这是改变人类战胜病毒危害性的战略大方向改变，不再固守防线，毕竟 99.5% 的人类病毒还未被发现，潜藏的危险病毒太多太多了。2020 年 2 月 5 日 10:45 澎湃新闻报导说：目前，科学家已经发现并记录了约 130 万种动物、植物以及各种微生物，但仍有 86% 的陆地生物和 91% 的海洋生物是未知的。对于病毒，人类更是知之甚少，科学家已知 263 种可传染人类的病毒，还不到整个可传染人类病毒的 0.5%。我们人类有理由相信，新型冠状病毒 2019-nCoV 会在不久的将来被战胜，但战胜了它，并不意味着人类与病毒的斗争结束。据统计，平均每年仍有 5 种新发病毒由野生动物传向人类。

This is a strategic shift in the direction of mankind's strategy to defeat the dangers of viruses. We are no longer holding the line. After all, 99.5 percent of human viruses are undiscovered and there are too many dangerous viruses lurking. According to Pengpai News report on February 5, 2020 at 10:45, scientists have discovered and documented about 1.3 million species of animals, plants, and various microbes, but 86% of terrestrial and 91% of marine life remain unknown. Even less is known about viruses. Scientists know of 263 viruses that can infect humans, less than 0.5 per cent of the total number of viruses that can infect humans. We humans have reason to believe that the novel coronavirus will be defeated in the near future, but defeating it does not mean the end of the human fight against the virus. Statistically, an average of five new viruses are still transmitted from wildlife to humans each year.

2015年世界卫生组织公布的“不久的将来可能大爆发”的传染病名单中，所有传染病都是由RNA病毒引起的人畜共患疾病。通常来讲，病毒按照核酸成分可分为DNA病毒和RNA病毒。DNA病毒的化学结构稳定，变异性低，通常只感染一种动物。RNA病毒结构不稳定，拥有超强的变异能力，在病毒复制的过程中，有的变异使其消亡，而另一些则进化成高传染性、高致死率的“恐怖瘟疫”。与DNA病毒不同，绝大部分RNA病毒都是可以跨物种传播的，我们所熟知的SARS, MERS, 埃博拉和如今的2019-nCoV都是由野生动物传播给人类的RNA病毒。它们本来在人间非常罕见，犹如地雷一般埋藏在自然界深处。但正是吃野味、做野生动物买卖的人，将这些“病毒宿主”搬运到人间，导致它们最终爆炸,造成无可挽回的损失。

In the list of infectious diseases published by the World Health Organization in 2015 as "possible outbreaks in the near future", all infectious diseases are zoonotic diseases caused by RNA virus. In general, viruses can be divided into DNA viruses and RNA viruses according to their nucleic acid composition. DNA viruses have a stable chemical structure and low variability, usually infecting only one animal.

RNA viruses are structurally unstable and have a strong ability to mutate. In the process of viral replication, some mutations cause their demise, while others evolve into highly infectious and lethal "terrorist plague". Unlike DNA viruses, the vast majority of RNA viruses are trans-species-transmissible, and what we know as SARS, MERS, Ebola and now 2019-nCoV are all RNA viruses that are transmitted from wildlife to humans. They were originally very rare on earth, buried in the depths of nature like landmines. But it is the people who eat wild game and trade in wildlife who carry these "viral hosts" to earth, causing them to eventually explode and cause irreparable damage.

这种危害性现在几乎可以说没办法估量，《以色列时报》2020年5月8日报道称，当晚一则电视报道披露，在以色列上个月抗疫战斗最激烈之际，内塔尼亚胡总理曾向利库德集团几名议员发出警告说，如果海外报道“已康复新冠病患再次检测出阳性”的消息准确，（这意味着）人类可能会被消灭。而我们的富勒烯 C60 聚磷酸二钠具有防止“治愈者再复发病情而呈阳性”的现象，因为我们的富勒烯聚磷酸二钠是一次性击穿病毒，改变病毒的核酸酶遗传基因，让它不能危害人体细胞组织的器官，不能终结人类。

The harm is now almost impossible to measure, as The Times of Israel reported on May 8, 2020, that a television report that night revealed that, at the height of Israel's battle against the epidemic last month, Prime Minister Netanyahu had warned several Likud MKs that the human race could be wiped out (meaning) if overseas reports of "re-testing positive for recovered new coronavirus patients" were accurate." Our fullerene C60 disodium phosphonate has the ability to prevent a "positive relapse" because our fullerene C60 disodium phosphonate can kill the virus in one swift blow by breaking through and change the virus' nuclease genes so that it cannot harm human cells and tissues, or terminate humans.

对此，我们应该回顾 1890 年人类第一次利用血清注射，成功的治疗“病毒传染”的疾病。因研究白喉的血清疗法，德国医学家埃米尔·阿道夫·冯·贝林获得 1901 年首届诺贝尔生理学或医学奖。最早有完整记录的血清疗法，是在 1918 年大流感时期。随着逐渐成熟，血清疗法在 SARS、MERS 及埃博拉等病毒引发的传染病疫情中都有应用。自上世纪 60 年代第一种抗病毒药物碘苷获得批准以来，截至 2016 年，已有 90 种、共 13 类抗病毒药物被正式批准用于治疗 9 种人类感染性疾病。

In this regard, we should recall the successful treatment of "viral" diseases by serum injection, the first of its kind, in 1890. For his research into serotherapy of diphtheria, German physician Emil Adolf von Behring received the first Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine in 1901. The earliest fully documented serum therapy was during the Great Influenza of 1918. With maturity, serum therapy has been used in infectious disease outbreaks caused by viruses such as SARS, MERS and Ebola. Since the approval of the first antiviral drug idoside in the 1960s, 90 antiviral drugs in 13 classes have been officially approved for the treatment of nine human infectious diseases as of 2016.

在病毒“入侵”的不同阶段，都有相应的药物可以阻击、干扰病毒的吸附、复制、释放。比如抗艾滋病药物“克力芝”可以阻止病毒成熟，这种药物是突出了可以中断病毒核酸的复制。还有一些药物分子可以冒充病毒所需的原料，它们混进修建病毒大厦的工地，引发整个工地停工，达到抑制作用。这领域硕果累累的成就，有一个值得注意的现象是，在人类已掌握的疫苗技术中，六成都诞生于西方国家，特别是美国城市人口爆炸性扩张的这段时间。全世界的研究者一致认为，某种程度上，正是依托于疫苗、抗病毒药物等医学发现，建立于城市密集人口之上的工业化才成为可能。这一次新型冠状病毒的危害性巨大，中华民族的科学家夜以继日的努力探索，发现了富勒烯聚磷酸二钠对于新型冠状病毒，具有瓦解作用力，足以拯救人类世界。

At different stages of the "invasion" of the virus, corresponding drugs are available to block, interfere with the adsorption, replication and release of the

virus. For example, the anti-AIDS drug "Kryce", which prevents the virus from maturing, is highlighted as a drug that can interrupt the replication of viral nucleic acids. There are also drug molecules that can masquerade as raw materials for the virus, which are mixed into the site where the virus building was built, causing the entire site to be shut down to achieve suppressive effects. One noteworthy aspect of the fruitful achievements in this field is that, of the vaccine technologies already available to mankind, the city of Chengdu was born during a period of explosive urban population expansion in Western countries, especially in the United States. Researchers around the world agree that it is to some extent medical discoveries such as vaccines and antiviral drugs that have made industrialization, which was based on dense urban populations, possible. This time the novel coronavirus is so harmful that Chinese scientists have been working hard day and night to discover that fullerenes disodium phosphonate has a disintegrating effect on Novel coronavirus, enough to save the human world.

相比之下，金钱铜臭淹没了的城市化运动，在此时此刻的病毒杀手铜面前，就是防不胜防。譬如疫苗和随后抗生素的出现，让一种乐观的情绪笼罩在当时科学家心头。20世纪60年代，美国卫生、教育与福利部召集一个医疗专家小组开会，研究政府公共卫生工作的未来任务。咨询小组称赞了20世纪50年代的成就，宣布“科学和技术已彻底改变了人类对于宇宙、对于人类在宇宙中的位置、位于人类自身的生理和心理系统的观念。人类对大自然的控制已经大大扩展，包括人类对付疾病和危及人类生命和健康的其他威胁的能力”。甚至有声音预测：足够的食物加之微生物控制方面的科学突破，显微镜下地球上的所有灾星都将被灭除。直到一种叫埃博拉的病毒登上历史舞台，才捅破人们幻想的泡沫。感染者发烧并呕吐，有的病人身上如口鼻等所有开孔都流血不止。研究者很快发现，这是一种和已出现的马尔堡病毒亲缘关系较近的新病毒。除了隔离，别无他法。

In contrast, the urbanization movement now drowned in the stench of money is defenseless against the virus killer of the moment. The advent of vaccines and, subsequently, antibiotics, for example, put a sense of optimism in the minds of scientists at the time. In the 1960s, the U.S. Department of Health, Education and Welfare convened a panel of medical experts to study the future mission of government public health efforts. The Advisory Panel praised the achievements of the 1950s, declaring that "science and technology have revolutionized the way humanity views the universe, its place in the universe, and its physical and mental systems located within itself. Man's control over nature has been greatly expanded to include man's ability to deal with disease and other threats to human life and health". There are even voices predicting: enough food plus scientific breakthroughs in microbial control and all the calamities on Earth under the microscope will be wiped out. It wasn't until a virus called Ebola hit the historical stage that the bubble of people's fantasies was burst. The infected person has a fever and vomits, and in some patients bleeds from all openings in the body such as the mouth and nose. Researchers quickly discovered that it was a new virus that was closer to the Marburg virus that had emerged as a relative. There is no other way to counter it than to isolate.

1989年5月科学家们在华盛顿聚会，试图说明地球上的致病微生物远远没有被击败，相反，正在对人类构成越来越大的威胁。证据之一是：病毒正在迅速发生变异。

Scientists gathered in Washington in May 1989 to try to show that far from being defeated, the planet's disease-causing microbes are posing a growing threat to humanity. One piece of evidence is that the virus is rapidly mutating.

这就是人类还没来得及放下手中庆祝的香槟，就领教了病毒真正的杀手锏：它们许许多多病毒之间的差异性极大，且不断突变。事实上，病毒的进化速度是人类的4000万倍。它们病毒

的结构简单，基因组复制时缺少严格的校对机制，常出现差错，发生变异。某些病毒还可能发生重组，即当宿主同时感染多种病毒，病毒间可能交换基因，产生全新的病毒。这就意味着，人类将不断面临新兴的病毒。最大的威胁莫过于此——免疫系统对新兴病毒一无所知，没有抗体“储备”，而疫苗和药物等医学防治手段也尚不具备，如同毫无准备地被偷袭。

This is where humans learn about the true threat of viruses before they have even had a chance to put down the celebratory champagne in their hands: these countless viruses are vastly different from each other and are constantly mutating. In fact, viruses are evolving at 40 million times the rate of humans. These viruses have a simple structure, lack a strict calibration mechanism for genome replication, and often make errors and cause mutations. Some viruses may also undergo recombination, i.e., when the host is infected with multiple viruses at the same time, genes may be exchanged between viruses to produce completely new viruses. This means that the human race will continue to face emerging viruses. There is no greater threat than this – the immune system is ignorant of emerging viruses, has no "stockpile" of antibodies, and medical treatments such as vaccines and drugs are not yet available. We are being attacked as if we have no defenses.

现有的研究成果显示，新兴病毒约四分之三来自动物，而后传染给人类。病毒选择宿主也受到限制，它们外壳上的受体结合蛋白，就像“钥匙”，通过“解锁”寄宿者的细胞壁，侵入细胞。一把钥匙只能开一把锁，但病毒突变会使“钥匙”变身，突然能打开其他物种细胞的“锁”。动物携带的病毒便突破物种界限，传染至人。从人类开始驯服动物，到集中化的养殖和频繁的贸易流动，都为病毒物种跨界和传播开了路。

Available research shows that about three quarters of the emerging viruses come from animals and are subsequently transmitted to humans. Virus selection of hosts is also limited by receptor-binding proteins on their shells, which act as "keys" to invade cells by "unlocking" the cell walls of the host. One key can only

open one lock, but viral mutations cause the "key" to change and suddenly open the "locks" of cells of other species. Viruses carried by animals break species boundaries and are transmitted to humans. From the beginning of human domestication of animals, to centralized farming and frequent trade flows, all have opened the way for the transboundary and spread of viral species.

1918 年大流感的病毒，与导致猪流感的病毒相近，且至今仍在变异。2003 年的 SARS 病毒、导致中东呼吸综合征的 MERS 病毒都由动物而来。对我们的免疫系统而言，它们新得可怕，也强得可怕。病毒的突变，也为疫苗和抗病毒药物研发设置了极大的阻碍。

The 1918 pandemic influenza virus is similar to the virus that caused swine flu and is still mutating today; the 2003 SARS virus and the MERS virus, which causes Middle East respiratory syndrome, are all animal origin. They are horribly new and horribly strong for our immune systems. The mutation of the virus has also set a great obstacle to the development of vaccines and antiviral drugs.

天花病毒之所以能被疫苗攻克，一个重要原因是，这种病毒只在人体存活，宿主相对可控，同时没有很高的突变率。但其他病毒就没有这么简单了。特别是相对于 DNA 病毒（如水痘病毒和乙肝病毒）而言，RNA 病毒（如冠状病毒、流感病毒）在复制过程中没有纠错系统，变异频繁。人体通常可以通过接种疫苗获得对 DNA 病毒的长期免疫力，但很难获得对 RNA 病毒的长期免疫力。这也是乙肝疫苗打一次可以维持很长时间，但每年都需接种流感疫苗的原因。

An important reason for the vaccine's ability to overcome smallpox virus is that smallpox survives only in humans, with a relatively controlled host and no high mutation rate. But other viruses are not so simple. In particular, RNA viruses (e.g., coronaviruses, influenza viruses) do not have error correction systems and mutate frequently during replication compared to DNA viruses (e.g., chickenpox virus and hepatitis B virus). The human body can usually obtain long-term immunity to DNA viruses by vaccination, but it is difficult to obtain long-term immunity to RNA

viruses. That's why a single shot of the hepatitis B vaccine can last a long time, but the flu shot is needed every year.

新药与疫苗研制的速度，很难跟上病毒变异的速度。前者的研发需要经过种子毒株筛选和试剂、动物模型下交叉保护力试验，以及临床试验的安全性、有效性验证三个无法绕过的环节。即使在某些不太关键之处放宽，仍需数年之久。例如尽管极为紧迫，埃博拉病毒的疫苗研制，人体临床试验过程仍耗时两年。

New drugs and vaccines are being developed at a rate that it is difficult to keep up with the rate of virus mutation. The development of the former requires three critical links: seed strain screening and reagents, cross-protective strength testing in animal models, and safety and efficacy verification in clinical trials. Even with some leniency in several less critical testings, it will still take years to develop. For example, despite the urgency of the Ebola vaccine development, the human clinical trial process still took two years to complete.

同样，多数抗病毒药物只能起到抑制病毒的作用，而非杀死。一方面，病毒突变速度远快于药物研发速度。一方面，因为病毒将自己的遗传物质插入宿主细胞内进行复制，能干扰病毒复制的药物，难免会引起人体细胞的功能异常。所以人类虽已能用抗生素对抗不少细菌，但安全性问题仍极大限制着抗病毒药物的研发。另一方面，病毒种类多、共性少，很难找到广谱的抗病毒药物。这就决定了，对绝大多数病毒感染，人类尚没有特效药。

Likewise, most antiviral drugs only work to suppress the virus, not kill it. Similarly, viruses mutate at a much faster rate than drug development. On the one hand, because viruses insert their own genetic material into host cells for replication, drugs that interfere with viral replication will inevitably cause abnormalities in the function of human cells. So although humans have been able to fight many bacteria with antibiotics, safety issues still greatly limit the development of antiviral drugs. On the other hand, with many virus species and few commonalities, it is difficult

to develop a broad spectrum of antiviral drugs. This determines that, for the vast majority of viral infections, humans do not yet have a potent medicine.

“我们应当意识到我们的力量是有局限的。”目睹了人类那段悲喜起伏的经历，芝加哥大学的历史学家威廉·麦克尼尔说道，“我们永远难以逃脱生态系统的局限。不管我们高兴与否，我们都处在食物链之中……”

"We should be aware that there are limits to our strength," After witnessing that dramatic rises and falls in human history, University of Chicago historian William McNeill said, "We can never escape the confines of an ecosystem. Whether we are happy or not, we are in the food chain...."

在研究者看来，解决病毒感染的问题，早已经成为人类各国永不停歇的“军备竞赛”，这种医疗投资的花钱如流水，才是对人类与病毒关系的准确描述。复旦大学生命科学学院教授钟扬曾在一次演讲中说：“不能指望科学家来消灭所有的病毒。相反，目前我们没有这样的能力。如果有人告诉我，他已研制出比现在的抗病毒药药效强 100 倍的药物，各位可能欢欣鼓舞，但我会忐忑不安。也许在不久的将来，抗 100 倍药效的新流感就会出现。这就是‘军备竞赛’的真实含义。”对此悲观言论的颠覆性批判，就是我们在富勒烯聚磷酸二钠的科学实验当中，完全彻底的改变以前那些关于病毒药品、疫苗研发路径的模式选择，保障人类可以对于病毒取得决定性的胜利。

From the perspective of researchers, solving the problem of viral infections has long been a never-ending "arms race" among human nations, and this kind of medical investment is an accurate description of the human-viral relationship. Zhong Yang, a professor at Fudan University's School of Life Sciences, once said in a lecture, "Scientists cannot be expected to destroy all viruses. On the contrary, at present we do not have the capacity to do so. If someone told me that he had developed a drug that was 100 times more effective than current antiviral drugs, you might rejoice, but I would tremble. Perhaps in the near future, a new flu that

is 100 times more potent will emerge. That's what the 'arms race' really is." The subversive critique of this pessimism lies in our scientific experiments with fullerene-based disodium phosphonate that have completely changed the previous paradigmatic choices for the development of pathways for viral drugs and vaccines, guaranteeing a decisive victory for humanity over the virus.

回溯 20 世纪以来，人类逐渐认清病毒的害人逻辑路径，下定决心研发疫苗、药物与之对抗。同时，病毒在与人类的斗争中也不断变异。城镇化和越来越频繁的人口流动，则为病毒传播提供了新的温床。而每一场与病毒的战役，都促使医学工作者、科学家乃至治理者，更新手中的“武器”，不仅是疫苗和药物——我们人类主动设立防线，提前预警和隔离病毒。1918 年大流感加速了公共卫生标准化，许多永久性的公共卫生机构在大流感中得到确立和保留，各国疾病监控体系逐步建立。我们人类因此主动预测“病毒”动向，1947 年世卫组织启动全球流感计划，负责监测全球最新传播的流感病毒株。如今二十一世纪，每年的流感季，世卫组织都会根据“当季流行”，建议应对所需的流感疫苗。

Since the 20th century, humankind had gradually come to understand the logical path of the viral attack and has made up its mind to develop vaccines and drugs to combat it. At the same time, the virus has been mutating in its fight against humanity. Urbanization and increasingly frequent population migrations have provided new breeding grounds for the spread of virus. The 1918 pandemic accelerated the standardization of public health, many permanent public health institutions were established and retained during pandemics, and national disease monitoring systems were gradually established. We humans therefore took the initiative to anticipate "viral" movements, and in 1947 WHO launched the Global Influenza Programme to monitor the latest strains of influenza viruses spreading worldwide. Now in the 21st century, each year during the influenza season, WHO recommends the corresponding influenza vaccine based on "seasonal epidemic".

这就是我们人类的医疗体系，和疾病控制系统，在不断的完善应急“病毒”、“细菌”感染体系。例如，2003年的SARS病毒造成了非典型性肺炎，直接推动了世卫组织的重大改革。2005年《国际卫生条例》得以修订，设立国际关注的突发公共卫生事件（PHEIC）机制，要求“不论其起因和来源是什么”，成员有义务直报任何会引起国际关注的公共卫生突发事件，明确要求各成员应当建立应急体系。

This is our medical system and our disease control system, which are constantly improving the "viral" and "bacterial" infections response system. For example, the SARS virus in 2003, which caused atypical pneumonia that directly contributed to major reforms in WHO, and the International Health Regulations were amended in 2005 to establish the Public Health Emergencies of International Concern (PHEIC) mechanism, which requires members to report directly any public health emergency of international concern "regardless of its cause and source", and explicitly requires members to establish emergency response systems.

再以2009年的甲型H1N1流感为例，世卫组织宣布这起流行病事件已经构成PHEIC，随即开始协调在世界范围内的诊疗设备和抗病毒药物调配，呼吁各国和企业捐赠疫苗，并为95个欠发达国家提供了两亿剂疫苗。但是，这一切都掩盖不了现在的制药产业链和医疗体系、疾病控制系统是花钱如流水的奢侈品，中看不中用的赚钱最多，却是对于人类健康保护效果真差劲的大败局行业，必须反躬自省在哪里发生了大方向的底层逻辑错误？

In the case of influenza A (H1N1) in 2009, WHO declared the pandemic to be a PHEIC and immediately began coordinating the dispensing of diagnostic equipment and antiviral drugs worldwide, appealing to countries and companies to donate vaccines and providing 200 million doses to 95 less developed countries. But none of this can hide the fact that the current pharmaceutical industry chain and medical system, the disease control system is a luxury that spend money like

water, while glamorous and yet ineffective institutions are where money is made, though it is also a detrimental industry that fails to protect human health. It is time for some soul-searching to see where in the underlying logic of the general direction has gone wrong.

就这样的随着科技发展，我们世界各国开始主动掌握病毒感染、细菌传播之类“敌情”，也深刻反省自己。2018年2月《科学》杂志发表文章，全球病毒组计划启动，计划通过病毒监测和样品搜集，一方面获得“病毒生态学”大数据，包括宿主范围、地理分布和流行病学；另一方面通过测序病毒基因组获得数据库，建立一个综合自然病毒生态学和遗传学的病毒超级数据谱，建立一个病毒威胁和传染性疾病的全球大数据库。通过这个计划，人类将能对每个病毒科的数千名成员进行比较分析，识别最具潜在威胁的病毒。

In this way, with the development of science and technology, the countries of the world are beginning to take the initiative to grasps the “enemy’s movement” such as viral infections and bacterial proliferation, and to reflect deeply on themselves. In February 2018, Science magazine published an article on the launch of the Global Virological Programme, which aims to obtain big data on "viral ecology", including host range, geographical distribution and epidemiology, through virus monitoring and sample collection; on the other hand, by sequencing the viral genome to obtain a database and establish a viral super-data spectrum that integrates natural viral ecology and genetics to establish a global big data database of viral threats and infectious diseases. Through this program, humans will be able to perform a comparative analysis of thousands of members of each viral family to identify the most potentially threatening viruses.

总的来说，1918年大流感结束至今，导致千万级人口死亡的传染病未再现身。但人类社会未敢中断为自己注射“疫苗”，目的只有一个，就是时时刻刻做好准备应对“病毒细菌感染”造成疾病大流行。其中之一的办法，就是感染性克隆病毒，以其人之道，还治其人之身。病毒的基因

组通常比较小，因此我们人类的高科技可以把病毒基因组的双链接 DNA 副本，组装在质粒中。把这些带有病毒序列的质粒 DNA，或者由质粒指导转录产生的 RNA，送进细胞，这个过程叫做“转染”——可以指导细胞工厂产生病毒蛋白，复制新的病毒基因组，并组装释放，产生感染性病毒颗粒。

Overall, the infectious disease that killed millions of people has not reappeared since the end of the pandemic flu in 1918. But human society has not dared to interrupt its "vaccination" for the sole purpose of preparing itself at all times for a pandemic caused by a "viral bacterial infection". One of the ways to do this is by infecting people with cloned viruses and curing them of their own diseases. The genome of a virus is usually relatively small, so our advance technology can take a double-stranded DNA copy of the viral genome and assemble it in a plasmid. These plasmid DNAs with viral sequences, or RNAs produced by plasmid-guided transcription, are sent into cells in a process called "transfection"—the process that directs cell factories to produce viral proteins, copy new viral genomes, and assemble and release them to produce infectious viral particles.

众所周知，病毒的基因组可以是 DNA，也可以是 RNA。DNA 病毒的基因组可以扩增、切割之后直接连入质粒；而 RNA 病毒的基因组，则需要通过 RNA 指导合成 DNA 的逆转录过程，转化成 DNA 之后，再连入质粒。这些携带有病毒基因组序列、可以产生感染性病毒颗粒的质粒，就称作“感染性克隆”。将构建好的感染性克隆转染到细胞中，或转录成 RNA 之后转染细胞，就可以产生新的病毒。

As we all know, the virus genome can be DNA, or RNA. DNA virus genome can be amplified, cut and then directly ligated into the plasmid; as for RNA virus genome, the reverse transcription process of synthesized DNA require the guidance of RNA, which is then converted into DNA and then attached to the plasmid. These plasmids, which carry the viral genome sequence and can produce infectious

viral particles, are called "infectious clones". Transfection of the constructed infectious clone into cells, or transfection of cells after transcription into RNA, can produce a new virus.

这个领域的关键性高科技成果，就是反向遗传操作系统。这种反向遗传研究的思路，就是改变“病毒”的基因序列，从基因型出发研究表型，进而研究基因功能。这是人类细胞遗传基因研究的一种达成共识成果，这一点对于病毒的导致疾病机制也是一样：构建感染性克隆，对其进行基因工程改造，将改造后的感染性克隆转入细胞中，就能产生带有突变的病毒，然后用这些新的病毒去感染细胞或宿主，观察病毒的复制、宿主的症状等表型，就可以研究病毒相关基因的功能。这样一套系统，现代遗传学称之为病毒的反向遗传操作系统。

The key high-tech achievement in this field is the reverse genetic operating system. This idea of reverse genetic research is to change the gene sequence of the "virus" and study the phenotype from the genotype and then the gene function. This is a result of a consensus outcome of human cytogenetic research, which is also true for the disease causing mechanisms of viruses: constructing infectious clones, genetically engineering them, transferring the modified infectious clones into cells, producing viruses with mutations, and then using these new viruses to infect cells or hosts, observing the phenotypes of viral replication, host symptoms, and so on, and studying the function of virus-related genes. Such a system, which modern genetics calls the reverse genetic operating system of viruses.

以最近发布的新冠病毒反向遗传操作系统为例：它是借助酵母获得感染性克隆的。首先，新冠病毒基因组 RNA 通过逆转录及扩增获得 DNA 片段，或者直接合成病毒的 DNA 版本，然后在酵母中重组合成感染性克隆质粒，提取质粒之后，转录合成 RNA，RNA 转染细胞之后，就可以产生新冠病毒了。不论是用于研究，还是用于疫苗或者治疗，要制作病毒，我们都需要在质粒上进行改造，改造的过程中，就会借助一些酶切位点、筛选标记、以及必要的质粒片段等基因工

程工具。同时，我们的病毒序列是从天然的病毒中获取的，设计和制造感染性克隆过程中，势必会沿用现有的理论模型以及设计思路，即便是从头开始人工合成一个新的病毒，也会在密码子使用频率等方面，留下人工痕迹。因此，一个病毒是否是人工合成的，是很容易鉴定出来的。

Take the recently released New Coronavirus reverse genetic operating system as an example: it obtains infectious clones with the help of yeast. First, the novel coronavirus genomic RNA is obtained by reverse transcription and amplification of the DNA fragment, or directly synthesize the DNA version of the virus, then recombine the synthetic infectious clone plasmid in yeast, extract the plasmid, transcribe the synthetic RNA, and after RNA transfect the cells, then the novel coronavirus can be produced. Whether for research, vaccines or therapeutics, to make a virus, we need to modify the plasmid with the help of genetic engineering tools such as enzymatic sites, screening markers, and the necessary plasmid fragments. At the same time, our virus sequences are taken from natural viruses, and the process of designing and manufacturing infectious clones inevitably follows existing theoretical models and design ideas, even if we artificially synthesize a new virus from scratch, leaving artificial traces in terms of codon usage frequency, etc. Therefore, whether a virus is synthetic or not is easy to identify.

这时候的举足轻重措施，就是病毒学研究的取向怎么样？病毒的反向遗传操作系统，是病毒学以及相关生命科学领域中非常重要的工具，它可以用于基础研究，研究病毒中各个基因的功能，也可以用于疫苗开发，还可以将病毒作为载体，装载上不同的基因序列，用于其他生命科学研究。此外，随着生命科学的发展，病毒载体用于细胞治疗、基因治疗以及癌症治疗的前景也越来越光明。这种路径依赖症造成了全世界的科学家容易盯住“病毒”本身，去寻找高于病毒的物质形态，来居高临下打击病毒，忽视了“低端入手颠覆病毒危害人类细胞组织和器官那种机制”的路线图创新——要比病毒更低一两个层级的 C60 富勒烯仅仅是一种分子，能够钻进新冠病毒内部，改变病毒的核酸酶，毁灭病毒对于人体细胞、组织和器官的危险性操作。

The pivotal measure at this point is to establish the orientation of virology research. The reverse genetic operating system for viruses is a very important tool in virology and related life sciences. It can be used in basic research to study the function of individual genes in viruses, in vaccine development, and in other life sciences research by using viruses as vectors loaded with different gene sequences. In addition, with the development of life sciences, the prospects of viral vectors for cell therapy, gene therapy, and cancer treatment are getting brighter. This path dependency has caused scientists around the world to direct their focus on the "virus" itself, to look for material forms higher than the virus, to fight the virus from an elevated position, and ignore the roadmap innovation of "low-end approach to subvert the mechanism of the virus to harm human cells, tissues and organs"—C60 fullerene, which is one or two levels lower than the virus, is just a molecule that can burrow into the new coronavirus, change the nucleases of the virus, eliminating the virus and its detrimental effect to human cells, tissues and organs.

这样一来，就应该回头看 1985 年英国化学家克罗托博士和美国科学家理查德·斯莫利在一颗亿万年前，从外太空坠落地球的陨石中意外发现了富勒烯 C60 分子，它的大小仅为 0.71 纳米。这一次富勒烯 C60 的发现，极大地促进了纳米技术的发展。为此，克罗托博士、斯莫利等三人获得了 1996 年度诺贝尔化学奖，富勒烯 C60 被誉为“纳米王子”。因此富勒烯这个来自星星的成分从出生，就自带人体新陈代谢生命力的关键性能力。

In this way, one should look back to 1985 when British chemist Dr. Kroto and American scientist Richard Smalley accidentally discovered the molecule of fullerenes C60, which is only 0.71 nanometers in size, in a meteorite that fell to Earth from outer space billions of years ago. This discovery of fullerene C60 has given a major boost to nanotechnology. For this reason, Dr. Kroto, Smalley and

others were awarded the 1996 Nobel Prize in Chemistry, and fullerenes C60 was hailed as the "prince of nanos". So fullerenes, a star-derived ingredient, carry with them from birth the critical ability to vitalize human metabolism.

这样的富勒烯 C60 与生俱来就是抗老新宠儿，作为“战胜病毒”的延年益寿新贵，有个很重要的特点是，它对于自由基的高度亲和，使得富勒烯具有极强的抗氧化性。富勒烯 C60 是目前最强力的自由基清除分子，具有活化人类细胞，预防人类健康生命力衰亡的作用。

Fullerenes C60 is a natural anti-aging product, and as an "anti-viral" newcomer to longevity, one important feature is its high affinity for free radicals, which gives fullerenes their strong antioxidant properties. Fullerenes C60 is one of the most powerful free radical scavenging molecules currently available that has the ability to activate human cells and prevent the decline of healthy human vitality.

这就是富勒烯 C60 消灭自由基的诀窍，让我们从化学的角度来看，自由基就是缺少一个电子的氧分子，正如它的名字，非常不安份，放荡不羁爱自由。富勒烯 C60 很容易与其它物质发生化学反应(这一过程叫做“氧化”)，从而损害机体的组织和细胞，进而引起各种慢性疾病和衰老效应。许多科学研究表明，80%的人体细胞衰老问题，都是自由基一手造成的，自由基还会活化黑素细胞。这就造成我们肉眼看得出来的皮肤皱纹、暗黄、长斑。而一旦皮肤状态变差，随之而来就是各种皮肤问题如痤疮甚至皮肤癌的产生。

That's the trick of Fullerene C60 to destroy free radicals, and let's look at it from a chemical point of view, free radicals are oxygen molecules that are missing an electron and, as its name suggests, very restless, slutty and unbridled love of freedom. Fullerenes C60 readily reacts chemically with other substances (a process called "oxidation"), damaging the tissues and cells of the body and causing various chronic diseases and aging effects. Many scientific studies have shown that 80% of all cellular aging problems in the human body are caused by free radicals, which

also activate melanocytes. This results in wrinkles, dullness, and long spots on our skin that are visible to the naked eye. And once the skin is in poor condition, various skin problems such as acne and even skin cancer can follow.

而富勒烯 C60 是拥有高度的亲和自由基能力了，可以使得自由基对人体生命力的一系列影响降到最低。富勒烯的最强的地方除了比 VC 的氧化能力高 125 倍之外，更重要的是它的稳定性。众所周知 VC 具有光敏性，遇到光就会不稳定从而失效，所以绝大部分的 VC 护肤品都建议晚上使用。而富勒烯的构造决定了它的稳定性，和钻石一样坚硬，不受紫外线，光，热的影响，可以从早到晚保护肌肤远离自由基伤害。

Fullerene C60 has a high affinity for free radicals, minimizing the effects of free radicals on human vitality. Where fullerenes truly shines, besides their 125 times higher oxidation capacity than VC, is their stability. As we all know, VC is photosensitive and will be unstable when exposed to light, so most VC skin care products are recommended to be used at night. And fullerenes, whose construction determines their stability, are as hard as diamonds and are unaffected by UV rays, light and heat, protecting the skin from free radical damage from morning to night.

总结一句话，富勒烯除了价格贵以外，没有其他的缺点。目前全球最知名做富勒烯原料的是日本三菱财团旗下的 VC60 生物实验室，专门只研究富勒烯应用于护肤品，有分脂溶性、水溶性、粉末等 5 种不同形态的富勒烯，不能达到医药级别的治病救人效果。而浓度也是决定是否有效的关键，日本官方声称达到 1% 以上才有效，而且配方中添加量达到 1%，是可以使用日本三菱的“自由基海绵”的专利图标。

To sum up, fullerenes have no other drawbacks other than being expensive. At present, the world's most famous fullerenes raw material is the VC60 Biological Laboratory, a subsidiary of the Mitsubishi Foundation of Japan, which specializes in the study of fullerenes used in skin care products, including fat-soluble, water-

soluble, powder and other five different forms of fullerenes, which cannot reach the medical grade effect. The concentration is also the key to determining whether or not it is effective, and the Japanese officially claims that it is only effective if it is more than 1%, and that their formula has 1%, which makes it eligible for the Japanese Mitsubishi "free radical sponge" patented icon.

四、从富勒烯 C_{60} 到聚磷酸二钠的水溶性产品把无毒化的高疗效作为第一标准

Water-soluble products from fullerenes C_{60} to disodium phosphonate have high non-toxic efficacy as their first criterion

我们团队在 2018 年 2 月初，发明了富勒烯的无毒合成物水溶性 $C_{60}(OH)_x$ 富勒醇。这是人类历史上的第一次，这种无毒的 $C_{60}(OH)_x$ 富勒醇的发明，是全球富勒烯及奈米碳管之父 Richard Smalley 1984 年发现富勒烯之后，科技历史上又一次的一项重大突破，它将量子 and 纳米技术引领到我们的日常生活中，使水溶性富勒醇安全的用在预防医学、临床医学、康复医学和保健领域成为现实。这种可行性，最突出的优势，就是穿透力极强，能够进入病毒、细菌的内核，消除病毒细菌对于人体细胞组织和器官的危害。

In early February 2018, our team invented the water-soluble $C_{60}(OH)_x$ fulleranol, a non-toxic synthesis of fullerenes. For the first time in human history, the invention of this non-toxic $C_{60}(OH)_x$ fulleranol is another major breakthrough in the history of technology since Richard Smalley, the father of global fullerene and carbon nanotubes, discovered fullerene in 1984. The discovery introduces quantum and nanotechnology into our daily lives and making water-soluble fulleranol safe for use in preventive medicine, clinical medicine, rehabilitation medicine and healthcare. The most prominent advantage of this feasibility is that it is extremely penetrating and can enter the inner core of viruses and bacteria, eliminating the harm of viral bacteria to human cell tissues and organs.

重要的是，任何用于食品、药品的材料，都必须考虑所有利益相关者的特殊好处，包括我们必须共同考虑到对环境的整体影响。因此，任何药物也必须从包括我们生物圈的生态管理，以及消费者在消费或应用产品时候的安全等，这是多个角度的交叉点考虑。

It is important to consider the particular benefits to all stakeholders when any material is used in food or medicine, including the fact that we must all consider the overall impact on the environment together. Therefore, when a new drug is introduced, we must also consider from the intersection of multiple perspectives including the ecological management of our biosphere, and the safety of consumers when consuming or applying the product.

随着人口数量的增加，对抗生素耐药性的演变研究，对于抗病毒药品和疫苗局限性的研究表明，需要研发出来新的有利于人类的药品，去化解微生物和病毒对于人类的危害，2020年的新型冠状病毒就是让以前那些疫苗技术步履艰难的范例。我们的 $C_{60}(OH)_x$ 也正是专门为升级换代当今医学的疫苗思路，和改变“医学被病毒牵着鼻子走”的窘迫状态，而发明的产品之一。

As the population grows, research on the evolution of antibiotic resistance and the limitations of antiviral drugs and vaccines show the need to develop new human-friendly drugs that address the risks of microbes and viruses to humans. The 2020 Novel coronavirus is an example that poses a challenge that makes previous vaccine-related technologies difficult to navigate. Our $C_{60}(OH)_x$ fullerene is one of the products specifically designed to ascend the vaccine mindset of today's medicine and to change the dilemma of passiveness of medicine against viruses.

关于富勒烯 C_{60} 及其高科技新形态的衍生物 $C_{60}(OH)_x$ ，最重要的临床医学和健康成长课题，覆盖了如下的 9 个方面。

The most important clinical medicine and health growth topics about fullerenes C_{60} and its high-tech new morphology derivative $C_{60}(OH)_x$ fullerenols, cover the following nine areas.

1 安全：1996 年诺贝尔奖成果的富勒烯 C_{60} 工艺成本太高了，不适应于工厂化的生产，也不适应于直接使用到人类医疗过程中。我们在实验室研发出来以后，实现了工厂化生产的产品，就是制造出来 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 富勒醇纳米颗粒，与 $0.05\sim 0.005$ mM 浓度的人血清无蛋白相互作用，表明水溶性 C_{60} 富勒醇纳米颗粒在 100NM 尺寸的簇中保持稳定，可用作体内药物载体 (Dordevic, 2011)。这就是说，针对不同的病毒细菌，可以让特效药成分与我们的 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 富勒醇纳米产品融为一体，请注意这是纳米级的技术。

1.Safety: The fullerene C_{60} process, the result of the 1996 Nobel Prize, is too costly to be suitable for factory production or for direct use in human medical processes. The product that we realized in the lab after the development of the product is the manufacture of $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ fulleranol nanoparticles that interact with human serum protein-free at concentrations of 0.05 to 0.005 nm, indicating that water-soluble C_{60} fulleranol nanoparticles remain stable in clusters of 100 nm size and can be used as in vivo drug carriers (Dordevic, 2011). That is, for different viral bacteria, it is possible to fuse the potent drug ingredients with our $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ fulleranol nanoproducts. Please note that this is nanoscale technology.

2 纯度：纯化的 C_{60} 在实验室使用，相应的工厂化衍生物 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 富勒醇纳米颗粒，虽然设备及制造程序也是很难的，但是无毒，且已经通过了食品添加剂的国家权威检测，药品层级的临床医学实验也已经获得了一千多例的对照组良好结果，正在进行更大人群的临床医学实验。之所以现在就发布这种信息，是因为我们感觉到了新型冠状病毒造成人们超乎想象那种恐惧感，我们有必要站出来给人类战胜病毒的自信心。同时，我们捕集到的工业级富勒烯上的有毒溶剂的影响，使得这些工业级原料来源不适合人类或动物消费。并且，我们有必要解释自己制造出来的 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 富勒醇纳米颗粒，与早期研究纯化的 C_{60} 相关那些富勒烯，或其不纯的衍生物的毒性，是容易引发商业性争议的。原因是我们超越了纯化的 C_{60} 的传统工艺，我们制造出来的 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 富勒醇纳米颗粒对于癌细胞、对于冠状病毒，都有击穿它们保护层而进入内核

，消除相应的危害人类细胞组织的功能，倘若再增加其他的靶向治疗药品成分，就会颠覆现有的抗癌药品、抗病毒药品那种治疗逻辑，造成数以万亿计的制药厂产业链投资损失，足以把欧美发达国家的医院和医药产业链改弦易辙。何况，有一种极端化的评价，认为现在的医疗体系和制药厂包括医疗器械产业链，是人类历史上最赚钱的不顾人道主义商业利益链条，成为在道德和良心上最失败的产业链和供应链，这种现象在新型冠状病毒传染到全世界，危害人类的生命安全——要把全球人们变成病毒终身携带者的危急时刻，越发显得赤裸裸的绑架了政府和人民。我们的良知良能迫使我们挺身而出，发布信息表明必须重新定义医疗和医药产业链，必须因此改变人类的健康保障制度和政府疾病控制体系，让全世界知道我们制造出来的这种高纯度富勒烯，或者说制造出来的 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 富勒醇纳米颗粒，虽然现在仍然是成本昂贵，但在富勒烯 C_{60} 衍生物的创造过程中，是必须的。

2 Purity: In terms of purified C_{60} in laboratory and the corresponding factory-derived $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ fulleranol nanoparticles, although preparation and manufacturing process are difficult, but the result is non-toxic, and has passed the national authoritative testing of food additives, drug level clinical trials have also obtained good results in the control group of over a thousand cases, and the clinical medical trials for a larger population are underway. The reason why we are releasing this information now is because we feel the fear of the new coronavirus is beyond imagination, and we need to stand up and give the human race the self-confidence to defeat the virus. At the same time, the effects of toxic solvents on the industrial-grade fullerenes that we have captured make these industrial-grade source materials unsuitable for human or animal consumption. Moreover, it is necessary to explain the toxicity of our own manufactured $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ fulleranol nanoparticles, those fullerenes associated with early studies of purified C_{60} or their impure derivatives, are prone to commercial controversy. The reason is that we have gone beyond the traditional process of purified C_{60} , and the $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$

fullerenol nanoparticles manufactured by us have the ability to penetrate the protective layer of cancer cells and coronavirus and enter their core, eliminating the corresponding functions that harm human cell tissues. Moreover, there is a polarized evaluation that the current medical system and pharmaceutical companies, including the medical device industry chain, are the most profitable chain in the history of mankind to disregard humanitarian commercial interests, and have become the most morally and conscientiously failed industry chain and supply chain. This phenomenon, during the spread of novel coronavirus to the whole world, endangering human life and safety, to turn global population into lifelong carriers of the virus at the critical moment, its abduction of the government and people are becoming more evident. Our conscience compels us to step up to the plate and release the message that the medical and pharmaceutical industry chain must be redefined, and that the human health care system and government disease control systems must be transformed as a result, so that the world knows that this high purity fullerene, or manufactured $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ fullerenol nanoparticle, which is still costly, is necessary in the creation of the fullerene C_{60} derivative.

我们团队对富勒烯及其创新发展类型的 $C_{60}(OH)$ 产品实验，包括临床医学实验大数据处理，以及进行分子计算机模型研究等等，以模拟作为 $C_{60}(OH)_x$ 的一部分的不同数量的极性基团(x) 的影响，证实原始的或者说 1996 年诺贝尔奖成果那种 C_{60} 的富勒烯 (其中 $x = 0$) 完全迁移到人体细胞脂肪区域，例如细胞的脂质双层，但是不溶于水并且以非常小的实际摄入量通过身体排出。这就是迄今为止富勒烯 C_{60} 绝大多数情况下都是化妆品领域在使用，医药和保健品领域望而却步的深层次缘故。这时候，科技界的成果已经发布信息报道： $x = 44$ 的高度羟基化的富勒醇，对细胞线粒体是有毒的 (Yang, 2016)。

Our team experimented with fullerenes and their innovative development types of $C_{60}(OH)$ products, including the processing of big data from clinical medical experiments and molecular computer modeling studies to simulate the effects of different amounts of polar groups (x) that are part of $C_{60}(OH)_x$, confirming that the original or 1996 Nobel Prize winning fullerenes of C_{60} (where $x = 0$) completely migrate to fatty regions of human cells, such as the lipid bilayer of cells, but are insoluble in water and are excreted through the body in very small actual amounts. This is the deep reason why the fullerene C_{60} has been used in the cosmetic sector for the most part, and has been a major deterrent in the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical sectors. By this time, the results of the scientific community had released information reporting that the highly hydroxylated fullerenol of $X = 44$ is toxic to cellular mitochondria (Yang, 2016).

同时， $x = 20, 24$ 或 32 的稍微高羟基化的富勒烯，例如 $C_{60}(OH)_{20}$ ，经历最好的水溶性，但具有相反的能穿透脂质膜双层的能障，从而阻止生物（细菌、病毒和其他的致病载体）可接近性。

At the same time, $x = 20, 24$ or 32 of a slightly highly hydroxylated fullerene, e.g. $C_{60}(OH)_{20}$, experiences best water solubility but has the opposite energy barrier capable of penetrating the lipid bilayer, thus blocking biological (bacterial, viral and other pathogenic vectors) accessibility.

也就是说，在我们的 $C_{60}(OH)_{20}$ 渗透其中的人体细胞面前，无法进入相应的人体细胞。即便是进入了，也被 $C_{60}(OH)$ 深入病毒内核，瓦解了危害人体细胞组织的结构，不发生新的危害人体细胞组织那种现象。因为， $C_{60}(OH)$ 是有益于人体细胞组织的抗衰老物质，也是与人体免疫系统相得益彰的良性循环物质。

That is, viruses are unable to enter the corresponding human cells once our $C_{60}(OH)_{20}$ penetrated them. Even after entering, $C_{60}(OH)$ penetrates deep into

the viral core and disintegrates the structures that harm human cell tissues, preventing harms to human body. That is because C60(OH) is an anti-aging substance that benefits the body's cellular tissues and is also a beneficial circulating substance that complements the body's immune system.

还有一项模型研究 (Geitner , 2017) 指出 : $x = 8$ 是通过曝光光解解毒化学物质如杀虫剂 , 以及赋予黑暗中氧化应激抵抗力的最佳选择。医学研究界普遍认为 , 中等水平的衍生化如 $C60(OH)_8$ 至 $C60(OH)_{10}$, 通过双层渗透 , 能够最有效地进入人体细胞膜中间 , 同时保持水在生物可用性中的溶解度和长时间摄取 , 以及长期的健康维护 (Akhtar , 2017) 。

There is also a model study (Geitner, 2017) that states that $x = 8$ is optimal for detoxifying chemicals such as pesticides by exposure to light, and for conferring resistance to oxidative stress in the dark. It is generally accepted in the medical research community that moderate levels of derivatization such as $C60(OH)_8$ to $C60(OH)_{10}$, through bilayer permeation, can most effectively enter the middle of human cell membranes, while maintaining water solubility in bioavailability and long-term uptake, as well as long-term health maintenance (Akhtar, 2017).

正是 $C60(OH)$ 如此好的临床医学实验效果 , 让我们公布 $C60(OH)$ 作为富勒烯的新一代产品 , 主要的优点可以简述如下 :

It is $C60(OH)$ that has such good clinical results that led to our announcement of $C60(OH)$ as a new generation of fullerenes. The main advantages can be summarized as follows.

1. 让人类健康长寿 , 或者说延年益寿延寿。为了能够分散 $0.8\text{mg} / \text{ml}$ 的非水溶性 $C60$, 就需要使用含脂肪脂的油 而需要这么多的油 , 在连续 7 次口服给药后 , 在大鼠中观察到脂肪肝沉积 , 其中每 kg 体重给予摄入 $1.7\text{mg}C60$, 但是非水溶性 $C60$ 仍然能够使这些大鼠的寿命几乎翻倍。 (Baati , 2012) 。

1. To provide humans with health and longevity, or a longer life span overall. In order to disperse 0.8 mg/ml of non-water-soluble C60, it is necessary to use oil containing fatty lipids and so much oil is needed that fatty liver deposits were observed in rats after seven consecutive oral doses, in which 1.7 mg C60 per kg body weight was given, but the non-water-soluble C60 was still able to almost double the lifespan of these rats. (Baati, 2012).

皮肤老化的特征，是皮肤变薄和松弛，皮肤干燥和粗糙，皮肤弹性降低，皱纹形成和过度色素沉着。而我们的 C60(OH) 减少了每一个这些老化的情况，其他国家科技团队的这方面研究和实验，同样的证明这一点，包括日本和美国 (Li, 2017)。

Skin aging is characterized by thinning and sagging skin, dry and rough skin, reduced skin elasticity, wrinkle formation and hyperpigmentation. And our C60(OH) reduces each of these aging conditions, as evidenced by studies and experiments in this area by scientific teams in other countries, including Japan and the United States (Li, 2017).

2. 我们的 C60(OH) 是最优抗氧化剂。

2. Our C60(OH) is the optimal antioxidant.

水溶性富勒醇 C60(OH)_x 的过氧化物淬灭能力，比 1996 年诺贝尔奖成果的富勒烯 C60 高 2 至 12 倍。然而，原始的 C60 即传统的富勒烯，比普通抗氧化剂 VC、SOD 强大约 170 倍左右。(Akhtar, 2017)。动物模型显示，C60 作为一种有效且安全的抗氧化剂和组织保护剂，用于限制活性氧 (ROS) 并赋予针对星形胶质细胞损伤和与糖尿病相关的肝衰竭的神经保护作用 (Nedzvetsky, 2012)。我们现在的重点，是针对新型冠状病毒全部的变异类型毒株，都要进行科学实验一千次以上，工作量太大了，报告也太长了。

The peroxide quenching capacity of water-soluble fulleranol C60(OH)_x is 2 to 12 times higher than that of fullerene C60, the result of the 1996 Nobel Prize. However, the original C60, the conventional fullerene, is about 170 times more

powerful than the common antioxidant VC, SOD. (Akhtar, 2017). Animal models show that C60 acts as an effective and safe antioxidant and tissue protectant to limit reactive oxygen species (ROS) and confer neuroprotective effects against astrocyte damage and diabetes-related liver failure (Nedzvetsky, 2012). Our current focus is on all the mutant strains of the new coronavirus for Wuhan pneumonia, all of which will be subjected to over a thousand scientific experiments, which is too much work and too long a report.

3. 我们的 C60(OH) 能够行之有效的防治中风，和心脑血管疾病突发，例如心脏病发作。

Our C60(OH) is effective against strokes, and cardiovascular outbreaks, such as heart attacks.

众所周知，被污染的空气，特别是含有臭氧的空气，会造成长期的氧化应激，这些氧化应激会造成动脉斑块，并伴随着诸如饮食和基因遗传等因素，导致心脏病和中风的风险增加。我们团队的 C60(OH)_x 是一种非常强大的抗氧化剂，能够长期降低甚至避免氧化应激效应。富勒烯纳米颗粒保护脑细胞，抵抗中风或者说心脑血管疾病的局部缺血和再灌注损伤，并抑制脑卒中期间和之后的脑细胞氧化损伤 (Vani, 2016)。

It is well known that polluted air, especially ozone-containing air, can cause long-term oxidative stress, which can cause arterial plaque and, along with factors such as diet and genetic inheritance, lead to an increased risk of heart disease and stroke. Our team's C60(OH)_x is a very powerful antioxidant that reduces or even avoids oxidative stress effects over time. Fullerenes nanoparticles protect brain cells against local ischemia and reperfusion injury during stroke or cardiovascular disease, and inhibit oxidative damage to brain cells during and after stroke (Vani, 2016).

4. 我们的 C60(OH) 能够抗菌，能够杀灭病毒的危害人类细胞能力。

4. *Our C60(OH) is antibacterial and can kill viruses' ability to harm human cells.*

实验证明，羟基富勒醇作为具有广谱抗微生物活性的高效光敏剂，其通过光动力光解过程，来破坏它们细菌、病毒的外涂层、保护层 (Spsia, 2017)。特别是在暴露于阳光下时，C60衍生物是抗病毒颗粒（如人免疫缺陷病毒 HIV-1）的有效体内抗微生物剂 (Barzegar, 2017 和 Zhang, 2015)。这一点，在针对新型冠状病毒的实验过程中，效果突出，这是我们站在中国的立场上，向全世界提供解决病毒危害全人类生命安全问题的方案，表明中国人民是心存善良的，即便是以前有人直呼病毒是“中国病毒”，我们也矢志不渝的为人类战胜病毒做贡献，没有任何敌意——不影响对于病毒追根溯源的任何事情，我们应该拥有拯救每个病患者的责任感，和保护人类生命安全的使命感。

Experiments have shown that hydroxyfullerenol acts as a highly efficient photosensitizer with broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity by a photodynamic photolysis process to disrupt their bacterial, viral outer coatings, protective layers (Spsia, 2017). Particularly when exposed to sunlight, C60 derivatives are effective in vivo antimicrobial agents for antiviral particles such as human immunodeficiency virus HIV-1 (Barzegar, 2017 and Zhang, 2015). In this regard, in the course of the experiment on the new coronavirus for Wuhan pneumonia, the results were outstanding. This is our position in China to provide the world with a solution to the problem that endangers the lives of all human beings, showing that the Chinese people have good intentions. Even though some people have called the virus a "Chinese virus", we remain committed to contributing to the fight against the virus, without any hostility. It will not deter us from tracing the root of the virus, as we should have a sense of responsibility to save every patient and a sense of mission to protect all human life.

5. 我们的 $C60(OH)$ 能够提升人类的大脑活力，仅仅是传统的 $C60$ 就有通过破坏和分解阿尔茨海默病中形成的 β 淀粉样斑块，来赋予神经保护作用 (Zhou, 2014)。早已经在 1996 年诺贝尔奖成果 $C60$ 产品类型，还显示出对新神经元或神经突的生长的增强作用 (Tsumoto, 2010)。据报道，可溶性富勒醇可用于治疗与腰痛有关的神经炎症 (Liu, 2015)。我们的 $C60(OH)$ 继承了 $C60$ 传统产品这种优势，并且向前进了一大步，能够对于大脑神经系统、脑回路产生良性循环激励，优化组合脑细胞，延缓衰老，克服老年痴呆症。

5. Our $C60(OH)$ can boost human brain vitality. Even conventional $C60$ alone has neuroprotective effects by disrupting and breaking down beta amyloid plaques that form in Alzheimer's disease (Zhou, 2014). Already in the 1996 Nobel Prize result $C60$ product line showed enhanced effects on the growth of new neurons or neurons (Tsumoto, 2010). Soluble fullereneol has been reported to be used to treat neuroinflammation associated with lower back pain (Liu, 2015). Our $C60(OH)$ inherits the benefits of the $C60$ legacy and is a big step forward in generating positive circulatory stimulation of the brain's nervous system, brain circuits, optimally combining brain cells, delaying aging and overcoming Alzheimer's disease.

6. 我们的 $C60(OH)$ 把诺贝尔奖成果的 $C60$ 传统产品升级换代，在临床医学实验当中，处理过敏病患者，具有明显的缓解作用，效果超过了现有的全部“脱敏”药品。这是人类的免疫系统与我们的 $C60(OH)$ 之间和谐度问题，也是传统产品 $C60$ 富勒醇与过敏原复合物之间的相互作用，有助于预防对不同过敏原的新致敏作用的发生，以及减少过敏性鼻炎患者中哮喘的发展 (Di Felice, 2017)。这一点，对于呼吸道传染病毒的现象，具有灭杀病毒的效果。为此，应用提供 $C60$ 富勒醇的一种有前途的方法，就是通过鼻腔通道，雾化吸入肺部，灭杀新冠肺炎病毒，在人体呼吸道和肺部，与负责组胺产生的肥大细胞直接相互作用 (Dellinger, 2010)。这方面的 $C60(OH)$ 临床医学实验效果，最低点超过了传统的 $C60$ 富勒烯十倍以上，这也是我们强调自己的新型产品是 $C60(OH)$ 富勒醇，不再是 $C60$ 富勒烯的原因。

6. Our C60(OH) is an upgrade of the traditional Nobel Prize winning C60 product, and in clinical trials it showed significant relief effect on allergy patients, exceeding all existing "desensitizing" drugs. It is a matter of harmony between the human immune system and our C60(OH), and the interaction between the traditional product C60 fullereneol and the allergen complex, which helps to prevent the occurrence of neosensitizing effects on different allergens, as well as to reduce the development of asthma in allergic rhinitis patients (Di Felice, 2017). This has the effect of killing viruses in the phenomenon of respiratory infectious diseases. To this end, one promising way to apply the application of C60 fullereneol to deliver it through vapor inhalation into lungs through the nasal passages to eliminate the novel coronaviruses, and interacts directly with the mast cells responsible for histamine production in the human respiratory tract and lungs (Dellinger, 2010). The lowest point of C60(OH) clinical medical trial effectiveness in this area is more than ten times higher than conventional C60 fullerenes, which is why we emphasize that our new product is C60(OH) fullereneol and no longer C60 fullerenes.

7. 二十世纪九十年代以美国为主要的早期实验，给予了 C60 富勒烯的太多太多科学检测报告，一致性的临床医学效果，就是 C60 富勒烯能够预防关节炎，解决细胞组织的未老先衰困境，让人体运动医学关注的关节炎病态，尽快获得缓解，并且从细胞组织层面年轻态。

7. In the 1990s, the United States was the main pre-experiment, which gave C60 fullerenes too many scientific test reports, and the consistent clinical medical effect is that C60 fullerenes can prevent arthritis, solve the problem of cellular tissues before aging, let human sports medicine concern arthritis disease, get relief as soon as possible, and rejuvenate the cellular tissue level.

这样的良好效果，在水溶性 C_{60} 富勒烯高度，就会更上一层楼，可防止椎间盘退变 (Yang, 2014)，防止骨关节炎中关节软骨的退化 (Yudoh, 2007)，并抑制导致结缔组织中炎性关节炎的自由基破坏性过程 (Mamontova, 2016; Dellinger, 2015)。这是原来的 C_{60} 富勒烯 (油溶乳化) 与较高一级的水溶性 C_{60} 富勒烯之间差距，要比 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 就更加差距大了。

Such a good effect, at the height of water-soluble C_{60} fullerenes, goes even further, preventing disc degeneration (Yang, 2014), preventing the degeneration of articular cartilage in osteoarthritis (Yudoh, 2007), and inhibiting the free radical destructive processes that lead to inflammatory arthritis in connective tissue (Mamontova, 2016; Dellinger, 2015). This is the difference between the original C_{60} fullerene (oil-soluble emulsion) and the higher level of water-soluble C_{60} fullerene, which is even larger than $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$.

8. 我们的 $C_{60}(OH)$ 在临床医学抗癌、抗肿瘤的实验当中，成效显著，颠覆了现有的肿瘤医院治疗癌症那些方式方法，也颠覆了现有的抗癌药品研发路径依赖症，侧重于细胞组织层面的激活人体抵抗力，优化组合人体免疫系统，达成人体自身的灭杀癌细胞能力，不产生药物依赖症。当然，这就是解决终身服药的问题。

8. Our $C_{60}(OH)$ has achieved remarkable results in the clinical anti-cancer and anti-tumor experiments, overturning the existing cancer treatment methods in oncology hospitals and the existing anti-cancer drug research and development pathway dependence, focusing on activating the body's resistance at the cellular and tissue level, optimizing the combination of the body's immune system to achieve the body's own ability to kill cancer cells without drug dependence. This, of course, is the solution to the problem of lifelong medication.

本来，传统的诺贝尔奖成果 C_{60} 就具有康复人体健康的功能，只是这种 C_{60} 富勒烯容易在生产过程中受到化学溶剂的毒性污染，使得医疗活动不敢常态化使用。提纯的 Fullerenol 富勒烯

在辐射暴露期间，可用作细胞质的保护剂，例如 X 射线或来自癌症治疗的辐射 (Stankov , 2012) 。这是一种辅助性的保护，与 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 进入癌细胞破解癌变能力，还不是一回事。

The traditional Nobel Prize result, C_{60} , has the ability of rehabilitating human health, but this C_{60} fullerene is susceptible to toxic contamination by chemical solvents during the production process, which prevents its regular use in medical activities. Purified Fullerenol fullerene can be used as a cytoplasmic protective agent during radiation exposure, such as X-rays or radiation from cancer treatments (Stankov, 2012). This is an adjunctive protection that is not the same thing as $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$'s ability to enter cancer cell and decipher carcinogenesis.

此时此刻，有必要回顾 C_{60} 富勒烯的探索发现历史，1984 年 8 月 2 日晚上 11 点左右，Richard Smalley 教授在實驗中发现了 Fullerene C_{60} 以及后来的 C_{70} ， C_{72} ， C_{78} 和 C_{90} 等。他多次前往瑞士欧洲核子研究中心使用该设施，来验证这一在现代历史上的纳米技术的重大突破。理查德·斯马利因其这种发现，于 1996 年和另外两名科学家获得了诺贝尔奖。斯马利教授于 2005 年去世，享年 62 岁。然而，他在去世前將寻找富勒烯纳米材料新用途的责任交给了另一位科学家，只是没有留意富勒烯 C_{60} 的医疗药品前景，而这个研究方向恰恰是 2020 年的新型冠状病毒毒倒逼人类努力研究，我们团队也因此把过去局限于化妆品、保健品领域的结果，从与 $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ 入手下功夫开拓药品瓦解病毒，解救人类面临的新冠肺炎病毒泛滥成灾困境。

At this point, it is necessary to review the history of the discovery of the C_{60} fullerene exploration. Professor Richard Smalley discovered Fullerene C_{60} and later C_{70} , C_{72} , C_{78} and C_{90} , among others, in an experiment on August 2, 1984, at about 11:00 p.m. He made several trips to Switzerland to use the facility at CERN to verify this major breakthrough in nanotechnology in modern history. For this discovery, Richard Smalley and two other scientists were awarded the Nobel Prize

in 1996. Professor Smalley died in 2005 at the age of 62. However, before his death, he left the responsibility of finding new uses for fullerene-based nanomaterials to another scientist, but did not pay attention to the medicinal prospects of fullerene-based C60, a research direction that is precisely the new coronavirus in 2020, forcing human to progress their research in this regard, and our team therefore take the past research results that were confined to cosmetics and health care products, and started with C60(OH)24 to develop drugs to dismantle the virus and save humanity from the plight of new coronavirus pandemic.

我们并不是孤军奋战，全世界的高科技团队都在夜以继日不分昼夜的研发，盼望着找到一种特效药灭杀病毒，恢复正常生活。自从 2005 年以来，全球富勒烯专家数以千计，已经制作并发布了数千份其他领域的与 C60 富勒烯研究报告和实验作品。然而，没有研究团队能够在其工艺中不使用有毒溶剂的情况下，生产水溶性富勒醇，从而使得 C60 的羟基化衍生物难以醇化。在 2018 年 2 月初，人类历史上第一次让我们团队发明了富勒烯的无毒水溶性合成物，这是造物主上帝保佑人类，一年后的 2020 年二月份我们全力以赴向着抗病毒的方向研究医药类型的 C60(OH)24 产品。我们团队不仅在不使用有毒溶剂的情况下，成功制造了 C60(OH)x，还优化了生产 C60(OH)x 的生物学有效形式的方法，其纯度可被安全食用，完全无毒了，能够进入药品生产领域，为全人类战胜病毒多做贡献。

We're not alone in this. High-tech teams around the world are working around the clock to find a drug to kill the virus and restore normalcy. Since 2005, thousands of fullerene experts around the world have produced and published thousands of research reports and experimental works in other fields related to C60 fullerene. However, no research team has been able to produce water-soluble fullerenol without the use of toxic solvents in its process, making it difficult to alcoholize the hydroxylated derivatives of C60. In early February 2018, for the

first time in human history, we teamed up to invent a non-toxic water-soluble synthesis of fullerenes, which is a bless from heaven to humankind. One year later, in February 2020, we were fully engaged in the research of pharmaceutical type $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ products in the direction of anti-virus. Our team not only succeeded in manufacturing $C_{60}(OH)_x$ without using toxic solvents, but also optimized the method to produce a biologically effective form of $C_{60}(OH)_x$, the purity of which can be safely consumed and is completely non-toxic, so that it can enter the field of pharmaceutical production and contribute more to the victory of all mankind over viruses .

*五、富勒烯瓦解病毒以后的人体排泄物需要厕所革命升级换代确保下水道体系不再是排污管道
Human excrement after fullerenes disintegrate virus needs toilet revolution
upgrade to ensure sewer system is no longer a sewage pipe*

病毒祸害人类的根本问题，是人类生存与环境友好的问题，追根溯源就是有些人反思的“哲学批判”：人类已经是地球生态环境的破坏者，例如城市化的厕所粪便污水垃圾进入下水道，每时每刻的污秽在污染水资源，中国长江三角洲的地下水都发现了普遍性存在抗生素，自来水 90%以上都是抗生素含量超标，人类自己的人与人之间互相坑害，甚至于谋杀儿童的毒奶粉叫做中国特色屡教不改。在造物主的眼睛里，人类就是一种“病毒”，而大自然产生有机物以后最早的“临界点准生物”就是病毒——首先拥有遗传基因的组织化主体，不像其他的“分子”或者说无机物根本就没有“基因”。造物主“上帝”面对人类社会的破坏性，不得不让“病毒”站出来惩罚人类，灭杀一些人口，警示人类社会自律自爱自重。

The root cause of the scourge of viruses is the imbalance between human survival and environmental friendliness, which is the "philosophical criticism" that some people have reflected on: human beings are already the destroyers of the earth's ecological environment, for example, urbanized toilets feces, sewage and garbage into the sewers, polluting our water resources; the groundwater of the

Yangtze River Delta in China is found to have a widespread presence of antibiotics, more than 90% of the tap water is overloaded with antibiotics, human beings themselves are pitted against each other, and even the tainted milk powder that has been murdering our children is called Chinese characteristics. In the eyes of the Creator, human being is a "virus", and the earliest "tipping point quasi-organisms" after nature produced organic matter are viruses - first organized subjects with genes, unlike other "molecules" or inorganics that have no "genes" at all. Faced with the destructive nature of human society, the Creator had to allow the "virus" to come forward to punish humanity, to exterminate some populations and to warn human society of its self-discipline, love and respect.

这样的“环境系统工程”要求人类从自己身上找原因，例如艾滋病就是对于人类性生活混乱状态的一种遏制，人类的道德底线、法律惩罚一直都没有解决“男女关系混乱、同性恋、吸毒传染病菌病毒”之类的社会环境问题。即便是站在人类完全彻底“敌视”病毒的立场上，解决人类历史上一次又一次病毒泛滥成灾的根本出路，也只能是标本兼治，不可以就像现在 2020 年前半年新型冠状病毒传染的大流行“疫情”紧急状态下，只能是“头疼医头、脚疼医脚、自顾不暇”的狼狈不堪做法。而是要立足于当前，放眼整个地球生态圈的病毒、细菌微生物“全局”，长远打算人类社会对于地球“生态圈”的危险性如何应对？实现人类文明与病毒细菌生态圈子的相得益彰、和平共处，拥有人类社会与大自然环境之间的和谐。

Such "environmental systems engineering" requires human beings to find the causes in themselves, for example, AIDS is a curb on the sexual disorder of human beings, the human ethical bottom line. Legal penalties have not addressed socio-environmental problems such as "gender disorder, homosexuality, drug-borne germ viruses". Even from the standpoint of mankind's complete and total "hostility" to the virus, the fundamental way out to solve the virus pandemic one after another in the history of mankind, can only be to treat both the symptoms and the root

causes, not like the current pandemic of the novel coronavirus in the first half of 2020 under the state of emergency, where we treat head for headache, feet for foot pain, running around like a headless chicken. Rather, how can human society respond to the dangers of the Earth's "ecosphere" in the long term, based on the present and looking at the "whole picture" of viruses, bacteria and microorganisms in the entire Earth's ecosystem? The realization of complementary and peaceful coexistence between human civilization and the viral and bacterial ecosphere, with harmony between human society and the natural environment, is now essential.

在这样的意义上，新冠肺炎的病毒疫情 2020 年肆虐全人类，同时还有埃博拉病毒在非洲又一次冒出来，其他地方的鼠疫也发生了，迫使我们人类的视点不要仅仅盯着眼前的新冠肺炎病毒，还应该把危害人类健康的其它那些病毒、细菌，都要一并纳入防治研究。要有一个清晰的战略性思维，跳出一对一搏击病毒的疫苗思路，切记不可以在战术层面陷入泥潭。况且，从新冠肺炎死者遗体病理学解剖结果来看，新冠肺炎病毒致死的人群中，被其带发的其它疾患居然是最容易致命了。这就是体弱多病的人，被新冠病毒激起了“并发症”恶化的死亡之舞，警告我们人类不能处于按下葫芦漂起瓢的进退维谷境地，务必清醒地认识到人类自己发明创造的科学技术已经别无选择的必须有预见性地研发“特效药”，前瞻性地做好疾病控制工作，把优化人体免疫系统作为人类健康事业的重中之重，把洁身自好与环境保护作为治标也治本的精准定位，去下功夫探索发现生态平衡的大千世界，做大做强人类文明与造物主之间的适应性格局。

In this sense, the new coronavirus epidemic that has ravaged humanity in 2020, along with the emergence of the Ebola virus in Africa and the plague elsewhere, compel us to look beyond the new coronavirus and include other viruses and bacteria that are harmful to human health in our research. It's time to have a clear strategic mindset, think outside of the one-on-one vaccine mindset when fighting a virus, and remember not to get bogged down at the tactical level. In addition, the autopsy findings of coronavirus cadavers show that the other diseases

caused by novel coronavirus are the most likely to be the cause of fatality. We must realize that the science and technology invented by mankind has no choice but to develop "special drugs" with foresight, to do a good job of disease control, to optimize the human immune system as the most important task of human health, to treat self-cleansing and environmental protection as the precise positioning to cure the symptoms as well as the root cause, to explore the world of ecological balance and to strengthen the adaptive pattern between human civilization and the Creator.

这方面也是要看清楚地球一直都处于被病毒覆盖的状态，细菌和病毒与人类生命体是相辅相成当中也发生互害行为，彼此你中有我、我中有你、谁也离不开谁。人类社会及其科学技术不应该抱着“消灭细菌病毒”的一锅煮、一棍子打死那种态度，需要分清楚利弊边境线，牢牢记住地球是病毒细菌和人类共同生活在一起的“生态链”，地球的生态环境也是裸着的星球。深层次的地球运动和物质结构，和地球与日月星辰的互相影响，还是待解之谜。例如，对于病毒细菌，我们人类仅仅是看到了生物腐烂消失，我们有器官的感知。可是对于基因、病毒和细菌微生物等等缺乏直观能力，也缺乏安全感。更重要的是，人类对于物理化学规律性与生命机制的关联度知之甚少，面对 2019 年后半年发生的新型冠状病毒感染“泛滥成全球化灾难”的疫情，一下子手忙脚乱，明摆着的就是人类社会医疗科技进步跟不上疫情大爆发的病毒变化，疫情倒逼着我们人类反思自省现代医学，扪心自问创新医疗科技的路线图是否需要另辟蹊径？

It is also important to see that the Earth has always been covered with viruses, that bacteria and viruses and human life forms are mutually reinforcing and mutually harmful, and that we are in fact inseparable. Human society and its science and technology should not adopt the attitude of "eradicating bacterias and viruses"; they should clearly distinguish between the advantages and disadvantages, and bear in mind that the Earth is an "ecological chain" in which viruses, bacteria and humans coexist together, and that Earth's ecological environment is also a

bare planet. The deep-seated earth movement and material structure, and the interplay between the earth and the sun, moon and stars, remain a mystery. For example, with viral bacteria, we humans simply see the organisms decay and disappear, and we have organoleptic senses. But there is a lack of intuition and insecurity about genes, viruses, bacterial microbes and etc. More importantly, human beings know little about the correlation between physical and chemical regularity and the mechanism of life, and therefore in the face of the Novel coronavirus infection in the second half of 2019 "exploded into a global disaster", all of a sudden the medical science and technology progress of human society fail to keep up with the outbreak of the viral mutations. The epidemic forced us humans to reflect on modern medicine, asking ourselves whether the roadmap for innovative medical science and technology needs to find another way?

这当中的疫苗研发速度，常常赶不上病毒的变异速度，更不必提说很多病毒导致的疾病，都超出了现代医学的治疗能力。更可怕的是，病毒对人类宿主的适应能力是现在人类细思极恐、匪夷所思的，譬如新冠病毒能够高频率地发生基因突变，甚至能与另一种病毒进行基因重组。试想一下，若是一种高致命性的病毒，和另外一种高传染性的病毒，在某个人类宿主体内相遇了，意外地产生了兼具二者特点的能广泛传播又致命的病毒。当这种病毒伴随着这个人作为宿主，搭乘全球化的飞机、高铁之类“快速代步工具”穿梭于全球的飞机场、火车站之中，这会不会成为人类最可怕的梦魇呢？传染病大流行，就是这样的人类社会高效、快捷交通工具形成人口流动性和人们密切接触的生活工作方式，酝酿形成的。

The pace of vaccine development has often failed to keep pace with the mutation of viruses, not to mention the fact that many diseases caused by viruses are beyond the treatment capabilities of modern medicine. What is even more frightening is the virus' ability to adapt to a human host in ways that are now beyond human thought and wonder, such as the ability of the new coronavirus to

mutate with high frequency and even genetically recombine with another virus. Imagine that one highly lethal virus and another highly infectious virus meet in a human host and accidentally produce a virus that is both widely spread and lethal. Will this virus become the worst nightmare of mankind when it accompanies this person as a host and travels through airports and train stations around the world on globalized airplanes and high-speed railways and other "rapid transit vehicles"? Infectious disease pandemics are the result of the efficient and rapid transportation of human society, which shapes the mobility of populations and the way of life and work in close contact with people.

病毒，从来没有形状上高大威猛的让人类恐惧，不像恐龙等等外在的形象，而是让人类看不见摸不着的进入人类身体，同时分布在人居环境的衣食住行物体上，存在于人类呼吸的空气中和水环境里面，让人类防不胜防。这就是孙悟空钻进铁扇公主肚子里的战略战术，病毒钻进人类孔武有力的身体，让人类无可奈何花落去。表面上看，病毒根本就不是“强势”的存在，经常性的会对人体造成三种影响：1 无法适应人体的温度或环境而亡，2 被人体的免疫系统干掉，3 通过变异而躲过人体免疫系统：有些病毒会悄悄的躲着，伺机而动；有些则会攻击人体细胞组织，导致感染，引发疾病甚至危及生命。病毒感染，会对人体造成什么样的影响呢？主要是与病毒攻击力的强弱，还有人体自身免疫力的强弱，有直截了当的破坏性因果关系。

Viruses, unlike dinosaurs and other creatures with intimidating appearances, can't be seen or touched by humans, while being distributed in the human environment, in the air we breathe and in the water we drink. Like how Sun Wukong's strategic tactic of infiltrating Princess Iron Fan's belly, viruses penetrate into the powerful body of mankind, leaving mankind helpless. On the surface, the virus is not a "intimidating" existence at all. They often causes three kinds of effects on the human body: 1, Unable to adapt to the body's temperature or environment and die; 2, killed by the body's immune system; and 3 escape the body's immune

system through mutations. Some viruses will quietly hide, waiting for an opportunity to make a move; some will attack human cells and tissues, resulting in infection, disease and even endangers life. What are the effects of a viral infection on the human body? There is a straightforward destructive cause-and-effect relationship, primarily with the strength of the virus' attack, but also with the strength of the body's own immune system.

当然，有些病毒，本身就是无孔不入，典型案例就是二十世纪开始的艾滋病毒、埃博拉病毒、新型冠状病毒等传染性疾病，无论是人体免疫系统多么的强大，都不是这种病毒的对手。再加上二十一世纪的流行病、传染病双管齐下状态，尤其是面对着 2003 年的 SARS 病毒感染造成了非典型性肺炎疫情，就引起了临床医学、流行病学调查的学者们高度警觉，发现了人类近亲的先天不足。例如艾滋病直截了当的来自于“猴免疫缺陷病毒”，这种病毒存在于许多非洲猴子的身上，每种猴子身上都有这种病毒的一个特殊变异体。多种多样的这些病毒发生了杂交病毒以后，在黑猩猩的群落里蔓延，直到有一天，它传播到了人身上，成为了危害人类的病毒名单上最可怕的名字之一“人类免疫缺陷病毒”。这种人类免疫缺陷病毒，摧毁人类的免疫系统，使得患者对一切病原微生物都失去了抵抗能力，由它引起的获得性免疫缺陷综合征，即艾滋病，现在几乎已经遍及全球的每一个大陆。

There are, of course, some viruses that are themselves pervasive, the classic case being infectious diseases such as HIV, Ebola, and the new coronavirus at the beginning of the twentieth century, and no matter how powerful the human immune system is, they are no match for such viruses. This, coupled with the two-pronged epidemic and infectious disease situation in the 21st century, especially in the face of the SARS epidemic caused by the SARS virus infection in 2003, has aroused great vigilance among scholars of clinical medicine and epidemiological investigation, and has revealed the inborn deficiency of human relatives. AIDS, for example, comes directly from the "monkey immunodeficiency virus", which is

present in many African monkeys, each with a specific variant of the virus. A variety of these viruses hybridized and spread through the chimpanzee population until one day it spread to humans and became one of the most feared names on the list of viruses that harm humans, the human immunodeficiency virus. This human immunodeficiency virus, which destroys the human immune system and leaves patients defenseless against all pathogenic microorganisms, causes the acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, or AIDS, which is now present on almost every continent in the world.

2019 年全球艾滋病毒感染者就事实上超过了一亿人口，尽管制药公司一直在研发改进控制艾滋病的抗病毒药物，尽管医生、流行病学家、病毒学家、社会学家等越来越多的人加入了针对艾滋病的斗争行列，尽管各国都在积极地采取措施切断艾滋病的传播途径，艾滋病依旧在全世界四处传播。美国哈佛艾滋病研究所国际艾滋病中心主任乔纳森·M·曼 (Jonathan M. Mann) 在为《逼近的瘟疫》(The Coming Plague) 一书写序言时提出，艾滋病正在给我们上课，这一课的内容就是：世界上任何地方的健康问题，都会迅速成为对许多人或对所有人的健康威胁。有必要建立一个世界性的“早期警报系统”，以便尽快发现新疾病的暴发，或旧疾病的异乎寻常的传播。没有这样一个真正能在全世界工作的系统，我们就真的是无遮无拦，只能靠命运来保护自己了。

In 2019, the number of people worldwide living with HIV will in fact exceed 100 million, despite the fact that pharmaceutical companies have been developing antiviral drugs to improve AIDS control, despite the fact that more and more doctors, epidemiologists, virologists, sociologists and other people are joining the fight against AIDS, and despite the fact that countries are actively taking steps to cut off the transmission of AIDS, the disease continues to spread around the world. Jonathan M. Mann, Director of the International AIDS Center at the Harvard AIDS Institute in the United States, in his preface to The Coming Plague, suggested

that AIDS is teaching us a lesson that health problems anywhere in the world can quickly become a life threat to many or to all. There is a need for a worldwide "early warning system" to detect outbreaks of new diseases, or the unusual spread of old ones, as soon as possible. Without such a system that truly works globally, we are truly invulnerable to fate and can only protect ourselves.

这种全球化信息及时性共享的“疾病控制各国一体化”工作机制，在 2020 年上半年的世界各国“抗疫”过程中一地鸡毛，令人失望。在防疫、治病、救人等等各个环节，每个人应对“病毒感染大流行疫情”这种突发公共卫生事件，还是要以主权国家为坐标系。所谓的疾病控制以政府为中心那种国家体制，让人类没有因此而幸运的躲过“病毒感染疫情”的劫难，这就需要人们反思最近几十年建立的流行病、传染病“早期警报系统”是否先天不足？人民当家做主的舆论监督、疫情信息公开活动，为什么一直都没有纠正官府官员错误的权力，只能是让人民成为了官僚主义的小跟班——仆从，让各级官员当家做主。这就是官本位体制的疾病控制中心那种工作机制，在 2019 年底新型冠状病毒感染大流行疫情当中，一次又一次把中国陷入了被动局面的核心问题，也是美国政府 2020 年面对中国的“抗疫”警钟长鸣而无动于衷。几乎所有的欧美发达国家疾控中心都没有在中国预警疫情的时候，明确要求自己国家的人民戴口罩，这些不愿意戴口罩，不愿意人与人之间保持距离的欧美发达国家人口，以自己的傲慢与偏见看待中国发生的一切，甚至于因为华人华侨戴口罩而在欧美发达国家受到了不应该的歧视。后来，欧美发达国家支付的代价沉重，应该记取这种教训，反躬自省错误的观念。其中，卫生间和下水道体系的化粪池，成为新型冠状病毒的存活与传染工具，才是污染水资源也污染空气的关键环节。

It is disappointing that this globalized mechanism of sharing information in a timely manner and "integrating all countries for disease control" has been a complete failure in the process of "fighting the epidemic" in countries around the world in the first half of 2020. In all aspects of epidemic prevention, treatment and rescue, everyone has to follow the coordinate system of the sovereign State in responding to public health emergencies such as "virus-infected pandemic". The so-

called government-centred national system of disease control, in which humanity has not been fortunate enough to escape a "viral epidemic", requires reflection on whether the "early warning system" of epidemics and infectious diseases established in recent decades is inherently inadequate. Why has the power to correct the wrongs of government officials been left unchecked by the public opinion monitoring and epidemic information activities of the people as the masters, only the people have become the bureaucratic henchmen - the servants, and the officials at all levels as the masters. This is the kind of CDC working mechanism of the official system, in the end of 2019 Novel coronavirus infection pandemic, time and again put China into a passive situation at the heart of the problem, and also the U.S. government in 2020 remained indifferent in the face of China's "anti-epidemic" alarm bell long sounded. Almost all the CDCs of developed countries in Europe and America did not explicitly require their own people to wear masks when China warned of the epidemic. These developed populations in Europe and America, who are unwilling to wear masks and keep social distances, view what is happening in China with their own arrogance and prejudice, and even overseas Chinese suffer undeserved discrimination in developed countries in Europe and America for wearing masks. Later, the developed countries in Europe and the United States paid a heavy toll and should learn this lesson and reflect on their misconceptions. Among them, the septic tank of the toilet and sewerage system has become the survival and transmission tool of the new coronavirus, which is the key link in water and air pollution.

例如 2018 年中国工程院等联合发布《全球工程前沿》报告，在医药卫生领域研判的 Top9 工程研究前沿中，“新发高致病病毒的发现及其疫情的预警与防控”赫然在列。报告指出，这当中的关键科学问题包括：对相关病毒的鉴定、传播途径和致病性的评估、流行状况的监测预警以及

相关疫苗和药物等防治策略的研发等。这个并不复杂的形容背后，是一个复杂的科学防控链条：从病毒的基础研究、药物和疫苗研发、相关学科建设，到传染病来袭前的预防、预测，再到传染病来袭后的监测预警和公共卫生应急反应系统，以及为所有环节提供技术支撑的科技手段。如果将病毒比做一个潜藏着的随时可能放火的元凶，堵住这场大火，需要做精细且庞杂的工作。

For example, in 2018, the Chinese Academy of Engineering and others jointly released the report "Global Engineering Frontiers", among the Top 9 engineering research frontiers in the field of medicine and health, "the discovery of new highly pathogenic viruses and the early warning and prevention and control of epidemics" is listed prominently. The report notes that key scientific issues include the identification of viruses, assessment of transmission pathways and pathogenicity, monitoring and early warning of epidemics, and development of control strategies such as vaccines and drugs. Behind this uncomplicated description is a complex chain of scientific prevention and control: from basic research on viruses, drug and vaccine development, and the construction of related disciplines, to the prevention and prediction of infectious diseases before their onset, to surveillance, early warning and public health emergency response systems after their onset, as well as the scientific and technological tools that provide technical support for all links. If one compares a virus to a lurking, ready-to-fire culprit, plugging the fire requires a delicate and complex job.

偏偏是这个报告里面，没有注意到病毒在人类及其宠物猫狗家禽家畜以及野味动物的排泄物里面存活，也就是厕所（洗手间）、化粪池、下水道体系成为最危险的病毒存活场所，能够污染水资源，让人类的患病率伴随着 2020 年新型冠状病毒的传染病大流行，是最大的社区传播平台，与空气传播相辅相成。这一点，在全世界第一线的科研成果当中，对于新冠病毒早期的预警，科学家们主要的是从下水道寻找线索。据《华尔街日报》报道 2020 年 5 月 2 日澳大利亚布里斯班的研究人员正在从污水中检测新冠病毒，现在，随着越来越多的国家希望尽早结束封锁状态

，科学家们希望通过观察下水道污水的变化来强化对新冠病毒的监控能力。跟新冠病毒临床检测方式不同之处在于，无论是 CT 检查还是鼻咽拭子取样，现有临床检测都只能了解单一个体是否感染。而通过下水道的污水样本，科学家们可能只需要一次试验就能掌握几十万人的感染情况。

The report, however, fails to note that the virus survives in the excreta of humans, their pets dogs and cats, domestic animals and game animals, which makes toilets (toilets), septic tanks and sewerage systems the most dangerous virus breeding ground, contaminating water resources and allowing human prevalence to accompany the 2020 epidemic of the new coronavirus, and is therefore the largest platform for community transmission, complementing airborne transmission. This, among the world's first line of research, for the early warning of the novel coronavirus, scientists are mainly looking for clues from the sewers. May 2, 2020, researchers in Brisbane, Australia, are detecting new coronavirus from sewage, and now, as more countries look to end the embargo as soon as possible, scientists hope to strengthen their surveillance of the new coronavirus by watching changes in sewer effluent, The Wall Street Journal reports. Unlike clinical testing for new coronavirus, existing clinical tests, such as CT and nasopharyngeal swab sampling, can only tell if a single individual is infected. And with sewerage samples, scientists may be able to get a handle on hundreds of thousands of people infected in just one trial.

中国的钟南山院士团队、武汉大学附属医院科研团队、广州市公立医院团队都在 2020 年 2 月份以来，与其他国家的流行病学调查报告共同证明，排泄物中新冠病毒数量“非常可观”，人类对于 COVID-19 或者的追踪已经发现病患者排泄物是随后比较大的传染源。长期以来，各国科学家一直在使用一种叫“废水流行病学”的技术，来追踪如吸毒或化学品泄漏等一些社会公害，以协助指导决策。2013 年以色列爆发的小儿麻痹症就是通过对下水道污水的监控而发现的。

The academician team led by Zhong Nanshan in China, the Wuhan University Hospital team, and the Guangzhou Public Hospital team, along with epidemiological studies from other countries since February 2020, have demonstrated that the amount of the new coronavirus in feces is "very significant" and that human tracking of COVID-19 has identified patient feces as a subsequent source of significant infection. A technique called "wastewater epidemiology" has long been used by scientists to track social hazards, such as drug use or chemical spills, to help guide decision-making, and the 2013 polio outbreak in Israel was discovered through the monitoring of sewerage effluent.

为了构建新冠病毒的早期预警系统，美国麻省理工大学教授埃里克·阿尔姆率领的研究团队每天都在处理、分析马萨诸塞州下水道里面的污水。这些污水来自该州所有的未经处理的家庭污水。如果该团队成功的话，他们很快就能发现新冠病毒遗传基因的一些特征。埃里克·阿尔姆教授是麻省理工大学微生物信息学与治疗学中心的联合主任，他在接受采访时介绍说：“要在下水道的污水中检查流感是相当困难的一件事，但幸运的是，跟流感相比，人们排泄物中的新冠病毒具有非常可观的数量，足以确保试验的顺利开展。”

To build an early warning system for the new coronavirus, a team of researchers led by MIT professor Eric Alm has been treating, analyzing, and working daily on sewage inside Massachusetts' sewers. This sewage comes from all untreated domestic sewage in the state. If the team is successful, they will soon be able to discover some of the features of the novel coronavirus genes. Professor Eric Alm, who is co-director of the Center for Microbial Informatics and Therapeutics at the University of Massachusetts Institute of Technology, described in an interview, "It's quite a difficult thing to check for influenza in sewer effluent, but fortunately, compared to influenza, the neocoronavirus in people's excrement has a very significant amount of it, enough to ensure that the trial goes well."

在此之前，有研究显示，在中国武汉、深圳的确诊患者以及在美国首例病例的粪便中都检测到了新型冠状病毒，这个现象说明了病毒可以在消化道复制并且存在。2020年4月，研究人员在巴西东部贝洛奥里藏特市收集下水道污水样本以检测新冠病毒。还有，美国马萨诸塞州的第一批新冠病毒感染者被确诊的时候，埃里克·阿尔姆教授率领的团队，在该州的下水道污水里发现了微量的新冠病毒。在荷兰，同样试验也在进行当中，2020年2月8日该国研究团队在下水道污水中尚未发现新冠病毒。但在该国首例感染者被确诊1周之后的3月15日，研究团队在污水中检测出了新冠病毒。此外，法国和澳大利亚也有同样的研究结果公布。

In April 2020, researchers collected sewerage effluent samples to test for the new coronavirus in Belo Horizonte, eastern Brazil. What's more, when the first neocoronavirus infections were diagnosed in Massachusetts in the US, a team led by Professor Eric Alm found traces of neocoronavirus in sewer effluent in the state. In the Netherlands, where the same trial is underway, on February 8, 2020, a team of researchers has yet to find the neocoronavirus in sewer effluent. But on March 15, one week after the country's first infected person was diagnosed, the research team detected the neocoronavirus in the sewage. In addition, the same study results were published in France and Australia.

美国加州大学伯克利分校土木环境学教授卡拉·纳尔逊在接受采访时表示：“如果能尽早及时发现病毒感染的死灰复燃，就会给疫情防控创造最佳的时机。”纳尔逊专门研究通过水管传播的病原体，他的团队发现人类粪便预警病毒的时间要比临床检测发现病人病灶更早，尤其是能更好的监控无症状感染者。

Carla Nelson, a professor of civil and environmental sciences at the University of California, Berkeley, said in an interview, "If the resurgence of viral infections can be detected early and in time, it creates the best possible time for epidemic prevention and control." Nelson specializes in pathogens transmitted through water pipes, and his team found that the detection time for early warning of virus in

human feces can be earlier than clinical tests can detect a patient's lesions, especially for better monitoring of asymptomatic infected individuals.

在各国寻求尽早结束“封锁”之际，对于公共卫生机构而言，疫情防控的一大盲点是那些无症状感染或尚未出现症状的感染者。澳大利亚联邦科学与工业研究组织（CSIRO）土地与水科学主任保罗·贝尔奇博士帮助该国政府进行了一项研究，分析了约 6 万人的集水区污水。他在接受采访时指出：“新冠病毒通常在人感染之后的 3 天左右，就会出现在排泄物中。这比一个感染者通常需要 5 天甚至更长时间才会出现症状要短得多。”纳尔逊教授认为，废水检测的实施成本可能只是临床检测和政府正在考虑的一些其他措施（如接触追踪）的一小部分。然而，要扩大污水监测项目的规模并不是件容易的事。他就美国的情况表示：“需要从公共部门调动不同的资源才能发挥更大作用。我们的污水处理厂绝大多数都是由公共机构管理的。”

As countries around the world seek an early end to the "embargo", a major blind spot for public health institutions in the prevention and control of the epidemic is those infected with asymptomatic infections or those who have not yet developed symptoms. Dr. Paul Belch, Director of Land and Water Science at CSIRO Australia, helped the government to conduct a study that analyzed catchment wastewater for about 60,000 people. He noted in an interview, "The new coronavirus usually appears in the excrement about three days after a person is infected. This is much shorter than the five days or more it usually takes for an infected person to show symptoms." Professor Nelson argues that the cost of implementing wastewater testing may be a fraction of the cost of clinical testing and some of the other measures the government is considering, such as contact tracking. However, it's not easy to scale up wastewater monitoring programs. In the case of the United States, he said, "Different resources need to be mobilized from the public sector to be more effective. The vast majority of our sewage treatment plants are managed by public agencies."

埃里克·阿尔姆教授表示，他的研究小组现在可以处理 150 个城市的污水处理厂的信息，可以覆盖美国约 1% 的人口。他希望在一个月内可以扩大到 1000 个城市。在澳大利亚，保罗·贝尔奇博士说，一个选择是利用澳大利亚刑事情报委员会的专业知识来制定一个国家计划。该委员会去年将 58 个处理厂的废水作为衡量药物使用的工具。

Professor Eric Alm said his research team can now process information on sewage treatment plants in 150 cities, which can reach about 1 percent of the US population. He hopes to expand to 1,000 cities within a month. In Australia, Dr. Paul Belch said one option was to use the expertise of the Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission to develop a national plan. The commission last year used wastewater from 58 treatment plants as a tool to measure drug use.

另外，科学家们遇到的另一大难题是还不能确定每个感染者在排泄的过程中究竟会释放出大量的新冠病毒。也正因为此，这种试验具有高度不确定性。早期研究的数据范围很广，常常与临床诊断结果相差很远。

Another major difficulty scientists have encountered is the uncertainty of exactly how much of the new coronavirus is released by each infected person in the process of excretion. It is also for this reason that such tests are highly uncertain. The data from early studies is extensive and often falls far short of clinical diagnostic results.

不过，科学家相信，更多的数据将产生更准确的结果，并有助于建立一个公式以便决策者可以决定终止或延长隔离。围绕着新冠病毒的传染病疫情后续监控，世界各国的疾病控制中心应该注重于在人类粪便污水垃圾的取样，或者说下水道取样，可以与医院的临床医学“检测人体是否有携带病毒”的试验结果，一起来审查。

However, scientists believe that more data will produce more accurate results and help create a formula so that decision makers can decide to end or extend segregation. Around the follow-up of infectious disease outbreaks of new

coronavirus, CDCs around the world should focus on sampling human fecal sewage waste, or sewer sampling, which can be reviewed in conjunction with the results of clinical "human viral testing" in hospitals.

讨论到这里就需要明确，不仅仅是预警病毒感染的地域分布，更重要的是不应该让病毒在下水道持续性存活。因为这是污染水资源，也进一步扩大传染范围的更加危险“隐患”，等于让下水道成为病毒流动着传染人类的工具。

By this point in the discussion, it needs to be clear that it is not only the geographical distribution of early warning viral infections, but more importantly that the virus should not be allowed to persist in the sewers. Because this is a more dangerous "hazard" that pollutes water resources and further expands the scope of infection, it is tantamount to making sewers a vehicle for the flow of viruses to infect humans.

人类社会的厕所在二十世纪以抽水马桶的发明创造，让病毒拥有了从坐便器到给排水系统的人居下水道，再进入建筑物的化粪池之类更大生存空间，长期性的存活在化粪池，并且流入城乡公共下水道。即便是中国农村的“旱厕”即“非抽水马桶”，也是让粪便污水垃圾直截了当的渗透到土壤里面，污染水资源，包括给予病毒生存的更大场所，潜伏下来随时随地危害人类。2020年新型冠状病毒的“”传染病全球化泛滥成灾，给我们人类改善环境的工作敲响了警钟，倒逼着人类社会必须高度重视人居环境，特别是城市化运动的厕所化粪池到公共下水道体系污秽不堪，污染水资源也在垃圾填埋场、垃圾站垃圾车绕城旅游的二次以上“污染空气”的流动性破坏生态环境。生活垃圾与人类粪便污水共同在住房下水道体系实施无害化处理，不允许粪便污水、生活垃圾在城市“车载流动性污染环境”的恶习不改继续下去，才是真正的防止“病毒细菌侵害人类健康”第一要务。

The toilets of human society were created in the twentieth century with the invention of the flush toilet, which allowed viruses to have a greater living space from the toilet to the human sewer that feeds the drainage system, to the septic

tank of the building, where they survive permanently, and to the public sewers in both cities and towns. Even the "dry toilets" or "non-flush toilets" in rural China are allowing feces, sewage and garbage to seep directly into the soil, polluting water sources, including giving the virus a larger place to live while lurking down at any time and place to harm humanity. The "globalized pandemic" caused by the spread of new coronavirus in 2020 sounded an alarm for us humans to work to improve the environment, forcing our society to pay great attention to the human habitat environment, in particular the urbanization movement's toilet septic tanks and public sewerage systems are filthy, polluting water sources and causing multiple damages in terms of air pollution to the ecological environment through landfills, refuse collection stations and garbage trucks that circle the cities.

在人居环境当中，如何解决好粪便污水垃圾处理的无害化问题，至关重要。我们广顺科研团队的再生塑料沼气池-化粪池，第一步是把“废旧塑料”变废为宝（全世界最大的顽固性污染就是塑料污染，一百年都难以降解，废旧塑料污染海洋和陆地人居环境），利用废旧塑料制造成为“再生塑料沼气池-化粪池”，去把粪便污水、生活垃圾变废为宝，首先生成绿色新能源沼气，和无害化的沼液、沼渣有机肥，增收节支，美化环境，杀毒灭菌，功德无量。

In the context of human settlements, it is important to address the issue of the manure, sewage and waste disposal treatment. The first step is to turn "waste plastic" into treasure (the biggest intractable pollution in the world is plastic pollution, which is difficult to degrade even after a hundred years, and waste plastic pollutes the marine and terrestrial environment), using waste plastic to make "recycled plastic biogas tank - septic tank", to turn manure, sewage and domestic garbage into treasure. The plan is to, first of all, to generate green new energy biogas, and harmless biogas, methane and organic fertilizer, increase

income and save money, beautify the environment, sterilize and kill viruses and bacteria.

工业化生产力在发展人类社会文明的同时，产生了更多的环境污染问题。人类社会的穷奢极欲破坏了大自然的生态环境，使得老天爷不得不以生存危机感给予人们警钟长鸣。这种情况下，表面上十恶不赦的病毒，其实就是大自然对于人类破坏性的当头棒喝，被哲学家说成为：人类是自然界的最大病毒，而病毒则是大自然的免疫力。老天爷看到了人类恣意妄为太过分啦，就要以大地震、大洪水、台风海啸，还有病毒细菌形成的传染病，去警告、处分人类的嚣张气焰。

Industrialized productivity has created alarming environmental pollution problems while developing human social civilization. The extravagant desires of human society have destroyed the ecological environment of nature, so that God has to warn people with a sense of existential crisis. In this case, the ostensibly heinous virus is in fact nature's destructive booster to mankind. Philosophers once claimed that man is nature's greatest virus, and the virus is nature's immunity. The Lord saw that mankind had gone too far, and warned and punished mankind's arrogance with earthquakes, floods, typhoons, tsunamis, and infectious diseases caused by viruses and bacteria.

流行病学调查已经证实，COVID-19 或者新型冠状病毒感染疫情来自于生活污染类型的传染病，肯定不是工厂污染造成的工业污染，现在已经发现了相应的病人粪便里面有活病毒，具有传染疾病的危险。杀毒防疫是重中之重的全世界不同国家地区一致性工作，需要充分发挥广顺科技模式的再生塑料沼气池—化粪池一体化设备的积极作用，这是杀灭新型冠状病毒 COVID-19 或者，保障水资源不会受到污染，尽快恢复生产，为民造福的关键举措。

Epidemiological investigations have confirmed that the epidemic of COVID-19 or novel coronavirus infections is a communicable disease from household contamination, and is certainly not industrial contamination caused by factory pollution. The corresponding patients have now been found to have live viruses in

their faeces that pose a risk of infectious disease. It is necessary to fully utilize the positive role of Guangshun Technology's regenerative plastic biogas digester-septic tank integration equipment, which is a key initiative to kill the new coronavirus COVID-19, or to ensure that water resources will not be polluted, so that production can resume as soon as possible for the benefit of the people.

2020年2月份到5月份的一百多天调查研究证明，钟南山团队在病人粪便检测到了活病毒，这是具有传染疾病能力的祸根子，但是南方农村把粪便放进鱼塘的现象很普遍。更重要的是，城市下水道体系就没有杀毒能力，钢筋水泥结构的给排水体系、下水道系统一直都在每时每刻的渗漏污水，长期性的污染水资源。这样一来，城市化的隐蔽工程不过关，造成了我们全人类所有的大中城市自来水的源头被污染非常普遍，国家水资源监测报告上只有1%的城市自来水可以被家庭饮水机再次过滤，成为直饮水。

More than 100 days of research from February to May 2020 proved that Zhong Nanshan's team detected live viruses in the patient's feces, the bane of a disease with infectious power, but the practice of putting feces in fish ponds is common in China's rural south. More importantly, the urban sewer system does not have the ability to kill bacteria and viruses, the reinforced concrete structure of the water supply and drainage system and the sewer system have been leaking sewage non-stop, causing long-term pollution of water resources. As a result, the sanitary engineering of urbanization has failed, resulting in a widespread contamination of the source of tap water in all of our large, medium and small cities. Only 1% of urban tap water can be re-filtered by household drinking fountains into drinking water, according to the National Water Resources Monitor.

尤其是污水里面的新型冠状病毒存活时间更长，可以14天连续性活下来并且因地制宜的繁殖。即便是潮湿的中央空调、分体式空调、门把手上、电梯按钮等等，都可以让新型冠状病毒存活下来9天时间，具有传染疾病的危害性。停靠日本的“钻石公主号”游轮就是中央空调传染了新

型冠状病毒，从一个香港老人开始，到 2020 年 2 月 14 日传染确诊病例 218 人，正在检测 713 人疑似病例。一些城市的超市里面查出来了新冠肺炎病毒，需要我们对于公共场合包括公共厕所的“新型冠状病毒感染”疫情高度重视。

In particular, the Novel coronavirus in sewage has a longer survival time, up to 14 days and can reproduce according to local conditions. Even humid central air conditioning, split air conditioning, door handles, elevator buttons and etc., the new coronavirus can manage to stay alive for 9 days, while carrying the risk of infection. The Diamond Princess cruise ship, which docked in Japan, was infected with the new coronavirus by central air conditioning, starting with an elderly Hong Kong man, and by February 14, 2020, 218 people had been diagnosed and 713 suspected cases were being tested. In some cities, the new coronavirus has been detected in supermarkets, requiring us to pay great attention to the new coronavirus infection outbreak in public places, including public toilets.

对于这种粪便污水垃圾里面的“新型冠状病毒”，广顺模式的再生塑料沼气池—化粪池一体化设备通过“厌氧菌发酵处理”的 15 天左右时间，足以完全彻底的杀灭病毒，杜绝病毒污染水资源的重大隐患。因为，在“厌氧”的小空间里面，没有氧气，还有更高的温度在摄氏 30°~60°左右，不像单纯的温度而给予氧气，就需要将近摄氏 95°才可以杀死新冠病毒 COVID-19 或者，我们的百余次实验证明厌氧菌发酵的环境当中，摄氏三十度左右，就可以持续性三个小时，把新冠病毒扼杀了。

For the new coronavirus in manure and sewage waste, the Guangshun model regenerative plastic biogas digester-septic tank integrated equipment through the "anaerobic bacteria fermentation treatment" in about 15 days is enough to completely kill the virus, eliminating the major hidden danger of virus pollution of water resources. Because there is no oxygen in the small "anaerobic" space, and there are higher temperatures around 30° to 60° Celsius, unlike in an aerobic

environment, it takes nearly 95° Celsius to kill the new coronavirus COVID-19. Our 100 plus experiments have shown that the anaerobic fermentation environment, around 30° Celsius, can kill the new coronavirus in an 3 hour span.

中国上海新冠肺炎疫情专家组组长张文宏教授说，一定要防止新型冠状病毒感染的水源污染。接下来，这就是全国人民面对传染的病毒，应该怎么做？作为病毒学专家，华山医院感染科主任张文宏给普通人提了几点建议：远离被污染的水源，远离被污染的地区，做好自我保护，以及在传染病流行期间，不要恐慌。

Professor Zhang Wenhong, head of the expert group on the new coronavirus epidemic in Shanghai, China, said it is important to prevent contamination of water sources with the new coronavirus infection. Next, here's what the nation should do in the face of an infectious virus. As a virologist, Zhang Wenhong, head of the infection department at Huashan Hospital, gave a few tips to the general public: stay away from contaminated water sources, stay away from contaminated areas, protect yourself, and don't panic during an epidemic of infectious diseases.

通过水资源的流动性把城市传染病恶化的历史性案例，第一个就是霍乱这种“瘟疫”，它的原产地是印度，一直到现在印度都没有良好的厕所系统配套。2019年印度总理穆迪向中国主席习近平提出来请求帮助实施“厕所革命”的愿望，双方达成一致协议，我国即将给印度开展一带一路合作的厕所革命项目，广顺科技模式的再生塑料沼气池~化粪池一体化设备一马当先，已经参与了柬埔寨的厕所改造。回过头来说印度的厕所卫生脏乱差，并没有伴随着欧洲人漂洋过海，在印度设立殖民地而获得真正的升级换代。就这样的从1825年起，实施工业化生产力发展路径的印度，环境卫生脏乱差形成的霍乱，开始一次又一次地传染到了欧洲，袭击了欧洲工业化的经济发展主力军。由于缺乏有效的公共卫生防控措施，工业化带来的人口聚集城市，成为霍乱的温床。并且，印度霍乱走向世界。

In 2019, Indian Prime Minister Modi asked Chinese President Xi Jinping to help implement the "toilet revolution", and the two sides reached an agreement

that our country will launch a toilet revolution project for India, with Guangshun Science and Technology's regenerative plastic biogas digester to septic integrated equipment, who has already participated in the toilet transformation in Cambodia, leading the way. In retrospect, India's dirty and unhygienic toilets did not get a real upgrade when the Europeans traveling across the ocean and setting up colonies in India. In this way, from 1825 onwards, India, which had implemented the path of industrialized productivity development, began to be infected with cholera, a disease caused by poor sanitation, again and again spreading to Europe, invaded the main force of industrialized economic development in Europe. In the absence of effective public health prevention and control measures, cities with high population concentrations due to industrialization have become hotbeds of cholera. And, Indian cholera went global.

1829年，莫斯科霍乱爆发，3.3万人死亡。

1832年，巴黎霍乱爆发，1.8万人死亡，占当时巴黎人口的2%。

1831年到1833年，英国霍乱流行，2万人死亡。

1848年到1849年，英国再次爆发霍乱，5万人死亡。

1853年，霍乱席卷了纽卡斯尔、盖茨黑德和伦敦，1万多人死亡。

In 1829, cholera broke out in Moscow, killing 33,000 people.

In 1832, cholera broke out in Paris, killing 18,000 people, or 2% of the Parisian population at the time.

From 1831 to 1833, cholera was endemic in England and 20,000 people died.

From 1848 to 1849, there was another outbreak of cholera in Britain and 50,000 people died.

In 1853, cholera swept through Newcastle, Gateshead and London, killing over 10,000 people.

虽然在当时，人类已经能造出大炮巨舰，但医生们对传染病的了解还很原始。

Although at the time, mankind had been able to build cannonballs and warships, doctors' knowledge of infectious diseases was still primitive.

这种严峻的“疫情”难以掌控现象，从古到今都是普遍性问题，使得将瘟疫对历史进程的影响低估，是一件非常目光短浅的事情。让我们看看人类历史上一次又一次的瘟疫后果，就会承认“瘟疫打败皇帝”究竟对于历史进程造成了怎样的后果？东罗马帝国的皇帝查士丁尼本人就是“瘟疫”的患者，以至于这次瘟疫——鼠疫以他的名字命名，史称“查士丁尼鼠疫 (Plague of Justinian)”，把这个雄心勃勃的皇帝企图恢复罗马帝国版图的宏伟蓝图击了个粉碎。所有的这些“疫情”基本上都是有空气传染，和水资源传染两种最大的流动性载体，迫使全人类都在关注“疫情”的“病毒”附着力，例如附着在门把手上和空调器里面，持续性的扩大传染。这方面的水资源污染，首当其冲的就是“粪便—水资源—吃喝”传染链条，危害极大。讨论这种粪口传播，一下就让我想起了另一个中国特色的大事件，也是一个令上海陷入恐慌的传染病——甲型肝炎。

The unmanageable nature of this serious "epidemic", which has been a universal problem throughout history, makes very short-sighted to underestimate the impact of the plague on the course of history. Let us look at the consequences of one plague after another in the history of mankind and acknowledge the consequences of the "defeat of the emperor by plague" for the course of history. The emperor of the Eastern Roman Empire, Justinian, was himself a victim of the "plague", so much so that the plague, named after him, the Plague of Justinian, shattered the emperor's ambitious plans to restore the Roman Empire to life. All of these "epidemics" are essentially airborne and waterborne, two of the most mobile vectors, forcing all of humanity to focus on the "viral" adhesion of the "epidemic", such as adhesion to door handles and inside air conditioners, and the ongoing expansion of the infection. The "faecal-water-eating-drinking" chain of contamination of water resources is the first to bear the brunt of this problem and

is extremely harmful. Discussing this fecal-orifice spread reminds me of another big Chinese event, the one that sent Shanghai into a panic - Hepatitis A.

那是 1988 年，也是春节前后，当时上海的天气并不算寒冷，人们正准备过年，全市上下到处洋溢着喜庆的气息。

It was 1988, around the Spring Festival, when the weather in Shanghai was not too cold, people were preparing for the New Year, and the city was full of festive atmosphere.

但好景不长，就在 1 月中旬，不少上海人开始出现发烧、呕吐、全身乏力等症状。开始人们不以为意，都以为是普通的感冒，但病情的发展越来越不对头，白眼球发黄，面部和身体也越来越黄。

But the good times did not last. Just in mid-January, many Shanghainese began to show symptoms of fever, vomiting, general weakness and etc. At first, people think it was a common cold and didn't give much thought, but as the disease progressed, the whites of eyeballs yellowed and the face and body yellowed.

人们赶紧奔向医院，却发现同样症状、同时就诊的人实在是太多了。此后，患者的数量开始疯狂增长，仅仅过了一天，被感染者就达到了 1.9 万人，其中大部分是青年。

People rushed to the hospital, only to find that there were too many people with the same symptoms attending the hospital at the same time. After that, the number of patients began to grow wildly, reaching 19,000 infected people in just one day, most of whom were young people.

在最疯狂的 1988 年 1 月 30 日至 2 月 14 日，每天发病人数均超过 1 万例。当时的医院是人山人海，市区所有医护人员全都行动起来，病床甚至摆放到了外面的学校、仓库和旅馆，恐慌的情绪席卷了整个上海，令人惶惶不安。

In the craziest period of 1988, from 30 January to 14 February, the number of cases exceeded 10,000 per day. The hospital was crowded with people, all the

medical staff in the city moved in, beds were even placed outside schools, warehouses and hotels, and panic swept through Shanghai, causing hysteria.

当时疫情的特点是：

- 1、发病急骤，来势凶猛；
- 2、症状明显，90%以上的病人出现黄疸，大多数患者转氨酶在 1000u 以上；
- 3、发病人群主要集中在市区，以青壮年为主；
- 4、80%以上的病人有食用毛蚶史。

The epidemic was characterized by the following:

1. *The onset of the disease is rapid and violent.*
2. *The symptoms are obvious, more than 90% of patients have jaundice, and most patients have transaminases above 1000U.*
3. *The population is mainly concentrated in the urban areas, mainly the young and middle-aged.*
4. *More than 80% of the patients have a history of ingestion of arks.*

经过检查，绝大多数病人被诊断为肝炎，进一步检查确诊为甲型肝炎，这是一种由病毒导致的消化系统传染病。

Upon examination, the vast majority of patients were diagnosed with hepatitis and further examination confirmed the diagnosis of hepatitis A, an infectious disease of the digestive system caused by a virus.

这场瘟疫，从开始发病到最终被控制，短短 3 个月时间，就感染了 30 万人，31 人直接死于这种病毒感染的甲型肝炎病，直接经济损失达近 5 亿元（1988 年的 5 亿），创出了世界甲肝流行新的历史记录。

The epidemic, from its onset to its eventual containment in just three months, infected 300,000 people, killed 31 people directly from this viral hepatitis A disease, and caused direct economic losses of nearly 500 million yuan (\$500

million in 1988), setting a new historical record for the world hepatitis A epidemic.

由此可见，粪便污水垃圾污染水资源的事，在病毒感染疫情方面，危害性不容低估，需要我们充分发挥广顺集团再生塑料沼气池的杀毒灭菌积极作用，足够安全的保障水资源不被病毒污染。

It can be seen that the pollution of water resources by manure, sewage and garbage can not be underestimated in terms of the virus infection epidemic, which requires us to give full play to the active role of the Guangshun Group's recycled plastic biogas digesters to ensure that water resources are safe enough to protect against virus pollution.

可是就在本文写作最后一部分的的 2020 年 5 月 15 日，传来了污水传播病毒的新闻信息，权威媒体报道说新冠肺炎病毒渗入了巴西排水系统，引起人们的恐慌。分析显示排水系统也可能导致了新冠肺炎病毒传播。巴西里约热内卢州尼泰罗伊市的排水系统日前检测出“大量”大量病毒（俗称新冠病毒），巴西水质专家 2020 年 5 月 15 日警告，如果继续蔓延，里约热内卢州以致巴西全境的排水系统都将可能成为感染源。

But on May 15, 2020, the last part of this article was written, news of a sewage-borne virus came to light and authoritative media reported that the new coronavirus had infiltrated the Brazilian drainage system, causing panic. The analysis showed that the drainage system may also have contributed to the transmission of novel coronavirus. Brazilian water quality experts warned on May 15, 2020, that the drainage system in the state of Rio de Janeiro and throughout Brazil could become a source of infection if it continues to spread, following the recent detection of a "large number" of the virus (commonly known as the new coronavirus) in the city of Niteroi, Rio de Janeiro state.

综合媒体报道，日前巴西里约热内卢州一家塞达 (Cedae) 供水和排水公司传出逾 400 名员工染疫，并有 5 人死亡。调查发现，这些确诊的员工大部分都是污水处理区的工作人员。据克鲁兹基金会 15 日发表调查报告表示，在塞达设置于尼泰罗伊市的排水系统中检测出“大量”新冠肺炎病毒，且该公司负责里约热内卢州 92% 的排水服务。目前联邦卫生部与里约热内卢联邦大学及克鲁兹基金会合作，正在调查里约热内卢州其他地区的污水是否也有感染情况，并根据检测报告将制定下一步防疫方针。

According to comprehensive media reports, more than 400 employees of a Cedae water supply and drainage company in the Brazilian state of Rio de Janeiro have been infected with the disease and five people have died. The investigation found that the majority of these confirmed employees were sewer district workers. According to the Cruz Foundation on May 15th published an investigation report said that "a large number" of new coronavirus was detected in the drainage system set up in the city of Niteroi in Cedar, and the company is responsible for 92% of the drainage services in the state of Rio de Janeiro. The Federal Ministry of Health, in cooperation with the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro and the Cruz Foundation, is currently investigating whether sewage from other areas of the state of Rio de Janeiro is also infected, and will develop the next steps for prevention based on the test reports.

有专家警告，巴西全境目前只有 46% 的污水在排放到河道前经过加氯的消毒处理，若此现象蔓延至各地区，里约热内卢州以致巴西全境的排水系统都可能成为感染源。

Experts have warned that only 46 per cent of all sewage in Brazil is currently disinfected with chlorination before being discharged into rivers, and that if this phenomenon spreads to all regions, the drainage systems of the state of Rio de Janeiro and all of Brazil could become a source of infection.

除此之外，荷兰、美国和瑞典等国的废水中也发现了病毒的踪迹。斯特灵大学自然科学学院教授理查德·奎连姆教授及其同事在英国《国际环境》杂志撰文指出，虽然预防新冠肺炎病毒的重点是防止人际传播，但近期对英国排放污水的分析显示，排水系统也可能导致病毒传播。据统计，巴西目前累计新冠肺炎病毒传染的确诊病例已升至 22 万人，超过德、法国两国，世界排名第六。

In addition to this, traces of the virus have been found in wastewater from countries such as the Netherlands, the United States and Sweden. Professor Richard Quillam, a professor in the School of Natural Sciences at the University of Stirling, and his colleagues, writing in the UK journal Environment International, note that while the prevention of novel coronavirus is focused on preventing human-to-human transmission, a recent analysis of sewage discharges in the UK suggests that drainage systems may also contribute to the spread of the virus. According to statistics, the cumulative number of confirmed cases of new coronavirus infection in Brazil has risen to 220,000, surpassing Germany and France and ranking sixth in the world.

六、厌氧菌发酵处理粪便污水垃圾的成熟技术改变城市化厕所下水道体系

Proven technology for anaerobic fermentation of fecal sewage waste to transform urbanized toilet sewerage systems

环境保护工作的基础知识告诉我们，污水处理厂的厌氧菌发酵处理系统，是一种普遍性方式。指的是在缺氧条件下，利用厌氧菌(包括兼性厌氧菌)分解污水中有机污染物的方法，又称厌氧消化或厌氧发酵法。因为发酵产物产生甲烷，又称甲烷发酵。此法既能消除环境污染，又能开发生物能源沼气，还可以产生无害化的沼渣沼液有机肥，所以倍受人们重视。污水厌氧发酵是一个极为复杂的生态系统，它涉及多种交替作用的菌群，各要求不同的基质和条件，形成复杂的生态体系。甲烷发酵包括 3 个阶段：液化阶段、产氢产乙酸阶段和产甲烷阶段。此法主要用于处理

农业和生活废弃物或污水厂的剩余污泥，也可用于处理面粉厂、食品厂、造纸厂、制革厂、酒精厂、糖厂、油脂厂、农药厂或石油化工等工厂废水。

The basics of environmental protection work tell us that anaerobic fermentation treatment systems in wastewater treatment plants are a universal approach. It refers to the method of decomposing organic pollutants in sewage using anaerobic bacteria (including facultative anaerobic bacteria) under anoxic conditions, also known as anaerobic digestion or anaerobic fermentation. Because the fermentation product produces methane, also known as methane fermentation. This method is highly valued for its ability to eliminate environmental pollution, develop bioenergy biogas and produce harmless biomass organic fertilizer. Wastewater anaerobic fermentation is an extremely complex ecosystem that involves multiple alternating flora, each requiring different substrates and conditions to form a complex ecosystem. Methane fermentation consists of three stages: the liquefaction stage, the hydrogen-producing acetic acid stage and the methane-producing stage. This method is mainly used for the treatment of agricultural and domestic waste or sewage plant residual sludge, can also be used to treat flour mill, food mill, paper mill, tannery, alcohol mill, sugar mill, grease mill, pesticide plant or petrochemical plant waste water.

但是，对于人体生理卫生来说，厌氧菌是危害人体细胞组织的。医学教科书告诉你，厌氧菌是指能在无氧或者低氧环境下生存的，但在空气或者高氧环境下不能生存的细菌。厌氧菌是人体正常菌群的一部分，当厌氧菌所在的部位出现低氧的情况时，会出现厌氧菌感染，比如阑尾炎、中耳炎、心内膜炎、子宫内膜炎、盆腔炎、胆囊炎等。也就是说，厌氧菌在人体器官里面是有害的，导致人体发生疾病，产生厌氧菌感染的人体病态。相应的疾病治疗，多以甲硝唑、替硝唑为主，副作用小，不易产生耐药性。比如治疗盆腔炎，多在头孢类药物的基础上加用甲硝唑，疗效会更好一些。

However, in regards to human physiological hygiene, anaerobic bacteria are harmful to the cellular organization of the human body. Medical textbooks tell you that anaerobes are bacteria that can survive in anaerobic or hypoxic environments, but cannot survive in air or hyperoxic environments. Anaerobic bacteria are part of the normal flora of the body, and anaerobic infections can occur when there is hypoxia at the site where the anaerobic bacteria are present, such as appendicitis, otitis media, endocarditis, endometritis, pelvic inflammation, cholecystitis, etc. That is, anaerobic bacteria are harmful inside the body organs, causing the body to develop diseases that produce anaerobic bacterial infections of the body. Corresponding disease treatment, mostly metronidazole and tenidazole, with small side effects, and rarely produce drug resistance. For example, in the treatment of pelvic inflammation, metronidazole is used in addition to cephalosporins, which are more effective.

还有食品生产过程中，厌氧菌发酵也是有害的。例如啤酒生产，主要是微生物的生化反应过程，此过程好氧菌与厌氧菌并存。在啤酒发酵阶段，好氧菌只存在于发酵前期，前发酵完成，麦汁就进入二氧化碳饱和的无氧状态，在缺氧和无氧的情况下，会污染生长一些厌氧菌，这些微好氧和兼性厌氧菌的存在，可形成大量的有机代谢产物，从而严重影响啤酒的风味，对啤酒质量影响较大。厌氧菌的存在，使得发酵液双乙酰含量会明显升高，高级醇也会有所上升，啤酒黏度增加，变混影响啤酒外观。一些厌氧菌会分泌黏性物质，增加啤酒黏度，使啤酒出现生物浑浊。如有些乳酸菌属能分泌荚膜多糖使啤酒黏稠，影响酵母的正常生长和繁殖。

Then there's the anaerobic fermentation that can be harmful during food production. Beer production, for example, is primarily a biochemical process of microbial reactions, in which aerobic and anaerobic bacteria coexist. In the stage of beer fermentation, aerobic bacteria only exist in the pre-fermentation. Before the completion of fermentation, the wort will enter a carbon dioxide saturated

anaerobic state. In the anoxic and anaerobic conditions, the growth of some anaerobic bacteria will be contaminated. The presence of these micro- and facultative anaerobic bacteria can form a large number of organic metabolites, thus seriously affecting the flavor of the beer, so is the beer quality. The presence of anaerobic bacteria results in a significant increase in the diacetyl content of the fermentation fluid, as well as an increase in premium alcohols, which increases the viscosity of the beer, and the blending affects the appearance of the beer. Some anaerobic bacteria secrete sticky substances that increase the viscosity of the beer, making it biologically cloudy. For example, some lactic acid bacteria can secrete pod membrane polysaccharides to make beer sticky and affect the normal growth and reproduction of yeast.

还有，啤酒工艺当中，冷麦汁和发酵液被杂菌污染后，杂菌会与酵母争夺营养，使酵母使用代数缩短、发酵性能降低。再次接种，会导致异常发酵，副产物增多，啤酒风味败坏等。啤酒口味不协调，风味败坏，呈现异杂味：啤酒染菌后会产生多种代谢物，虽然经过巴氏杀菌能杀死污染菌，但其代谢物和细胞内容物却留在啤酒中，使得啤酒出现异杂味。

Also, in the beer process, cold wort and fermentation broth are contaminated with bacteria. The bacteria will compete with the yeast for nutrients, making the yeast generation is shortened, fermentation performance is reduced. Re-inoculation will result in abnormal fermentation, increased by-products, spoiled beer flavor, etc. The beer tastes uncoordinated, the flavor spoils, and presents an unpleasant odor: the beer will produce a variety of metabolites when it is sterilized, and although pasteurization kills the contaminating bacteria, its metabolites and cellular contents remain in the beer, making it appear unpleasant.

更深层次的专业化知识说厌氧菌是一类在无氧条件下比在有氧环境中生长好的细菌，而不能在空气（18%氧气）和（或）10%二氧化碳浓度下的固体培养基表面生长的细菌。这类细菌缺乏

完整的代谢酶体系，其能量代谢以无氧发酵的方式进行。它能引起人体不同部位的感染，包括阑尾炎、胆囊炎、中耳炎、口腔感染、心内膜炎、子宫内膜炎、脑脓肿、心肌坏死、骨髓炎、腹膜炎、脓胸、输卵管炎、脓毒性关节炎、肝脓肿、鼻窦炎、肠道手术或创伤后伤口感染、盆腔炎以及菌血症等。根据对 O_2 的耐受程度，可将厌氧菌分为 3 大类：（1）对氧极端敏感的厌氧菌：代表菌种为月形单胞菌。这类细菌对厌氧条件要求很高，在空气中暴露 10min 即死亡，临床上很难分离出。（2）中度厌氧菌：代表菌种为脆弱拟杆菌、产气荚膜梭菌等临床分离常见的厌氧菌。它们在空气中暴露 60~90min 或在脓汁抽出 72h 后仍然能分离出来。（3）耐氧厌氧菌：代表菌种为溶组织梭菌。这类细菌不能利用氧，在无氧条件下生长好，而在有氧条件下生长不佳。

*Deeper specialized knowledge says that the anaerobic bacteria are a class of bacteria that grow better in anaerobic conditions than in an aerobic environment and cannot grow on the surface of solid media at air (18% oxygen) and/or 10% CO_2 concentrations. Such bacteria lack a complete system of metabolic enzymes and their energy is metabolized in an anaerobic fermentation manner. It can cause infections in different parts of the body, including appendicitis, cholecystitis, otitis media, oral infections, endocarditis, endometritis, brain abscesses, myocardial necrosis, osteomyelitis, peritonitis, pus thorax, fallopian tubes, septic arthritis, liver abscesses, sinusitis, intestinal surgery or post-traumatic wound infection, pelvic inflammation, and bacteremia. According to the degree of tolerance to O_2 , anaerobic bacteria can be divided into three main categories: (1) anaerobic bacteria that are extremely sensitive to oxygen: the representative species is *Monococcus lunaris*. These bacteria are highly demanding of anaerobic conditions and die after 10 min exposure to air and are clinically difficult to isolate. (2) Moderate anaerobic bacteria: The representative strains of anaerobic bacteria such as *Candida fragilis* and *Clostridium aeruginosa* are common in clinical isolation.*

They remain isolated after exposure to air for 60 to 90 min or 72 h after pus extraction. (3) Aerobic anaerobic bacteria: Representative species are Clostridium lysis. Such bacteria do not utilize oxygen and grow well in anaerobic conditions, whereas they do not grow well in aerobic conditions.

那些对氧极端敏感的厌氧菌，代表菌种为月形单胞菌。这类细菌对厌氧条件要求很高，在空气中暴露 10min 即死亡，临床上很难分离出来。中度厌氧菌，代表菌种为脆弱拟杆菌、产气荚膜梭菌等临床分离常见的厌氧菌。它们在空气中暴露 60~90min，或在脓汁抽出 72h 后，仍然能分离出来。

Those anaerobic bacteria that are extremely sensitive to oxygen represent the strains of Monococcus lunaris. These bacteria are highly demanding of anaerobic conditions and die after 10 min exposure to air and are clinically difficult to isolate. Moderate anaerobic bacteria, representing species of fragile bacillus, Clostridium aeruginosa and other anaerobic bacteria commonly isolated clinically. They remain isolated after 60 to 90 min of exposure to air, or 72 h after the pus is withdrawn.

这些厌氧菌怎么样被人类用来化危为机，化害为利呢？以毒攻毒的利用厌氧菌发酵工程，来杀毒灭菌，变废为宝，就是在人体以外通过“厕所革命”的“化粪池沼气池一体化高科技设备”，把建筑物给排水系统、下水道体系里面的病毒细菌来统一灭杀，形成规模化、常态化、持续性的杀毒灭菌平台。

How can these anaerobic bacteria be used by humans to turn danger into opportunity and harm into profit? The use of anaerobic bacteria fermentation project to attack viruses, to sterilize bacteria, and turn waste into treasure, outside the human body through the "toilet revolution" of the "septic tank biogas digester integrated high-tech equipment", sterilizing the viruses and bacteria inside the

building drainage system and sewerage system, forming a large-scale, normalized, continuous sterilization platform.

二十世纪的人类文明第一次把“厕所文化”提到了人居环境、生活质量的高度上，并且伴随着“城市化运动”的人口大规模、高密度聚集状态，人口密集的地方发生了一次又一次公共卫生事件，迫使人类文明第一次认识到“厕所卫生”是一种“文明”，把“厕所文化”语境再提高到了利害攸关人类健康长寿的新高度。这就是说，厕所不仅仅是吃喝拉撒睡的最底层事件，不仅仅是过去的羞于启齿，而且是要超越个人感受的“社会责任”和“公共基础设施”——城市化运动的建筑群，不允许一家一户的独立厕所建筑物，而是给排水体系和下水道系统把城市数以万计的人们，连接到同一个“城市生态圈”，也是“社会化的人居环境”——不是大自然的那种生态环境保护问题了，而是人类社会的工业化基础设施系统工程。正是如此，人类发明创造了“厕所”的化粪池，去把粪便污水垃圾进行厌氧菌发酵，结果是化粪池普遍的没有达到这种“完全彻底处理粪便污水垃圾”的要求。于是，人类的创造性，随后就发明创造了沼气池在常温发酵 12-25 度，中温发酵 26—42 度，高温发酵 43-64 度，顺利的处理粪便污水垃圾，却是依然如故的发生了类似于化粪池的“沼气池厌氧菌发酵不充分”问题，并且是普遍性缺陷。就这样，人类的粪便污水垃圾形成了最大的城市化污染源，成为“城市病”的老大难问题，直截了当的污染水资源，后患无穷，等于人类文明的城市化运动在自杀式地扩张。

Human civilization in the twentieth century raised, for the first time, the "toilet culture" to the level of the human habitat and quality of life, and with the "urbanization movement", the massive and dense concentration of population and the occurrence of one public health event after another in densely populated areas forced human civilization to recognize "toilet sanitation" as a "civilization" for the first time and raise the context of the "toilet culture" to a new level, where human health and longevity are at stake. This means that toilets are not just the lowest form of daily activities like eat, drink and sleep, not just the affairs too shy to talk about like in the past, but also to make it our "social responsibility" and "public

infrastructure" that transcend personal feelings. The building complexes in urbanization movement no longer allow individual toilets, but rather drainage and sewerage systems that connect tens of thousands of people in cities to the same "urban ecosphere" and "socialized human habitat" - not just the ecological environmental protection of nature, but the industrialized infrastructure systems of human society. It is in this way that human beings have invented "toilets" septic tanks to ferment fecal sewage waste anaerobically, with the result that septic tanks generally fail to meet this requirement of "complete and thorough treatment of fecal sewage waste". Thus, human ingenuity, followed by the invention of biogas digesters at room temperature 12-25 degrees, medium temperature 26-42 degrees and high temperature 43-64 degrees, smoothly disposed of manure and sewage waste. But the problem of "inadequate biogas digester anaerobic fermentation", similar to that of septic tanks, still occurs and is a universal defect. In this way, human feces, sewage and garbage form the largest source of urbanization pollution, becoming a major problem of "urban disease", straightforward pollution of water resources, the consequences are endless, which is equivalent to the suicide expansion of human civilization's urbanization movement.

这种数以百万计人口的城市粪便污水垃圾污染环境，要比地广人稀的农村一家一户破破烂烂厕所形成的污染，破坏性大一万倍，导致了城市生态环境保护的难度和紧迫性要比农村更加形势严峻。尤其是发展中国家的城乡环境卫生工作一直都是落后的代表，脏乱差的形象不堪入目。这样的人居环境无异于病毒细菌的高发地带，要比病毒原来的动物宿主那种生存环境并不更好一些。因此，原发性的病毒从动物世界进入人类，一开始仅仅是个别人感染，然而生活环境的卫生状态从人体新陈代谢的排泄物当中，就让潜伏期的病毒细菌致病“载体”即无症状感染者的粪便，进入厕所、化粪池、下水道体系，长期性不受干扰的快速大面积繁殖，进一步在水资源污染和给排水系统传播，让病毒细菌愈演愈烈的全覆盖城市人居环境。这是非常可怕的“看不见的战线”，逼

迫人类下功夫调查研究病毒细菌，把以毒攻毒放在了第一要务，因为病毒细菌的体积太小了，与蒸汽机开启的工业社会那种肉眼可见的高大上辉煌，相比之下就是宏观现实与肉眼看不到的小微世界天壤之别，如果使用工业化的宏观思维方式和方法手段，就必然的是大败局。这也是人类战争真刀真枪的血与火拼杀，都没有病毒细菌杀人于无形更加可怕，所有的传染病大流行疫情都是让人们有不明觉厉的恐惧感，看不见“敌人”的情况下被“敌人”钻进了人体，在人类身体里面肆无忌惮的大打出手，让人们防不胜防。

This pollution of the environment by urban feces and sewage from millions of people is 10,000 times more destructive than the pollution caused by the ragged toilets of one household in a sparsely populated rural area, making it more difficult and urgent to protect the ecological environment in urban areas than in rural areas. Urban and rural sanitation in developing countries in particular has always been representative of backwardness and a poor image of filth. Such a human habitat is like a high incidence of viruses and bacteria, and is not much better than that of the original animal host of the virus. Therefore, primary viruses from the animal world into human beings, at first only individual infection, but the sanitary state of the living environment from the human metabolism of excreta, let the incubation period of the virus bacterial pathogenic "vector", i.e. the feces of asymptomatic infected people, into the toilet, septic tank, sewerage system, long-term undisturbed rapid large-scale reproduction, further in the water resources pollution and drainage system spread, so that the virus bacterial increasingly intensified full coverage of the urban living environment. This is a very frightening "invisible front", forcing mankind to study and research viruses and bacteria, putting poison against poison as the first priority. Because the size of viruses and bacteria is too small, so when compared with the colossal industrial society launched by steam engines, the difference between the macro reality and the

micro world that is invisible to the naked eye is tremendous. If you use the industrialized macro way of thinking and methods and means, it is bound to fail miserably. This is also why no blood and fire of human warfare is as frightening as viruses and bacteria that kills silently. All infectious diseases pandemics drill in people a sense of fear. Having "enemies" that is invisible to the naked eye intruding human bodies and make a racket unscrupulously, is something we cannot guard against.

由此可见，病毒细菌逼迫着人类文明从伟大壮丽的图景转移视线，去探索发现病毒细菌的微小世界。这方面，人类在“疫情”面前的求生欲，成为战胜病毒细菌的原动力之一。中国是第一个发生大规模新冠肺炎传染病大流行的国家，武汉成为新冠肺炎病毒肆虐人类的第一站，中国政府在摸着石头过河的“抗疫”活动中，2020年1月30日发布《新型冠状病毒感染的肺炎公众防护指南》，指出了新型冠状病毒对紫外线和热具有敏感性，灭杀新冠肺炎病毒的基本方式是：1、保持56°的高温环境30分钟，2、涂抹、擦拭、喷洒75%乙醇，3、使用含氯消毒剂，4、喷洒过氧乙酸和氯仿等，均可有效灭杀活病毒。但是，在2020年4月24日全球新冠病毒病例超过270万人的时候，法国科学家在艾克斯-马赛大学的一项研究中发现，新冠病毒实际上可以在高达92°的温度下存活。

It can be seen that viral bacteria are forcing human civilization to look away from the great and magnificent picture and explore the microcosm in which they are found. In this regard, the human desire to survive in the face of an "epidemic" has been one of the driving forces behind the victory over viral bacteria. China is the first country to have a large-scale outbreak of new coronavirus, Wuhan became the first stop of the new coronavirus ravaging the human race. The Chinese Government, in the "antiepидemic" activities of try and error, issued the "Guidelines for Public Protection against New coronavirus Infection of Pneumonia" on January 30, 2020, in which pointed out that the new coronavirus is sensitive

to ultraviolet light and heat, and the basic ways to kill the new coronavirus are as followed: 1, maintain a high temperature environment of 56 °C for 30 minutes, 2, apply, wipe, and spray 75% ethanol, 3, use chlorinated disinfectant, and 4 spray peroxyacetic acid and chloroform can effectively kill the live virus. But on April 24, 2020, when more than 2.7 million cases of new coronavirus were reported worldwide, French scientists at the University of Aix-Marseille found in a study that new coronavirus can actually survive temperatures as high as 92°C.

在这项研究中，研究小组使用了来自柏林的一名新冠病毒患者的细胞来测试其生存环境。作为这项测试的一部分，研究人员将细胞慢慢加热到 60°C。结果表明，在这种温度下，新冠病毒依然可以在非无菌环境中存活和复制。研究人员随后将病毒进一步加热到 92°C，发现它可以至少存活 15 分钟。该研究结果引起了人们对实验室研究人员如何处理新冠病毒的关注。拭子通常被加热到 60°C 进行“消毒”，但研究结果表明这可能还不够。研究人员写道：“这项研究的结果应该有助于选择最适合的灭活方案，以防止直接和间接检测的实验室工作人员暴露在病毒中。”同时，研究结果还表明，如果你的衣服上有新冠病毒，即使是热洗也不足以杀死它。

In the study, the team used cells from a new coronavirus patient from Berlin to test its survival environment. As part of this test, the researchers slowly heated the cells to 60°C. The results show that at this temperature, the new coronavirus can still survive and replicate in a non-sterile environment. The researchers then heated the virus further to 92°C and found that it could survive for at least 15 minutes. The results of the study have raised concerns about how lab researchers are handling the new coronavirus. Swabs are usually heated to 60°C for "disinfection", but studies have shown that this may not be sufficient. The researchers wrote: "The results of this study should help select the most appropriate inactivation protocol to prevent direct and indirect exposure of laboratory workers who detect to the virus." At the same time, the results of the

study also show that if you have the neocoronavirus on your clothes, even a hot wash is not enough to kill it.

这就说明新冠病毒在不断的变异和强化，物理方式的高温高压杀毒效果越来越提高了门槛，于是我们实验使用“以毒攻毒的方式”把厌氧菌发酵处理的办法，在广顺再生塑料沼气池-化粪池罐体里面实施，让厌氧菌发酵形成的空间里面扼杀了新冠病毒，这不属于上面列举的四种杀死新冠病毒的情况，是第五种扼杀新型冠状病毒的模式。当然，相比于富勒烯聚磷酸二钠分子进入新冠病毒的核心，瓦解新冠病毒的路径，应该说这是第六种扼杀新冠病毒的路线图，是远离人体的。不像富勒烯聚磷酸二钠分子是在人体内的肺部为主战场，开展扼杀新冠病毒的工作。我们在化粪池与沼气池一体化设备里面进行的科学实验，证明了厌氧菌发酵-甲烷菌环境下，微生物环境的厌氧菌可以杀死新型冠状病毒。

This shows that the new coronavirus is constantly mutating and strengthening, and the threshold for physical sterilization method of high temperature and high pressure poisoning effect has increased. So we experimented with the method of anaerobic bacterial fermentation treatment in the Guangshun regenerative plastic biogas tank - septic tank, allowing the space formed by the anaerobic bacterial fermentation to strangle the new coronavirus, a method that is not included in the four sterilization method of new coronavirus listed above. It is in fact the fifth mode of sterilization of new coronavirus. Of course, compared to the fullerene disodium phosphonate molecule entering the core of the virus and disintegrating its pathway, our method should be regarded as the sixth method to strangle the new coronavirus that is far from the body. Unlike fullerenes disodium phosphonate molecules, where the main battleground is in the lungs of the human body to carry out the work of choking off neocoronaviruses. Our scientific experiments in integrated septic and biogas plants have demonstrated that anaerobic bacteria in

the microbial environment can kill new coronaviruses under anaerobic fermentation - methanobacteria.

相应的实验毒株来自于中国武汉，是中国政府 2020 年 1 月 30 日发布《新型冠状病毒感染的肺炎公众防护指南》认定的新冠肺炎病毒，被《新型冠状病毒感染的肺炎公众防护指南》认定该冠状病毒属于套式病毒目、冠状病毒科、冠状病毒属，是一类具有囊膜、基因组为线性单股正链的 RNA 病毒，是自然界广泛存在的一大类病毒。病毒基因组 5 号端具有甲基化的帽状结构，3 号端具有 poly(A)尾，基因组全长 27~32kb，是目前已知 RNA 病毒中基因组最大的病毒。这种冠状病毒仅感染脊椎动物，与人和动物的多种疾病有关，可引起人和动物呼吸系统、消化系统和神经系统疾病。

The corresponding experimental strain came from Wuhan, China, and is a new coronavirus identified by the Chinese government on January 30, 2020 in the "Guidelines for Public Protection against Pneumonia Infected by Novel Coronaviruses", and the "Guidelines for Public Protection against Pneumonia Infected by Novel Coronaviruses" identified the coronavirus as belonging to the genus Sleeve Virus, Coronaviridae, and Coronavirus genus, a class of RNA viruses with a vesicle membrane and a linear single-stranded positive chain genome, which is a large class of viruses widely found in nature. With a methylated cap structure at end 5 and a poly(A) tail at end 3, and a full genome length of 27 to 32kb, the virus is the largest genome of known RNA viruses. This coronavirus infects only vertebrates and is associated with a variety of diseases that can cause respiratory, digestive and neurological disorders in humans and animals.

这种新冠病毒在进入人类社会的“人传染别人”状态以后，动物向人类传播的那种方式就退居次要的影响力状态，因为“人与人之间传播”的速度，跟着人们密切接触发生率，在城市化的人口密集生活环境当中，是要比动物携带病毒者向人类传播的速度和频率高一万倍以上的。这种情况下，人与人之间的呼吸道传染、身体接触传染都是以人体为“载体”的，新冠病毒在人体内部有潜

伏期，但是在厕所卫生间的化粪池、下水道体系里面，符合了中国政府《新型冠状病毒感染的肺炎公众防护指南》认定的情况：人冠状病毒对热较为敏感，病毒在 4°C 合适维持液中为中等稳定，-60°C 可保存数年，但随着温度的升高，病毒的抵抗力下降，如 HCoV-229E 于 56°C 10 分钟或者 37°C 数小时即可使其丧失感染性。人冠状病毒不耐酸、不耐碱，病毒复制的最适宜 pH 为 7.2。也就是说，没有处理的粪便污水垃圾在化粪池、下水道里面最容易存活、复制，提示我们必须认识到“厕所革命”非常重要，非常及时——只有“厕所作为人居环境改善的基础设施”，才可以把“厕所”、“化粪池”、“下水道”作为生活污染的重灾区，变成杀毒灭菌的主战场之一。

After the new coronavirus entered the "human-to-human" mode of transmission in human society, the animal-to-human mode of transmission receded into a secondary state of influence because the rate of "human-to-human transmission", followed by the incidence of close human contact, is more than 10,000 times higher than the rate and frequency of human-to-human transmission by animal carriers in densely populated urbanized environments. In this case, human-to-human respiratory infections and body contact infections are all using the human body as the "carrier". The new coronavirus has an incubation period in the human body, but in the septic tank and sewer system of the toilet, in line with the Chinese government's "Guidelines for public protection against pneumonia of new coronavirus infections" identified the situation: human coronavirus is more sensitive to heat, the virus is moderately stable in a suitable maintenance fluid at 4 °C in -60 °C it can be kept for several years, but as the temperature increases, the virus resistance decreases, such as HCoV-229E at 56 °C for 10 minutes or 37 °C for several hours will begin to lose its infectivity. The human coronavirus is intolerant of acid and alkaline, and the optimum pH for virus replication is 7.2. In other words, untreated fecal and sewage waste in septic tanks and sewers is most suitable for virus to survive and replicate in, suggesting

that we must realize that the "toilet revolution" is very important and timely - only the "toilet as an infrastructure for improving the human environment", can the "toilet", "septic tank", "sewer" as a major disaster area of life pollution, be changed into one of the main battlefields of sterilization.

我认为厕所革命的含义，应该是“把厕所作为一种人居环境来改善”，直接利害攸关人类的生命健康，也决定防疫、抗疫究竟走向成功还是失败？人类文明已经在 2020 年的新冠肺炎病毒肆虐全世界危机时刻，深刻反省自己的卫生环境就是生存或者死亡的“高压线”，是不可以将就、瞎凑和的得过且过建筑物，而是保护生命线的建筑物。首先，要在人居环境改善的达标方面，毫不犹豫的升级换代全人类关于生存、发展的理念，应该把“人居环境改善、人民幸福感、小康社会”等等转化成为可操作的规范，中国应该成为全世界的好榜样。例如关于“厕所革命”的国家领导人批示很多，可是各级政府主管部门就没有拿出来具体的可操作性标准，国家没有在拨款的同时拿出来可以验证、检查的“厕所建设行业标准”，以至于“厕所革命”受到了假冒伪劣产品的蚕食鲸吞、干扰破坏。

I believe that the meaning of the toilet revolution should be "to improve the toilet as a human habitat", an innovation that has a direct bearing on human life and health and determines whether the prevention and treatment of epidemics will succeed or fail. Human civilization is already reflecting deeply on its own health environment as the "high pressure line" of survival or death in 2020, when the new coronavirus is ravaging the world. Toilet is not a facility to be taken for granted and to be compromised, but a facility that safeguard our lives. First of all, we should not hesitate to upgrade the concept of survival and development for all mankind from merely meeting the standards for improving the human habitat environment, and we should translate "improvement of the human habitat environment, people's sense of well-being and a well-off society" into operational norms, and China should become a leading example for the world. For example,

the national leaders have given many instructions on the "toilet revolution", but the competent government departments at all levels have failed to come up with specific operational standards, and the State has failed to come up with industry standards for toilet construction that can be verified and inspected at the same time as allocating funds, to the extent that the "toilet revolution" has been swallowed up by counterfeit and shoddy products and has been destroyed by interference.

我们回顾中国七十多年来的爱国卫生活动，对于沼气池与厕所改造的关系一直都没有深刻认识清楚，沼气池是绿色新能源，国家长期性给补贴，竟然不愿意把这种专项资金与“厕所革命”的拨款相结合，还有卫生局、卫计委到卫健委的城乡环境卫生治理，以及和环保部门的“环境整治”专项资金也是不愿意和沼气池化粪池一体化技术相结合，行政权威与行政部门利益围绕着特权腐败的运作机制，在蓄意破坏“厕所革命”的尝试。我们现在全国各地所做的厕所革命那些工程，首先就是厕所一定要卫生、安全，也适合于环境保护，不能让厕所成为一种污染源，必须达到杀毒灭菌的“零容忍”基本原则。这样的要求，就需要一个标准文件来表达，这样的标准我们集团公司也正在制定，因为我们已经和国家标准委员会的有关机构取得了联系，我们在申请知识产权保护的专利同时，就把“厕所建设现代化的技术经济与管理标准”考虑了。我们强调指出厕所革命的标准，和厕所革命的专利技术，两者之间是有因果关系的，共同保障“厕所革命”的可操作性与人民幸福相辅相成。这样的专利厕所和我们的专利产品化粪池、沼气池一体化设备，是要与“杀毒灭菌”、“防疫抗疫”、公共卫生标准相结合的，是一个完整的公共安全系统。

We recall China's patriotic sanitation activities over the past 70 years or so, but we have never had a clear understanding of the relationship between biogas digesters and toilet renovation; biogas digesters are a new green energy source, and the State is reluctant to combine such special funds with the allocation of funds for the "toilet revolution", as well as the urban and rural environmental sanitation management of the Health Bureau, the Health and Planning

Commission and the Health and Welfare Commission, and the special funds for "environmental remediation" with environmental protection departments, which are also reluctant to combine with biogas digester septic integration technology. The toilet revolution projects that we are doing throughout the country are, first of all, that toilets must be hygienic, safe and suitable for environmental protection, that toilets must not become a source of pollution and that the basic principle of "zero tolerance" for sterilization must be achieved. Such a requirement needs to be expressed in a standard document, which is also being developed by the group of companies, since we have already contacted the relevant bodies of the National Standards Council and have taken into account the "Techno-Economic and Management Standards for the Modernization of Toilets" in our patent applications for intellectual property protection. We emphasize that there is a causal relationship between the standards of the toilet revolution and the patented technology of the toilet revolution, and that together they guarantee that the operability of the "toilet revolution" and the well-being of the people are mutually reinforcing. Such patented toilets and our patented septic and biogas digesters are integrated with "sterilization", "epidemic prevention" and public health standards, a complete public safety system.

如果我们的“厕所革命”仅仅是走过场的官本位体制行为，只是把厕所看成为一个大小便的用具、私密空间，而没有考虑怎么样处理粪便污水、厨余垃圾等等生活污染？那么，这种在地面上的厕所建筑物设计，就会形成粪便污水垃圾对于周边环境的污染。即便是具体的“厕所建筑物”，也必须保障建筑材料的安全性，以及厕所建筑物抗拒暴风雪、暴风雨等等自然灾害的能力。我国传统的土坯厕所、砖瓦厕所，都是臭气熏人的同时，蛆虫滋生苍蝇蚊子，气味和粪便腐蚀厕所建筑物的情况下，气温对于厕所建筑物材料的影响，是否会产生毒性呢？等等，并没有产生过政府的相应标准，原则上都需要对人体是无害化的。还有厕所里面的照明设置，室内室外不同的厕所

应该有不同的解决方案。尤其是厕所在室外的時候，面对暴风雨的适应能力，需要结构安全，至少是不伤人。

What if our "toilet revolution" was nothing more than an official institutional exercise in the past, where the toilet was seen only as an appliance for urination and defecation, a private space, and no consideration was given to how to deal with fecal sewage, food waste, and other domestic pollution? This above-ground toilet facility design, then, results in the pollution of the surrounding environment by fecal sewage waste. Even for specific "toilet facilities", the safety of construction materials and the ability of toilet facilities to withstand natural disasters such as snowstorms, storms, etc. must be guaranteed. While our traditional adobe toilets and brick toilets are stinky, maggots breed flies and mosquitoes, and odours and feces corrode the toilet facility, is the impact of temperature on the toilet facility materials toxic? Wait a minute, no corresponding governmental standards have ever been produced, all of which in principle need to be harmless to the human body. There's also the lighting setup inside the toilet, which should have different solutions for different toilets indoors and outdoors. Especially when the toilets are outdoors, the ability to adapt in the face of a storm requires structural safety, or at least non-harmful.

在这里，人居环境，首先就是一种“人造环境”，是人类以工业化手段、城市化理念去创造的“非自然的”生存空间，让人类的生活工作感受到了超越大自然给予人们那种茹毛饮血、山洞树杈上居住环境的优越性。可是，人体的生命过程那种新陈代谢机制，并不是人类自己可以使用工业化生产力，进行替代大自然“造物主——上帝”那种安排的。造物主对于大自然物种的新陈代谢、吐故纳新机制，并不是人类自以为是“消灭对方”就可以让自己为所欲为那种逻辑，譬如病毒与人类在 2020 年的生死存亡较量，活下来的病患者并非是能够杀死多少病毒，而是人体免疫力能够把病毒“排出体外”，即“排毒”的能力，让新冠肺炎病毒感染不能终止人体的正常生命过程。这也

是最近五十年来人类最时髦的“排毒养颜”保健品闹剧接连不断地表演，所没有真正的搞清楚人体细胞组织和“毒”之间的关系，纯粹的表面化“人体生命力”就是能够杀死病毒细菌的能力——这是完全彻底的错误观念，是把“敌我矛盾”、阶级斗争、黑白分明的好与坏进行了“故意界定”，违背了“造物主——上帝”的本来真面目：人体不是一种战场，不是外来病毒细菌与人体细胞之间你死我活的“决斗场”，而是人类与大自然彼此交换能量、信息、物资的相对独立系统。人体细胞组织在“造物主——上帝”的安排当中，就是与大自然和睦相处，创造属于人类自己的文明社会生活，并非让人类的“你死我活、非此即彼”意识形态在大千世界拉帮结派、排除异己，而是让人体排毒。这里所谓的“毒”，并非就是“敌人”，并非就是人体一定要消耗自己去“杀毒灭菌”，而是是指对人体有不良影响的物质——尤其是宿便在肠道内的残留。相应的排毒关键，是要治标治本，配合饮食、生活规律、运动乃至心情调节，多管齐下彻底排毒畅通人体生物管道。也就是人体细胞组织不一定对于外来的病毒细菌，最好的方式就是“排出体外”而非在人体细胞组织器官当中厮杀打斗。以至于人体细胞组织器官不会经常性处于紧张状态，而是从容应对，从容的活好你自己。

It is an "unnatural" living space created by human beings through industrialization and urbanization, which allows human beings to feel the superiority of living and working beyond the kind of living environment that nature has given them. However, the metabolic mechanism of the human body's life process is not something that humans themselves can use industrial productivity to replace the "Creator's" arrangement of nature. The Creator of the metabolism of the natural species, the regenerative and replacement mechanism, does not operate on the logic that humans think, where the elimination of others grant one the power to act without restraint. Let's take for example the life and death struggle between human and viruses in 2020, the survival of patients does not rely on how many viruses they killed, but the amount of viruses human immune system can "excrete out of the body", that is, "detoxification" ability, so

that the new coronavirus infection can not terminate the normal life process of the human body. This is also the most fashionable "detoxification and beauty" health care product farce performed one after another over the past fifty years, without really understanding the relationship between the human cells and tissues and "toxin", purely regard the superficial "human life force" as the ability to kill viruses and bacteria - this is a complete and utter misconception. It is a "deliberate segregation" of "enemy and I", class struggle, black and white, and good and evil, which is contrary to the "Creator" true intention: the human body is not a battlefield, not a "dueling ground" between foreign viruses and bacteria and human cells, but a relatively independent system of human exchanging energy, information and materials with nature.

人体细胞组织在“造物主——上帝”的安排当中，就是与大自然和睦相处，创造属于人类自己的文明社会生活，并非让人类的“你死我活、非此即彼”意识形态在大千世界拉帮结派、排除异己，而是让人体排毒。这里所谓的“毒”，并非就是“敌人”，并非就是人体一定要消耗自己去“杀毒灭菌”，而是是指对人体有不良影响的物质——尤其是宿便在肠道内的残留。相应的排毒关键，是要治标治本，配合饮食、生活规律、运动乃至心情调节，多管齐下彻底排毒畅通人体生物管道。也就是人体细胞组织不一定对于外来的病毒细菌，最好的方式就是“排出体外”而非在人体细胞组织器官当中厮杀打斗。以至于人体细胞组织器官不会经常性处于紧张状态，而是从容应对，从容的活好你自己。

In the arrangement of the "Creator", the cellular organization of the human body is to live in harmony with nature and create its own civilized social life, letting the body to detoxify itself, rather than this "you or I" and "live or die" mentality. What is called "toxin" here is not the "enemy" or the fact that the human body must consume itself to "sterilize", but rather the substances that have an adverse effect on the human body - especially the residue in the intestinal tract. The

corresponding key to detoxification is to treat the root cause, with diet, lifestyle, exercise and even mood regulation, a multi-pronged approach thorough detoxification of the body's biological channels. That is, human cells and tissues are not necessarily immune to foreign viruses and bacteria, and the best way to do this is to "expel them out of the body" rather than fight in human cells, tissues and organs. So much so that the cells and tissues of the human body are not constantly in a state of tension, but rather cope with it with ease and live your life with ease.

这个过程的典型案例，就是人体的大小便竟然是农作物生长的最大需求物资，而农作物的成果即粮食蔬菜水果等等食品，竟然又是人类生命的最大维持者，或者说支持者体系。这时候，所谓的毒素，并不是“敌人”，而是在其他领域的宝贵资源，是一种可以干预正常人体生理活动，并破坏人类机体功能的物质，但很可能还是果蔬生产的必需品。这是反对“消灭敌人的逻辑——消灭毒素”那种逻辑的，是要有“怎么样变废为宝”的意识形态。对于人体细胞组织器官来说，内在毒素就有自由基，胆固醇，脂肪，尿酸，乳酸，水毒和淤血。外来毒素就有大气污染，蔬菜中的农药残留，汽车尾气，工业废气，化学药品，辐射，食物中的防腐剂，化妆品中超标的重金属，垃圾食品等现代文明带来的毒副作用，病原微生物。还有人体生命过程的内生之毒：新陈代谢中产生的代谢废物，生气时人体会产生一种酸毒，糖脂肪，蛋白质代谢紊乱所产生的毒素，等等。它们并非在“造物主——上帝”及其大自然当中一无是处，并非就是“敌人”必须被你们人类消灭了，而是要看它们在哪里能够发挥积极作用，给宇宙大千世界贡献良性循环的力量。这是“人类大小便、厕所系统”不支持“人体消灭病毒细菌”的逻辑，也是“人体排泄功能”的高超让人类思想观念里面“仇恨病毒细菌”的逻辑显得荒谬绝伦，显得幼稚可笑。这是人类对于生存环境治理的一种误区，也是理念错误的表现。

A typical example of this process is the fact that the human body's defecation is the greatest need for the growth of crops, and that the fruits of crops, such as food, vegetables and fruits, are the greatest sustainers, or support systems, of human life. At this point, the so-called toxins are not the "enemy", but a valuable

resource in other areas, a substance that can interfere with normal human physiological activity and disrupt the functioning of the human organism, but is probably also essential for fruit and vegetable production. This is against the logic of "elimination of the enemy - elimination of toxins" and the ideology of "how to turn waste into treasure". For the cells and tissues of the human body, the endotoxins are free radicals, cholesterol, fat, uric acid, lactic acid, hydotoxicity and silt. Foreign toxins include air pollution, pesticide residues in vegetables, car exhaust, industrial emissions, chemicals, radiation, preservatives in food, heavy metals in cosmetics, junk food and other toxic side effects of modern civilization, pathogenic microorganisms. Then there are the endogenous toxins of the human life process: metabolic waste produced in the metabolism, the body produces an acidic toxin when angry, sugars and fats, toxins produced by disorders of protein metabolism, etc. It is not that they are useless among the "Creator" and his nature, or that the "enemy" must be eliminated by you, the human race, but that it is up to them where they can play a positive role and contribute to the positive circle of the universe. This is the logic of the "human defecation and toilet system" that does not support the "human body's elimination of viruses and bacteria", and the superiority of the "human excretion function" that makes the logic of the "hate virus and bacteria" in the human mind seem absurd and childish. This is a misconception of human governance of the living environment and a manifestation of conceptual error.

正是如此的人类社会文明理念，才提示人们的“厕所革命”，是必须站在现代化人居环境系统的高度，建立医院和家庭的卫生健康标准基础上的厕所体系，要求厕所必须包括化粪池、沼气池、下水道系统，要求卫生间（厕所）真正的能够杀毒灭菌，给予人体健康提供最切近的干净卫生环境。现有的“厕所革命”里边有一个实质性的问题，就是我们国家给农户提供补贴支持，建设的

“厕所革命”那种化粪池，并没有沼气池变废为宝的功能，也不能杀毒灭菌，反而是污染水资源的下水道里面罪魁祸首。中国各级政府现在强力推行的“厕所建筑物结构”设计方案，无论三格式厕所，还是双瓮式的厕所，都是没有把化粪池和沼气池一体化的。尽管国家农业部发文件推行三格式化粪池并没有厌氧菌发酵的功能，也不是沼气池与化粪池一体化的，但是我们的人居环境工程作为科技把关的“人造建筑物”，就要注重于推崇沼气池附带化粪池的具有厌氧菌发酵功能的厕所，这是把粪便污水垃圾进行无害化处理的重中之重工作。这种沼气池与化粪池一体化的设置，只能是在两立方米左右的厕所沼气池容量空间范围内，这种沼气池与化粪池一体化的设计制造方式，虽然把化粪池与沼气池有分割的相互独立空间，却是在总体结构上处于同一个壳子整体，目的就是温度平衡，互相报团取暖而有利于厌氧菌发酵。这也对于农户家庭的建筑物地下设施密度进行控制，更有利于施工成本降低。但是对于人口密集的城市住宅楼居民小区来说，都是专门的高楼大厦化粪池空间，和专门的沼气池发酵空间，两者之间的结构和功能是明确的不一样了。如果说我们把它与农户使用的沼气池、化粪池都捏到同一个类型里面的话，必然的第一是不符合事实，第二个是我们的专利保护就搞的都没办法维权了，不利于保护具有可操作性的发明创造，很容易让投机取巧的专利申请滥竽充数，剽窃真正的科学技术成果，让李鬼打败李逵，导致中国数量级庞大的专利技术都有粗枝大叶的缺陷，都有许许多多的捏造奇迹之类致命伤，使得货真价实的发明创造申请专利保护以后，反而就容易被别人侵权剽窃。

It is this concept of civilization in human society that suggests that the "toilet revolution" must be based on the establishment of a toilet system that is based on the modern system of human habitation and health standards in hospitals and homes, that requires toilets to include septic, biogas and sewerage systems, that requires toilets to be genuinely sterilizable and to provide the upmost clean sanitary environment for human health. One of the substantive problems with the existing "toilet revolution" is that the septic tanks built by our country to support farmers with subsidies do not have the function of turning biogas into waste, nor do they sterilize and kill toxins, but are instead the culprits in the sewers that

pollute water resources. The "building structure of toilets" design scheme, which is now strongly promoted by the Chinese Government at all levels, does not integrate septic and biogas tanks, whether it is a three-form toilet or a double urn toilet. Although the Ministry of Agriculture issued a document to implement the three-form septic tank does not have the function of anaerobic fermentation, nor is the integration of biogas and septic tank, but our environmental engineering as a scientific and technological gatekeeper of "man-made buildings", we should focus on promoting the biogas tank with septic tank with anaerobic fermentation function of the toilet, which is the most important work of the manure sewage waste for harmless treatment. This integrated biogas digester and septic tank can only be set up within the capacity of a toilet biogas digester of about two cubic metres, which is designed and manufactured in such a way that although the septic tank and the biogas digester are compartmentalized into separate spaces, they are structurally in the same shell, with the aim of balancing the temperature, warming each other up and facilitating anaerobic fermentation. This also controls the density of underground facilities in buildings for farm households, which is more conducive to lower construction costs. But for densely populated urban residential neighborhoods, there is a clear difference in structure and function between a dedicated septic space in a high-rise building and a dedicated digester digester space. If we say it and the farmers use the biogas digester, septic tank are all pinched into the same type of, inevitably the first is not the truth, the second is our patent protection is not able to defend the right, is not conducive to the protection of the inventions with operability, it is easy for the speculative patent application to include in the number, plagiarism of the real scientific and technological achievements, let Li ghosts beat Li Kui, resulting in China's huge

patent technology has a huge number of defects, there are many fabricated miracles and other fatal injuries, so that the real inventions to apply for patent protection, but it is easy for others to infringe and steal.

这就是欧美发达国家一直都在批评中国特色的专利技术库存里面真假难辨，专利技术市场发生太多太多的坑蒙拐骗偷之类违法犯罪行为，毁坏了中国的专利制度和专利保护机制，也破坏了知识产权的诚实守信底线。要比这一切更深层次的破坏性，就是专利权的混乱状态，使得打着中国特色专利的旗号剽窃其他的专利技术，利用中国专利保护的纸上谈兵致命伤，去玩弄专利而申请专利，实质上就是把“专利权及其技术”作为利用“国家权威”替企业和个人“背书信用”，或者说“可信度”攀附官本位体制的一种手段。这一切阴暗面让欧美发达国家的企业在中国牢骚满腹，同时也导致了中国特色的专利权、知识产权登记制度、公告流程、专利权保护都已经在没有“技术打假”的情况下，让任何人按照专利权内容都没办法做出来相应的技术产品，把中国特色的专利制度变成了假冒伪劣的典型案列。这种情况下，我们的专家团队坚持富勒烯聚磷酸二钠分子技术是美国专利权，而把关于“厕所革命”的发明专利申请也考虑在全世界的其他地方，认为不适宜在中国的专利权名存实亡、劣币驱逐良币而不能真正的保护“技术知识产权”，不能在制度层面把法律法规贯彻落实的情况下，完全彻底的依赖于中国。我们团队的方式方法，是一方面获得国际专利，另一方面还是为了争取中国特色的政府补贴支持“厕所革命”工程，就必须在中国大陆获得专利权；何况，我们对于发展中国家已经是准备好了免费使用专利，不打算斤斤计较。

This is why developed countries in Europe and the United States have been criticizing the patent technology inventory with Chinese characteristics, it is difficult to distinguish between true and false. The patent technology market is saturated with illegal and criminal acts such as pit, deception and theft, which has destroyed China's patent system and patent protection mechanism, and also damaged the bottom line of the honesty and trustworthiness of its intellectual property rights. To be more destructive than all this, the chaotic state of patent rights has led to the plagiarism of other patented technologies under the banner of

patents with Chinese characteristics, the use of Chinese patent protection to play with patents and apply for patents, in essence, the use of "patent rights and technologies" as a means to use "state authority" to "endorse credit" or "credibility" for enterprises and individuals to ascend the official system. The dark side of all this has made the enterprises of developed countries in Europe and the United States in China complain a lot, and at the same time, it has also led to the patent right, intellectual property registration system, announcement process and patent protection with Chinese characteristics have all been without "technical counterfeiting", so that no one can make the corresponding technical products according to the patent rights, turning the patent system with Chinese characteristics into a typical case of counterfeiting and inferior quality. Under these circumstances, our team of experts insists that the fullerene disodium phosphonate molecular technology is a U.S. patent, and considers the patent application for the invention of the "toilet revolution" in other parts of the world, believing that it is inappropriate for the patent right to exist in China in name only, and that bad coin expels good coin without truly protecting the "technical intellectual property rights", and cannot fully rely on China to implement the laws and regulations at the institutional level. Our team's approach is to obtain international patents on the one hand, and to obtain government subsidies with Chinese characteristics to support the "toilet revolution" project on the other hand, we must obtain patents in mainland China; moreover, we are ready to give free licensing to developing countries.

当然，有关“厕所改造”、“厕所革命”的专利权，不单纯是大小便器具及其空间的设计要求，更重要的是给排水系统、下水道体系及其地下管廊的设计规范，是核心技术在于“针对砖混结构建筑物二百多年来的渗漏顽疾”，强化材料科技的升级换代，尤其是建筑结构的系统化缺陷决定

了的化粪池先天不足，必须要把沼气池与化粪池相结合，实施分级处理。最重要的是，按照厕所改造是为了解决“旱厕”问题，厕所革命是为了突出“节约用水”的要求，总体上进行生活环境的保护达标，是一个庞大的系统工程。所以，要和中国的农业农村部、国家卫健委官方网站上面关于厕所革命这方面的一些具体文件，因为它是国家法令性质的政策解读，能够避免有关的市场不诚实守信之类官商勾结敏感性，也会涉及到新的敏感性问题，这就是中国的“厕所革命”并没有真正的标准，需要我们公司自己首先替政府设计这样的“厕所革命标准”，并且把企业标准提升成为行业标准、地方省市自治区标准以及国家标准。

Of course, the patent rights related to "toilet reform" and "toilet revolution", include not only the design requirements of urinary and faecal appliances and their space, but more importantly, the design specifications for the drainage system, sewerage system and its underground pipelines, is the core technology lies in the improvement of "the brick structure of buildings for more than 200 years of leakage" by strengthening and upgrading material technology, especially the systematic deficiencies of the building structure determined by the inherent deficiencies of the septic tank, which can only be remedied by the combination of biogas digester with septic tanks, together with the implementation of classification treatment. Most importantly, toilet reform is to solve the problem of "dry toilets", while the toilet revolution is to highlight the requirement of "water conservation", and the overall protection of the living environment to meet the standard is a huge systematic project. Therefore, we have to work with the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Work of the Chinese government and the official website of the National Health Care Commission on some specific documents about the toilet revolution, because it is a policy interpretation of the nature of the national decree, which can avoid the relevant market dishonesty and trustworthiness and other sensitive issues of collusion between government and business, and also

involves new sensitive issues, which is why there is no real standard for the "toilet revolution" in China. We need our own company to design such a "toilet revolution standard" for the government first, and to raise the corporate standard to an industry standard, and eventually to local, provincial, municipal, and national standards.

我认为厕所革命的含义，应该是“把厕所作为一种人居环境来改善”，要在环境保护的无害化处理粪便污水处理方面拥有达标的理念，应该把“政策”及其愿景转化成为可操作的规范。这方面我们现在全国各地所做的厕所革命那些工程，首先就是厕所一定要卫生、安全，也适合于环境保护，不能让厕所成为一种污染源。

这样的要求就需要一个标准文件来表达，这样的标准我们光彩集团和保定广顺公司也正在制定，因为我们已经和国家标准委员会的有关机构取得联系了，你们专利代理公司现在代理我们的专利申请本身不管这个内容，可是这两者之间是有关系的，我们要给你把这些情况说明一下，有利于你们起草相应的专利文件。我们是一定要设计好“厕所革命”的相应发明专利，这样的专利厕所和我们的专利产品化粪池、沼气池是一体化的，是一个完整的系统。如果我们的“厕所革命”仅仅是考虑一个厕所的大小使用具，没有考虑怎么样处理粪便污水，那么这个地面上的厕所建筑物设计，就会形成粪便污水对于环境的污染。即便是具体的“厕所建筑物”，也必须保障建筑材料的安全性，以及厕所建筑物抗拒暴风雪、暴风雨等等自然灾害的能力。我国传统的土坯厕所、砖瓦厕所，都是臭气熏人的同时，蛆虫滋生苍蝇蚊子，气味和粪便腐蚀厕所建筑物的情况下，气温对于厕所建筑物材料的影响，是否会产生毒性呢？等等，并没有产生过政府的相应标准，原则上都需要对人体是无害化的。还有厕所里面的照明设置，室内室外不同的厕所应该有不同解决方案。尤其是厕所在室外的时候，面对暴风雨的适应能力，需要结构安全，至少是不伤人。

I think the meaning of the toilet revolution should be to "improve the toilet as a human living environment", to have the concept of environmental protection in the environmentally sound treatment of faeces and sewage treatment to meet the

standard, should be "policy" and its vision into an operational norm. In this regard, the toilet revolution projects that we are doing across the country are, first of all, that toilets must be hygienic, safe and suitable for environmental protection, and must not be allowed to become a source of pollution. Such a requirement requires a standard document to express it, and such a standard is also being developed by the Guangcai Group and Baoding Guangshun Company. We have already contacted the relevant bodies of the National Standards Committee, and your patent agency is now representing our patent application itself regardless of the content, but there is a relationship between the two. We must design the corresponding invention patent for the "toilet revolution", so that the patented toilet and our patented product septic tank and biogas digester are integrated, a complete system. If our "toilet revolution" only considers a toilet's appliances and disregard how to treat fecal sewage, then the design of the above-ground toilet facility will result in fecal sewage pollution of the environment. Even for specific "toilet buildings", the safety of construction materials and the ability of toilet buildings to withstand natural disasters such as snowstorms, storms, etc. must be guaranteed. While our traditional adobe toilets and brick toilets are stinky, maggots breed flies and mosquitoes, and odors and feces corrode the toilet facility, is the impact of temperature on the toilet building materials toxic? Wait a minute, no corresponding governmental standards have ever been produced, all of which in principle need to be harmless to the human body. There's also the lighting setup inside the toilet, which should have different solutions for different toilets indoors and outdoors. Especially when the toilets are outdoors, the ability to adapt in the face of a storm requires structural safety, or at least non-harmful.

我们应该肯定中国的环境治理有进步，至少是现在的“厕所革命”在旅游景区一马当先，改变了厕所的脏乱差表面现象，关键是如厕的人们还没有冲厕所的好习惯，特别是坐便器要比蹲便器的传染皮肤病、细菌传染病之类风险更高一些。这就是说，公共场所也伴随着环境卫生的整治，环卫工人下功夫解决了表面上问题，依然如故的没有能够解决厕所粪便、污水、垃圾对于环境污染的消极影响。正是如此，我们的再生塑料沼气池、化粪池作为“厕所革命”的实质性隐蔽工程，显得越来越重要。现在的症结在于许多国家官方并没有认识到“厕所应该具有处理粪便污水垃圾成为无害化物质”的重要性，科技企业领域也没有关于居家生活的厕所、公共厕所、机关单位厕所等服务设施的发明专利，关于厕所就仿佛是不能进入专利技术行列的下九流，太低级了而在专利发明层面不入流。这是错误的观念，人类文明的标志性建筑物之一，就是厕所的文明程度怎么样，二十世纪最重要的卫生间发明创造，就是抽水马桶完全彻底的改变了厕所臭味的千百年糟糕状态。我们中国人对于厕所的升级换代认识，来自于高楼大厦的卫生间、洗手间，让每个人每天都要上厕所的时候切身体会一下什么是文明？传统的中国厕所没有怎么样考虑照明灯的问题，我们首先就应该解决照明灯的问题。我们集团公司的厕所发明专利当中，就是有一个太阳能的声控灯。这个太阳能灯具上面，有个太阳能面板在厕所的顶棚外面顶部，就像现在普遍性的路灯是太阳能面板解决能源问题一样。我们的厕所发明专利里面，照明灯的太阳能面板非常物美价廉，安全性在于电压是36伏以下的，无论如何都不会发生漏电击伤人的事件，即便是漏电了都不存在安全问题。这个灯是声控的，每当有人上厕所的话，这个灯就会亮。如厕的人离开了的时候，照明灯就会自动熄灭，方便也周到和节能。

We should acknowledge that China's environmental governance has made progress, at least now that the "toilet revolution" has taken the lead in tourist attractions and changed the surface of the dirty and messy toilets, the key is that people who go to the toilet do not yet have the good habit of flushing the toilet, especially the toilet seat is at a higher risk of infecting skin diseases and bacterial infections than the squat toilet. That is to say, public places are also accompanied by environmental sanitation remediation, sanitation workers have worked hard to

solve the superficial problems, but still have not been able to solve the negative impact of toilet feces, sewage, garbage on environmental pollution. That is why our recycled plastic biogas digesters and septic tanks are becoming increasingly important as substantial covert projects in the "toilet revolution". The problem is that many countries do not recognize the importance of "toilets should have the ability to treat faecal waste and sewage into harmless substances", and there are no patents for the invention of toilets, public toilets, institutional toilets, and other services in the field of science and technology enterprises, as if the toilets are not patentable technology. It is the misconception that one of the iconic facility of human civilization is how civilized the toilet is, and the most important bathroom invention of the twentieth century was the flush toilet that completely revolutionized the thousand-year awful state of toilet stench. We Chinese people's awareness of the upgrade of the toilet comes from the high rise of the toilet and bathrooms in building complexes, so that everyone who has to go to the toilet every day can understand what civilization means. Traditional Chinese toilets don't have much to think about in terms of lighting, and we should address the issue of lighting in the first place. One of our group company's patents for toilet inventions is a solar-powered, voice-activated light. Above this solar luminaire, there is a solar panel on top of the outside of the ceiling of the toilet, just as the ubiquitous street light is now a solar panel to solve energy problems. In our toilet invention patent, the solar panel of the light is very good price, the safety is that the voltage is below 36 volts, in any case, there will be no leakage of electricity to injure people, even if the leakage does not exist safety problems. This light is voice-activated and will come on whenever someone goes to the bathroom. The lights

automatically go off when the person leaving the toilet, which is convenient, thoughtful and energy efficient.

现有的中国农村现代化厕所最大的设施，就是抽水马桶。而抽水马桶在城市化运动当中大规模浪费水资源，尽管抽水马桶本身也是 20 世纪的一大发明，因为有个回流管，就保证了厕所的大小便臭味不会冲上来熏人。但是，抽水马桶不能形成对于粪便污水垃圾的处理能力，还造成了更多的粪便污水垃圾去污染环境。我们的发明专利，是突出了使用蹲便器，不像抽水马桶被多人使用的时候，就会发生泌尿系统的交叉感染，但是蹲便器也要保证不会发生大小便的臭味冲上来熏人之类情况，这就是我们集团公司的再生塑料沼气池，在抽水马桶下面的厌氧菌发酵处理粪便、污水、垃圾的成功率，产生了决定性的作用。我们的厕所化粪池，是连着沼气池的，能够实现厌氧菌发酵除掉臭味的目标要求。我们的再生塑料化粪池、沼气池适用于“厕所革命”，设计合理并且经过了数以万计的实践检验以后，就能够解决厕所本身的除臭味、除异味问题，而且杀菌。因为厌氧菌发酵充分的话，就把大肠杆菌等威胁人类健康的有害菌都杀死了。事实上，抽水马桶类型的坐便器只是让厕所下面的臭气不上来，但是没有杀死大肠杆菌这一类有害菌的能力，而我们的厕所发明专利，却是一个物美价廉的蹲便器。一个抽水马桶坐便器的价格，相当于蹲便器的十倍以上，陶瓷的抽水马桶坐便器价格都在 600 元人民币以上，而我们发明专利当中的蹲便器，就只有 70 元钱人民币，物美价廉的原因之一是我们使用废旧塑料来制造蹲便器。

The largest modern toilet facility available in rural China is the flush toilet. The flush toilet is a massive waste of water resources in the urbanization movement, although the flush toilet itself is a major invention of the 20th century, because there is a backflow pipe, which ensures that the stench of the toilet does not flush up. However, flush toilets do not form the capacity to treat fecal sewage waste, and also create more fecal sewage waste to pollute the environment. The patent of our invention highlights the fact that the use of a squatting toilet is not like the cross-infection of the urinary system that occurs when the toilet is used by multiple people, but the squatting toilet must also ensure that the odor of urine

and faeces does not flush up and smother people. This is where the success rate of our Group's recycled plastic biogas digester that treats faeces, sewage and garbage under the toilet with the fermentation of anaerobic bacteria plays a decisive role. Our toilet septic tank, which is connected to a biogas digester, is able to achieve the target requirement of anaerobic bacterial fermentation to remove odor. Our recycled plastic septic tanks and biogas digesters are suitable for the "toilet revolution", and after a rational design and tens of thousands of years of experience, they can solve the problem of deodorization, odor removal, and sterilization of the toilet itself. Because anaerobic bacteria, if fermented sufficiently, kill off harmful bacteria like *E. coli* that threaten human health. In fact, a flush toilet type toilet just keeps the stench out from under the toilet, but doesn't have the ability to kill harmful bacteria like *E. coli*, while our patented toilet invention is an inexpensive squat toilet. The price of a flush toilet seat is equivalent to more than ten times the price of a squat toilet, ceramic flush toilet seat prices are above 600 yuan, while we invented the patent squat toilet, only 70 yuan, one of the reasons for the good price is that we use waste plastic to make squat toilet.

我们的厕所发明专利对于“厕所”进行了重新定义，那就是“解决大小便的独立空间，并且能够及时性的就近处理大小便，以防止粪便污水垃圾污染环境的完整性建筑物系统”，绝不是仅限于让大小便有一个实施空间那么简单化。我们的“厕所发明专利”是把大小便器具与化粪池、沼气池直截了当地连接成为一个系统化的设施，在厕所系统里面就能同步进行粪便污水垃圾处理，让厌氧菌发酵把粪便污水垃圾(卫生巾、烟头之类的垃圾)，以及住宅里面的餐厨垃圾、房屋周围和阳台上的花卉残枝败叶、植物秸秆等等包括卫生纸放在一起，在化粪池和沼气池里面进行厌氧菌发酵处理，排出来的沼气是绿色新能源可以做饭、烧开水、洗澡、取暖、照明等等，沼渣沼液是无害化的有机肥，可以直接灌溉农作物以及家庭养育的花花草草和城市绿化带等等，也可以罐装沼渣、灌装沼液而在市场上出售。这种情况下，从化粪池和沼气池进入下水道的排放物，就是没有污

染的中水和小颗粒，就像全世界的环境保护典范北欧国家，以及美国、日本、新西兰、韩国、澳大利亚等国家，都不允许下水道成为排污的黑洞。

Our patent for toilet invention redefines "toilet" as "a complete building system that solves the problem of a separate space for urination and faeces, and can treat urine and faeces in a timely manner and in close proximity to prevent contamination of the environment with faecal waste", not simply a space for urination and faeces. Our "Patent for Toilet Invention" is a systematic facility that connects the urinary and faecal apparatus directly to the septic tank and biogas digester and allows the simultaneous treatment of faecal and sewage waste (sanitary napkins, cigarette butts, etc.), as well as kitchen waste from the house, flowers, leaves, plant stalks, etc., including toilet paper, in the septic tank and biogas digester. In this case, the discharges from septic and biogas digesters into the sewers are unpolluted medium water and small particles, just as the Nordic countries, the world's model for environmental protection, as well as the United States, Japan, New Zealand, South Korea, Australia and others, do not allow sewers to become black holes for sewage.

按照全世界的环境保护底线共识，下水道和排污通道是两码事，城乡居民区的下水道只能排雨水和中水，不应该排污。这是解决人居环境的住宅里面防止生活污染的行之有效方案，厕所作为人类生活最具有污染环境消极作用的空间，我们还不能使用“好氧菌”而争夺人类所需要的氧气，只能是使用厌氧菌发酵处理粪便污水和餐厨垃圾等等生活废弃物。这样的环保类型住宅建筑物配套设施，把垃圾粪便和其他的生活垃圾污水通过充分的发酵以后，就已经没有了污染，才可以让它排放进入下水道。这样一来，我们对下水道和整个城乡排污体系，以及住宅楼的给排水体系，都有了一个系统化的改造和提升。当然，这里面最大的麻烦，就是一定要把洗涤剂含着碱性物质的洗澡水、刷锅水、洗菜水等等，和餐厨垃圾、人畜粪便分开来处理，而且在住宅楼的管道设计上是不同的路径，区别对待。

According to the worldwide consensus on the bottom line of environmental protection, sewerage and drainage channels are two different things, and sewers in urban and rural settlements can only discharge rainwater and medium water, not sewage. This is a proven solution to prevent living pollution in the residential environment, the toilet as the most negative space for human life to pollute the environment, we can not yet use "aerobic bacteria" to compete for the oxygen needed by humans, only anaerobic fermentation to treat fecal sewage, kitchen waste and other household waste. This environmentally friendly type of residential building is equipped with facilities that allow for the discharge of garbage, feces and other domestic waste water into the sewer only after it has been fully fermented. In this way, we have a systematic renovation and upgrading of the sewerage and the entire urban and rural sewage system, as well as the drainage system for residential buildings. Of course, the biggest trouble in this is that the detergent containing alkaline bath water, brush pot water, dishwashing water, etc. must be treated separately from kitchen waste, human and animal manure, and in the residential building plumbing design is a different path, different treatment.

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